

13TH INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM ON FRONTIERS IN BIOMEDICAL
POLYMERS

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

19-23 MAY, 2019

PUERTO DE LA CRUZ, CANARY ISLAND (SPAIN)

FBPS2019

13TH INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM ON FRONTIERS IN BIOMEDICAL POLYMERS

PUERTO DE LA CRUZ, CANARY ISLAND (SPAIN) 19-23 MAY, 2019

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Welcome Message from the FBPS 2019 Chair

Julio San Román del Barrio

Dear Friends and colleagues. The organizing committee of the series Frontiers in Biomedical Polymers constituted by David Kaplan, Claudio Migliaresi, Teruo Okano, Daniel Cohn, Rui Reis and myself, welcome everybody to attend the 13th edition of the International Symposium on Frontiers in Biomedical Polymers, that will be held in Puerto de la Cruz, Tenerife , Canary Islands, the dates 19 – 23th May 2019.

The participation of excellent professionals and experts in the area gives to the symposium a very high quality and the guarantee of the relevant participation with presentation of the most interesting advances in this important field for the development of Regenerative Medicine, Tissue Engineering, Drug Delivery Systems and Controlled Release of bioactive compounds.

We thank the support of International Institutions, European Society for Biomaterials (ESB), European Polymer Federation (EPF), Spanish Royal Society of Chemistry (RSEQ), Network Centre for Biomedical Research (CIBER-BBN), Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), and the pharmaceutical companies ALODIA FARMACEUTICA and ADVENTIA.

We have prepared a very dense and intense program, due to the high participation of researchers of the highest level coming from all over the world. We hope that all of you will actively participate and enjoy not only the scientific papers, but also the opportunity to get in touch with friends in this carefully chosen site that was selected to enjoy the beautiful village of Puerto de la Cruz, and the sea side location of the hotel. We have to acknowledge the efforts of the local organizing committee and the young people of the Group of Biomaterials of the CSIC for their contribution in the organization of the congress and the design of the scientific sessions that we hope will be of interest to all the participants.

You are invited to participate actively in the discussion of the presentations and posters that will be exhibited in the same room of the presentations during the whole symposium.

WELCOME TO FBPS 2019

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Julio San Román del Barrio". The signature is written in a cursive style and is underlined.

Julio San Román del Barrio
Chair, FBPS 2019 Spain

Instructions for presenters & moderators

Speakers are kindly requested to hand in their presentation (USB-key) at least two (2) hours before their scheduled presentation time. If your presentation is scheduled early in the morning, you are kindly requested to hand in your presentation the day before.

All versions of MS PowerPoint are accepted. If you are using embedded video clips in your presentation, please remember to submit video files separately. The following audiovisual equipment will be available for all presenters:

- ✓ Laptop
- ✓ Data video projector (PowerPoint presentations)
- ✓ Laser pointer
- ✓ Microphones

Oral Presentations

To ensure that all the sessions run smoothly, Oral Presenters are kindly requested to read the following instructions:

- ✓ Speakers are requested to be in the session room 10 minutes before the start of the session and introduce themselves to the chairs of the session.
- ✓ Each presentation has been assigned 15 minutes, 12 minutes for the presentation and 3 minutes for questions and answers (Oral presentations); 20 minutes, 17 minutes for the presentation and 3 minutes for questions and answers (Keynote presentations) and 30 minutes, 27 minutes for the presentation and 3 minutes for questions and answers (Plenary presentations)
- ✓ Please check the schedule carefully for your session time and order of presentations.
- ✓ The chairperson will monitor your presentation time-keeping.
- ✓ All presentations should be in PowerPoint.
- ✓ Please check all your videos run properly with the support team before your presentation.
- ✓ Speakers will be provided with a wireless microphone and a laser pointer for use in their presentations.
- ✓ Speakers are requested to familiarize themselves with the room prior to the presentation.

Poster Presentations

Two designated Poster Areas will be located at session room.

All posters should be formatted vertically, of standard A0 (120cm x 84cm) size. During the conference, poster presenters are responsible for attaching their poster to their assigned poster panel. Pins and tacks will be provided from the Poster Area Helpdesk operating throughout the duration of the conference.

Poster panels will be arranged numerically and organized by thematic area. Posters should be mounted on the appropriately numbered board in the first day of the conference.

Any posters not collected at the end of the conference will be discarded. To allow easier identification of the author, we suggest you include a photograph (ideally cm x 9 cm) on the poster header. It is also a good idea to pin an envelope to the bottom of the board for the receipt of business cards and messages and/or make mini copies of your poster which can be taken away by other delegates.

There will be three official breaks when delegates will be directed to the Poster Areas to view posters. Please ensure that you are present at your poster during these times:

- ✓ Monday, May 20, 15:00-16:00
- ✓ Tuesday, May 21, 15:00-16:00
- ✓ Wednesday, May 22, 15:00-16:00

Organizing Committee

Julio San Román (Chair)

Blanca Vazquez (Co-Chair)

Luis García-Fernández (Scientific Secretary)

Maria Rosa Aguilar

Luis Rojo

Luis Rodriguez-Lorenzo

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Araceli Delgado

Eva Espinosa

María Puertas

Ana Mora

Gloria Pontes

Miguel Huerta

Gerardo Asensio

Dainel Fernández

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Sunday 19 th	
12:00 – 15:30	Registration open
15:30 - 16:00	Welcome and Opening Remarks
16:00 - 16:30	PL-1 Buddy Ratner
16:30 - 16:50	KN-1 Dirk Grijpma
16:50 - 17:10	KN-2 Manuel Toledano
17:10 - 17:30	KN-3 Elisabeth Engel
17:30 - 17:45	O-1 Emmanuelle Marie
17:45 - 18:00	O-2 Alicia Fernández-Colino
18:00 - 18:15	O-3 Mark Grinstaff
18:15 - 18:30	O-4 Benjamin Nottelet
18:30 - 18:45	O-5 Tali Tavor Re'em
19:30 - 20:30	Welcome Party

Session I
Chair: Julio San Román

Monday 20th			
8:30 - 9:00	PL-2	Anthony S. Weiss	Session II Chair: Rui Reis
9:00 - 9:20	KN-4	Angel Licea-Claverie	
9:20 - 9:40	KN-5	Nicolas Blanchemain	
9:40 - 10:00	KN-6	Bárbara Pérez-Köhler	
10:00 - 10:15	O-6	Sergio Acosta	
10:15 - 10:30	O-7	Isabelle Texier	
10:30 - 10:45	O-8	Ana Lopez Periago	
10:45 - 11:00	O-9	Juan González	
COFFEE BREAK + POSTERS			
11:30-11:50	KN-7	J. Carlos Rodríguez-Cabello	Session III Chair: C. Migliaresi
11:50 - 12:10	KN-8	Ana Oliveira	
12:10 - 12:30	KN-9	Andreas Lendlein	
12:30-12:50	KN-10	María Jesús Vicent	
12:50 - 13:05	O-10	Bernard Martel	
13:05 - 13:20	O-11	Matthias Gabriel	
13:20 - 13:35	O-12	Ali Aboudzadeh	
LUNCH + POSTERS			
16:00 - 16:30	PL-3	Kazunari Akiyoshi	Session IV Chair: Daniel Cohn
16:30 - 16:50	KN-11	Manuela E. Gomes	
16:50 - 17:10	KN-12	Martijn van Griensven	
17:10 - 17:30	KN-13	Matilde Alonso	
17:30 - 17:45	O-13	Jacek Wychowaniec	
17:45 - 18:00	O-14	Costas Kiparissides	
18:00 - 18:15	O-15	Malgorzata Wlodarczyk-Biegun	
18:15 - 18:30	O-16	M. Virginia Rivero	
18:30-18:45	O-17	Hadda Zebiri	
18:45-19:00	O-18	Julieta Paez	

Tuesday 21st			
8:30 - 9:00	PL-4	Abhay Pandit	Session V Chair: Andres García
9:00 - 9:20	KN-14	João F Mano	
9:20 - 9:40	KN-15	Aránzazu del Campo	
9:40 - 10:00	KN-16	José Vidal-Gancedo	
10:00 - 10:15	O-19	Husam Younes	
10:15 - 10:30	O-20	Natalia Davidenko	
10:30 - 10:45	O-21	Noo Li Jeon	
10:45 - 11:00	O-22	Ana Mora-Boza	
COFFEE BREAK + POSTERS			
11:30-11:50	KN-17	Antonio Martínez-Richa	Session VI Chair: Buddy Ratner
11:50 - 12:10	KN-18	Vamsi Yadavalli	
12:10 - 12:30	KN-19	Antonella Motta	
12:30-12:50	KN-20	Ugo D'Amora	
12:50 - 13:05	O-23	Miguel González Pérez	
13:05 - 13:20	O-24	Verónica Luque-Agudo	
13:20 - 13:35	O-25	Helene Van Den Berghe	
LUNCH + POSTERS			
16:00 - 16:30	PL-5	Andres J. García	Session VII Chair: M.Jesús Vicent
16:30 - 16:50	KN-21	Thomas Groth	
16:50 - 17:10	KN-22	Nuno Neves	
17:10 - 17:30	KN-23	Michelle LaPlaca	
17:30 - 17:45	O-26	Judith Feitosa	
17:45 - 18:00	O-27	Malo Dufay	
18:00 - 18:15	O-28	Leire Ruiz Rubio	
18:15 - 18:30	O-29	Muhammad Muhammad	
20:00 - 23:00	Conference Dinner		

Wednesday 22nd			
8:30 - 9:00	PL-6	Yasuhiko Tabata	Session VIII Chair: Thomas Groth
9:00 - 9:20	KN-24	Sanjukta Deb	
9:20 - 9:40	KN-25	Marcelo Calderón	
9:40 - 10:00	KN-26	F. Javier De la Mata	
10:00 - 10:15	O-30	Petr Chytil	
10:15 - 10:30	O-31	Shardul Bhusari	
10:30 - 10:45	O-32	Diego Velasco	
10:45 - 11:00	O-33	Samuel Pearson	
COFFEE BREAK + POSTERS			
11:30-11:50	KN-27	Conrado Aparicio	Session IX Chair: Ana Oliveira
11:50 - 12:10	KN-28	Michel Vert	
12:10 - 12:30	KN-29	Rodrigo Silveira Vieira	
12:30-12:50	KN-30	Claudio Migliaresi	
12:50 - 13:05	O-34	Eva Espinosa-Cano	
13:05 - 13:20	O-35	Laurent Leclercq	
13:20 - 13:35	O-36	Petr Humpolicek	
LUNCH + POSTERS			
16:00 - 16:30	PL-7	David Kaplan	Session X Chair: J. Carlos Rodríguez
16:30 - 16:50	KN-31	Roberto Olayo	
16:50 - 17:10	KN-32	Giuseppe Battaglia	
17:10 - 17:30	KN-33	Julio Suay	
17:30 - 17:45	O-37	Raúl Fontelo Rodríguez	
17:45 - 18:00	O-38	Beatrice Labat	
18:00 - 18:15	O-39	Felix Reisbeck	
18:15 - 18:30	O-40	Inmaculada Aranz	

Thursday 23 rd			
8:30 - 9:00	PL-8	Joachim Kohn	Session XI Chair: M. van Griensven
9:00 - 9:20	KN-34	Auxiliadora Prieto Jiménez	
9:20 - 9:40	KN-35	M. Rosa Aguilar	
9:40 - 10:00	KN-36	Francisco Goycoolea	
10:00 - 10:15	O-41	María Puertas Bartolomé	
10:15 - 10:30	O-42	Anna Herrmann	
10:30 - 10:45	O-43	Gloria María Pontes Quero	
10:45 - 11:00	O-44	Araceli Delgado	
COFFEE BREAK + POSTERS			
11:30-11:50	KN-37	Daniel Cohn	Session XII Chair: David Kaplan
11:50 - 12:10	KN-38	Alejandro Sosnik	
12:10 - 12:30	KN-39	Gilson Khang	
12:30-12:50	KN-40	Luis Rojo	
12:50 - 13:05	O-45	Binh T. Mai	
13:05 - 13:20	O-46	Guzmán Carissimi	
13:20 - 13:35	O-47	Soyoun Jang	
13:40	Closing session		

LIST OF ABSTRACTS

Plenary presentations

- PL1 Professor Buddy D. Ratner (University of Washington)
Form, Bumps, Pores, Shapes (FBPS) Control Biocompatibility
- PL2 Professor Anthony S. Weiss (University of Sydney)
Synthetic elastin biomaterials
- PL3 Professor Akiyoshi Kazunari (Kyoto University)
Self-assembly of glyco-based polymers (Nanogels and Vesicles) for Protein Delivery and Immunotherapy
- PL4 Professor Abhay Pandit (National University of Ireland)
Redefining Identity of Disease, Tissues and Cells – a Biomaterials Paradigm)
- PL5 Professor Andres J. García (Georgia Institute of Technology)
Biosynthetic Materials for Islet Encapsulation and Transplantation
- PL6 Professor Yasuhiko Tabata (Kyoto University)
Release Technology of Cell Recruitment Molecules to Induce In Situ Tissue Regeneration Therapy
- PL7 Professor David Kaplan (Tufts University)
Silk Protein Modifications for Functional Materials
- PL8 Professor Joachim Kohn (Rutgers University, USA)
The Race Towards Bioactive Scaffolds

Keynote presentations

- KN1 Dirk Grijpma: *Electrically Conducting Poly(trimethylene carbonate) and Reduced Graphene Oxide Composites.*
- KN2 Manuel Toledano: *Effects of polymeric nanostructured membranes on bone healing.*
- KN3 Elisabeth Engel: *Cell derived-Extracellular Matrix Scaffolds with Polylactic Acid Microcarriers for Tissue Engineering and Cell Therapy.*
- KN4 Angel Licea-Claverie: *PEGylated pH-responsive nanogels for delivery of chemotherapeutic agents to cancer cell-lines*
- KN5 Nicolas Blanchemain: *Hydrogel and Sponge based on polyelectrolyte complex (Chitosan / Polymer of Cyclodextrins) for application on drug delivery system and tissue engineering*
- KN6 Bárbara Pérez-Köhler: *Bioactive polymeric coatings with antibacterial activity for application in hernia repair mesh*
- KN7 J. Carlos Rodríguez-Cabello: *Dynamic Systems Based on Elastin-Like Recombinamers*
- KN8 Ana Oliveira: *Silk as a Dress Code for Chronic Wound Healing*
- KN9 Andreas Lendlein: *Designing Multifunctionality in Polymers to Create Effects Required in Biomedical Applications*
- KN10 María Jesús Vicent: *Polypeptide-based Conjugates for CNS disorders: Exploring the Intranasal Route of Administration*
- KN11 Manuela E. Gomes: *Targetting tissue regeneration with the use of Human-based biomaterials and biophysical stimulus*
- KN12 Martijn van Griensven: *Tissue Engineered Enthesis using Biphasic Silk Fibroin Scaffolds*
- KN13 Matilde Alonso: *Kinetic Control of Artificial Extracellular Matrix Remodelling as a Way to Increase the Quality of Regenerated Tissues: Osteochondral lesion regeneration by kinetically controlled protease sensitive E*
- KN14 João F Mano: *Polysaccharides as building blocks in tissue engineering applications*

- KN15 Aránzazu del Campo: *Light-stimulated collagen production: new approaches to reconstruct tissues*
- KN16 José Vidal-Gancedo: *Radical Dendrimers. Synthesis, Characterization and Biomedical Applications*
- KN17 Antonio Martínez-Richa: *Synthesis of crosslinked poly(ester-urethane)s, with potential uses as scaffolds for tissue engineering*
- KN18 Vamsi Yadavalli: *Bioinspired materials and strategies for the fabrication of functional devices*
- KN19 Antonella Motta: *Methods for silk scaffolds fabrication*
- KN20 Ugo D'Amora: *Chemical Strategies to tailor the properties of hyaluronic acid-based materials*
- KN21 Thomas Groth: *Engineering of bioactive surface coatings and hydrogels with polysaccharides*
- KN22 Nuno Neves: *Functional Nanofibrous Scaffolds Combined with Stem Cells for Advanced Biomedical Devices and Therapies*
- KN23 Michelle LaPlaca: *3-D Neural Culture System to Study Neuroinflammation and Neurotoxicity*
- KN24 Sanjukta Deb: *Antibacterial Systems for Dental Applications*
- KN25 Marcelo Calderón: *Rational Design of Responsive Prodrug-based Nanomedicines for Antitumor Therapy*
- KN26 F. Javier de la Mata: *Dendritic nanosystems of carbosilane nature as a versatile platform for the treatment of different pathologies*
- KN27 Conrado Aparicio: *Oligopeptides and Recombinamers at Surfaces and Interfaces to Address Oral Infections*
- KN28 Michel Vert: *Making the literature of lactic acid-based polymers profitable to everyone*
- KN29 Rodrigo Silveira Vieira: *In vitro degradability of strontium delivery systems based on oxidized bacterial cellulose and strontium apatite*
- KN30 Claudio Migliaresi: *Silks: spider and silkworm, where the differences?*

- KN31 Roberto Olayo: *Plasma Pyrrole Polymers as Implants In Spinal Cord Chronic Injury: MRI Study*
- KN32 Giuseppe Battaglia: *The Goldilocks principle applied to nanomedicine design*
- KN33 Julio Suay: *Complement proteins regulating macrophage polarisation on biomaterials*
- KN34 Auxiliadora Prieto Jiménez: *Engineering bacteria to produce added value biomaterials from wastes*
- KN35 María Rosa Aguilar: *Nanotechnology for the treatment of sensineural hearing loss*
- KN36 Francisco Goycoolea: *Chitosan based Nanoformulations for Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Applications*
- KN37 Daniel Cohn: *3D printing: From "ink" to medical devices*
- KN38 Alejandro Sosnik: *Novel Targeted and Stimuli-Responsive Amphiphilic Nanobiomaterials*
- KN39 Gilson Khang: *Novel Collagen from Natural Origin for Organ Regeneration*
- KN40 Luis Rojo del Olmo: *Biodegradable composites for musculoskeletal regeneration bearing osteoinductive and antibacterial cations*

Oral Presentations

- O1 Emmanuelle Marie: *Mixed Ad Layers of Poly(Lysine)-Based Copolymers to Dynamically Control Cell Adhesion/Migration.*
- O2 Alicia Fernández-Colino: *The Elastin Grafts: biohybrid compliant grafts as off-the-shelf small caliber vascular substitutes.*
- O3 Mark Grinstaff: *Polymers for Cartilage Tissue Supplementation and Lubrication.*
- O4 Benjamin Nottelet: *Controlled anchoring of iron-oxide nanoparticles on polymeric nanofibers: a simple approach towards hybrid and multifunctional scaffolds.*
- O5 Tali Tavor Re'em: *Constructing a Three Dimensional in Vitro Embryo Implantation Model Using Alginate Macroporous Scaffold.*
- O6 Sergio Acosta: *Advanced antimicrobial recombinant polymers: Insights onto the self-assembly - bactericidal properties relationship*
- O7 Isabelle Texier: *Localized siRNA delivery by collagen/lipid nanoparticle hybrid scaffolds*
- O8 Ana Lopez Periago: *Coordination polymers for biomedical applications*
- O9 Juan González: *Self-assembling ELR nanoparticles as smart drug delivery systems*
- O10 Bernard Martel: *Aryl-sulfonated chitosan: synthesis, characterization, anticoagulant properties and electrospinning*
- O11 Matthias Gabriel: *Peptide and non-Peptide modified Surfaces specific for the Adhesion and Growth of Valvular Interstitial Cells*
- O12 M. Ali Aboudzadeh: *Design of gold (Au)/cyclic polymer hybrid materials for biomedical applications*
- O13 Jacek Wychowaniec: *3D Printing of Spatially Patterned Magnetically Responsive Hydrogels*
- O14 Costas Kiparissides: *Engineering Responsive and Biomimetic Hydrogels for Biomedical Therapeutic and Diagnostic Applications (BIOGEL)*
- O15 Malgorzata Wlodarczyk-Biegun: *3D printing of PEG-based hydrogels with dynamic metal coordination crosslinking*

- O16 Maria Virginia Rivero Buceta: *Antibacterial hydrogels based on bacterial cellulose and PHACOS*
- O17 Hadda Zebiri: *Design of Biodegradable Anti-Adhesive Membranes in Orthopaedic Surgery*
- O18 Julieta Paez: *Filling the kinetic gap: a new thiol-X crosslinking chemistry for 3D cell culture hydrogels*
- O19 Husam Younes: *Poly(decanediol-co-tricarballylate) Elastomeric Nano-Fibrous Mesh Fabricated by Photoreactive Electrospinning for Cardiac Tissue Engineering Applications*
- O20 Natalia Davidenko: *Influence of Substrate Stiffness on Cell Response. Focus on Collagen*
- O21 Noo Li Jeon: *High-Throughput 3D Microfluidic Platform for Vascularized Micro Physiological System Applications*
- O22 Ana Mora-Boza: *3D bioprinting of soluble chitosan-lactate conjugate bioinks*
- O23 Miguel González Pérez: *Interface spontaneous membrane formation by two elastin-like recombinamers*
- O24 Verónica Luque-Agudo: *Highly Hydrophobic PLA Films and Their Degradation Over Time*
- O25 Helene Van Den Berghe: *A New Synthesis Route of Amphiphilic Polyester-g-Oligosaccharide Copolymers for Anticancer Drug Delivery*
- O26 Judith Feitosa: *Injectable Hydrogel based on Chitosan Derivative, Galactomannan and Chitin Whiskers*
- O27 Malo Dufay: *PP peritoneal meshes covered with PCL nanofibers functionalized by cold plasma with antiadhesive properties*
- O28 Leire Ruiz Rubio: *Hyaluronic acid/chitosan titanium multilayers with antibacterial properties*
- O29 Muhammad Muhammad: *Modification and optimization of polysaccharides for hydrogel formation for bone tissue regeneration*
- O30 Petr Chytil: *Micellar HPMA Polymer-Drug Conjugates for Immunooncotherapy*

- O31 Shardul Bhusari: *Light-responsive drug release from living hydrogels*
- O32 Diego Velasco: *Vinyl-based microfluidic chips for human skin models*
- O33 Samuel Pearson: *Photoresponsive biomaterials for light-triggered angiogenesis)*
- O34 Eva Espinosa-Cano: *Long-term anti-inflammatory capacity of layer-by-layer coatings embedding naproxen-based polymeric nanoparticles*
- O35 Laurent Leclercq: *Characterization of polyelectrolyte complexes by inline coupling of capillary electrophoresis to Taylor dispersion analysis – Application to polyplexes*
- O36 Petr Humpolicek: *The biocompatibility of electrically conducting polymers*
- O37 Raúl Fontelo Rodríguez: *Selective block copolymer films with antibacterial and biocompatible properties*
- O38 Beatrice Labat: *Chondroitin Sulfate A-based PEM films: Biomimetic matrices for tissue engineering*
- O39 Felix Reisbeck: *Synthesis of dPG-based Nanogels as Polyvalent Carriers for T Cell Staining*
- O40 Inmaculada Aranz: *Controlled released of risperidone from β -chitosan hydrogels*
- O41 María Puertas Bartolomé: *3D printing of a reactive hydrogel loaded with catechol containing nanoparticles*
- O42 Anna Herrmann: *Geometric Separation of Detection Levels by a Bioorthogonal Porous Polymer – Introducing Functionality and Increasing Multiplexicity*
- O43 Gloria María Pontes Quero: *Encapsulation of hydrophobic agents into vitamin E-based polymeric nanoparticles*
- O44 Araceli Delgado: *Bioactive Hydrogels for Bone Regeneration in Osteoporosis*
- O45 Binh T. Mai: *Nanostructures Based on Stimuli-responsive Polymers: Promising Platforms for Controlled Drug Delivery*

- O46 Guzmán Carissimi: *Process Optimization of Drug Loaded Silk Fibroin Nanoparticle Synthesis Using Ionic Liquids*
- O47 Soyoun Jang: *Adipose derived stromal vascular fraction with Extracellular matrix scaffold synergetic effect on skin regeneration.*

Posters List

Advanced contributions of polymers and methodologies for Tissue Engineering

- T1-1 Bohumila Podhorska (Institute of Macromolecular chemistry CAS)
Macroporous hydrogel scaffolds for stem cells cultivation: Comparison of microscopical methods SEM and LSCM
- T1-2 Soyoun Jang (Idea Plastic Surgery)
Adipose derived stromal vascular fraction with Extracellular matrix scaffold synergetic effect on skin regeneration
- T1-3 Marcelo Salierno (King's College)
Mechanical confinement to promote direct reprogramming of glial cells into neurons
- T1-4 M^a Luisa López-Donaire (Instituto Ciencia y Tecnología de Polímeros, ICTP-CSIC)
Hyaluronic acid -based hydrogel membranes for cartilage regeneration
- T1-5 Gilson Khang (Chonbuk National University)
Application of Duck's Feet-derived Collagen and Gallus Gallus Var. Domesticus-derived Demineralized Bone Powder for Bone Tissue Engineering

- T1-6 Thomas Groth (*Department Biomedical Materials, Institute of Pharmacy*)
Free-standing films created by dip coating using Genipin crosslinking for wound dressing applications
- T1-7 Ana Oliveira (*Universidade Católica Portuguesa*)
Fast-forming hybrid sericin hydrogel with tissue-inspired multifunctionality
- T1-8 Barbara Pérez-Köhler (*University of Alcalá*)
In vivo assessment of an antibacterial carboxymethylcellulose gel loaded with chlorhexidine for the prophylactic coating of hernia repair mesh materials
- T1-9 Sujin Song (*Pusan National University*)
Functional Graphene Nanomaterial-Coated Implants to Enhance Osseointegration
- T1-10 Sofia Perea Ruiz (*University of Glasgow*)
Bioengineering microenvironments to study vascularization in bone regeneration
- T1-11 Gerardo Asensio Martín (*Instituto Ciencia y Tecnología de Polímeros, ICTP-CSIC*)
Biomimetic SrFO/ZnFO-loaded biohybrid scaffolds for osteochondral tissue regeneration
- T1-12 J H Lee (*Hannam University*)
In Situ Alginate/Hyaluronic Acid Hydrogel with Ultrasound Stimulation for Effective Bone Regeneration

T1-13 J H Lee (Hannam University)

Bone Regeneration by Plasmid DNA-Loaded Polycaprolactone/Hyaluronic Acid Hybrid Microspheres

T1-14 Salvador David Aznar Cervantes (Instituto Murciano de *Investigación y Desarrollo Agrario*)

Influence of different cocoon stifling methods on the properties of silk fibroin biomaterials

T1-15 Julia Bujan Varela (University of Alcala)

Preclinical model for bone infected: the use of polylactic-co-glycolic acid microspheres added to fixative cements and its role on bone

Smart Polymers for delivery of drugs and bioactive compounds

T2-1 Kristyna Venclikova (Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry, CAS)

Paclitaxel-loaded polylactide/polyethylene glycol fibers with long-term antitumor activity as a potential drug carrier for local chemotherapy

T2-2 Daniela Machova (Institute of Macromolecular chemistry CAS)

HPMA copolymer-bound ritonavir as nanotherapeutics with suitable properties for advance anticancer therapy

- T2-3 Aaron Sloutski (Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Israel)
Designing reverse thermo-responsive polymeric nano-shells
- T2-4 Mahfoud BOUSTTA (IBMM- UMR CNRS 5247)
New UCST-Type Thermoresponsive Hydrogels As Artificial Gelatin
- T2-5 Niuris Acosta (Complutense University of Madrid)
Semisolid formulation with microparticulate functional ingredients
- T2-6 Larysa Janisova (Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry v.v.i)
Novel multifunctional nanoparticles for drug delivery and nanocrystallization
- T2-7 Nadiia Velychkivska (Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry, AS CR, Prague, Czech Republic)
Thermoresponsive polymeric systems studied by NMR Spectroscopy
- T2-8 Mariusz Uchman (Charles University, Faculty of Science)
Synthesis of Sugar and pH-Responsive Triblock Terpolymers Based on Polyesters and Phenylboronic Acid via ROP and Click Chemistry and Controlling their Aqueous Self-Assembly
- T2-9 Rebeca Bouza (Universidade da Coruña)
Simultaneous dual release of hydrophobic drugs from PHBV microparticles/ ?-carrageenan composite hydrogel

T2-10 Francisco Javier Caro León (Centro de Investigación en Alimentación y Desarrollo A.C.)

Characterization and antioxidant activity of catechol-chitosan/ β -Lactoglobulin nanoparticles

T2-11 Stephanie Degoutin (University of Lille)

Bilayer coating of vascular stent with electrospun bioactive nanofibers for the prevention of restenosis and thrombosis

T2-12 Miguel Huerta Madroñal (Instituto Ciencia y Tecnología de Polímeros, ICTP-CSIC)

Polymeric nanoparticulated systems for transdermal drug delivery of hydrophobic drugs

T2-13 Antonio Abel Lozano-Pérez (Instituto Murciano de Investigación y Desarrollo Agrario y Alimentario)

Designing New Hybrid CO Releasing Materials based on Silk Fibroin Nanoparticles

T2-14 Julita Pachla (Warsaw University of Technology)

Supramolecular structure of antimicrobial polycations with amphiphilic anions

T2-15 Raquel Osorio (University of Granada)

*A *Caenorhabditis elegans* model for testing toxicity of zinc and doxycycline loaded polymeric nanoparticles*

Bioactive polymers and microfluidics

T4-1 Zdenka Capáková (Tomas Bata University in Zlin)

Conductive polyaniline/PVA scaffolds: biocompatibility study

T4-2 Dominika Kozon (Warsaw University of Technology)

Biological properties of linear polyethyleneimine and its hydrophobic modification

T4-3 Rafal Kopiasz (Warsaw University of Technology)

The stability study on antimicrobial polycations containing novel degradable linker.

Modification and functionalization of synthetic and natural polymers

T5-1 Mark Grinstaff (Boston University)

Synthesis and Biomedical Applications of Poly-amido-saccharides

T5-2 Claire Desfrancois (CERMAV-CNRS and CEA-Leti)

Synthesis and characterization of well-defined polyrotaxanes for the design of stretchable gels

T5-3 Matthias Müller (Freie Universität Berlin)

Mucin-inspired broad range virus binding inhibitor based on multivalent high molecular weight hyperbranched polyglycerol

T5-4 Ji-Ung Park (Seoul National University Boramae Hospital)

Enhanced biocompatibility and reduced capsule formation of silicone surfaces via tantalum ion implantation

T5-5 Alejandro Borrás Caballero (ICMAB-CSIC)

Preparation of Graphene Oxide / Polyethyleneimine Composite Aerogels

T5-6 Mauro Pollini (University of Salento)

Surface functionalization of polyurethane foams: silver-based antimicrobial treatments on air filtration units for prevention of respiratory diseases

T5-7 Federica Paladini (University of Salento)

Silver treated antibacterial compounds for the development of bioactive devices for prevention of respiratory diseases

T5-8 M. Luisa González-Martín (Universidad de Extremadura)

Bacterial Response on Thin PLA/Mg Composite Film

T5-9 Antoniac Lulian (University Politehnica of Bucharest)

Magnesium powder filled PLA for filament based 3D Printing for medical applications

T5-10 Gloria Villora (Universidad de Murcia)

Effects of Silk Degumming in Fibroin Nanoparticle Synthesis

T5-11 Marcela Martín del Campo (Instituto Ciencia y Tecnología de Polímeros, ICTP-CSIC)

Evaluation of the osteoinductive potential of HDPSCs on membranes of PCL/f-MWCNTs decorated with β -glycerol phosphate for bone regeneration

T5-12 Jong-il CHOI (Chonnam National University)

Degradation of Carboxymethylcellulose by Radiation for Sterilization

Targeting and controlled release of bioactive systems

T7-1 Costas Kiparissides (CERTH/CPERI)

Nose-to-Brain Controlled Drug Delivery from Microparticles Embedded in a Hydrogel Patch

T7-2 Marcela Filipova (Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry CAS)

Oligopeptide-Polymer Conjugates for Image-Guided Surgery Targeted against $\alpha V\beta 3$ Integrin

T7-3 Ondrej Lidicky (Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry, Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic)

Personalized nanomedicine for Non-Hodgkin lymphoma treatment

- T7-4 Daniel Fernández Villa (Instituto Ciencia y Tecnología de Polímeros, ICTP-CSIC)
Synthesis and characterization of new methotrexate derivatives containing divalent cations and their evaluation as bioactive compounds for musculoskeletal regeneration

Others

- T8-1 Radoslaw Wach (Lodz University of Technology)
Approach to Sterilization of Implantable Device for Therapeutic Delivery
- T8-2 Crenguta Bacaoanu (Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi)
Study of biological fluids adsorption by surgical fibers
- T8-3 Sang-Won Park (Chonnam National University)
The influence of volume fraction on the microstructure and physical properties of zirconia produced with polymer suspensions by the additive manufacturing
- T8-4 Xun Xu (Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht)
Edge sharpness of geometric microcavity enhances contractility and osteogenesis of mesenchymal stem cells via ROCK signaling
- T8-5 Luis García-Fernández (Instituto de Ciencia y Tecnología de Polímeros, ICTP-CSIC)
Luminescent chitosan-based silver nanoclusters with photothermal activity

Plenary Presentations

Form, Bumps, Pores, Shapes (FBPS) Control Biocompatibility

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INTRODUCTION

A unique aspect of polymer science (in contrast to chemistry) is that polymer science is concerned not only with the composition of novel polymers that are synthesized but also their mechanical properties and fabrication. This talk will explore how the finished, fabricated form of the polymer (Form, Bumps, Pores, Shapes) can exert a more profound effect on *in vivo* bioreaction than the composition or chemistry

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

There are many methods to control the form, bumps pores and shapes of polymers intended for biomedical applications and some of these will be reviewed. The talk will particularly focus on the 6S method for creating precision porous structures. The 6S method has six steps: (1) Sieve non-crosslinked, polymeric microspheres to a uniform size cut, (2) Shake those microspheres to compact them to a close-packed mass, (3) gently heat the microspheres so they Sinter with each other, (4) Surround the microspheres with monomer, (5) Solidify (polymerize) the monomer and finally (6) Solubilize the entrained microspheres to create a porous structure where every pore is the same size and interconnected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6S structures made from silicones, polyurethanes and hydrogels all show similar *in vivo* healing in many different implant sites and many different animal models. If the pore size is approximately 40 microns, a vascularized, non-fibrotic tissue reconstruction will be seen. Examples will be presented with subcutaneous implants, scleral implants, bone implants and a vascular prosthesis.

CONCLUSION

Evidence will be present of the strong, profound effect of form, bumps, pores, shapes (and mechanical properties) on the *in vivo* bioreaction to implanted materials.

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Synthetic elastin biomaterials

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The mammalian extracellular matrix comprises various proteins, proteoglycans and glycosaminoglycans. Elastic tissues such as vasculature, skin, lungs, and elastic ligaments possess the ability to undergo non-destructive cycles of stretch and relaxation.

This unique property is imparted by elastic fibers in the extracellular matrix.

Elastin is an extracellular matrix protein polymer that imparts tissues with the ability to endure stretch-recoil cycles. The formation of elastin has been explored through its major components, such as the natural precursor tropoelastin and mimics in elastin-like polypeptides, and involves a remarkable process of hierarchical self-assembly at physiological temperatures through interactions principally between their hydrophobic sequences. These properties have made elastin an attractive candidate for incorporation into biomaterials for a range of applications in regenerative medicine.

Over 90% of elastic fibers are composed of elastin, which is composed of the monomer tropoelastin. The stages through which tropoelastin self-assembles into elastin and, in turn, elastic fibers, are hierarchical and the topic of extensive, ongoing research. Beyond tropoelastin, this self-assembly property has also been demonstrated with solubilized elastin fragments and elastin-like polypeptides. It is this capacity for self-assembly that is of interest for a class of materials with applications in regenerative medicine.

There has been considerable recent progress in understanding the self-assembly of tropoelastin and elastin-based derivatives, and the strategies in which this property has been utilized in novel materials for regenerative medicine. This presentation will summarize the recent advances in understanding how the sequence and structure of elastin influence the thermodynamics that govern the functionality of elastin and its derivatives, and will describe innovations in harnessing these mechanisms to create tunable elastin-based biomaterials.

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Self-assembly of glyco-based polymers (Nanogels and Vesicles) for Protein Delivery and Immunotherapy

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INTRODUCTION

The biologics such as proteins and nucleic acids are attracting attention as innovative next-generation pharmaceutical products. We have developed bio-inspired nanocarriers, bio-nanotransporters, based on nanogel tectonics engineering¹, proteoliposome engineering and exosome engineering for drug delivery system (DDS) and tissue engineering^{1,2}. Self-nanogels by hydrophobized polysaccharides showed molecular chaperone-like activity that enables them to capture various protein and peptide molecules within their polymer matrix and to release in the native form³. Cancer vaccines were the first practical application of the self-Nanogels as vehicles for antigen DDS^{4,5}. Intranasal vaccination is attractive immunization strategy for delivering vaccine antigens directly onto the mucosa to induce a protective immune response. Cationic self-Nanogels were effective in penetrating the nasal mucosa and resulted in successful nasal vaccines^{6,7}.

Enzymes represent promising therapeutic agents, in enzyme replacement and enzyme prodrug therapies for a wide variety of diseases. Therapeutic applications of enzymes are, however, still hampered by their degradations by proteases and inactivation by the immune system. A therapeutic nanofactory is an enzyme nanoreactor that can accumulate at disease sites in the body, where encapsulated enzymes would convert toxic materials into harmless compounds or transform inert prodrugs into cytotoxic compounds within the tumour or other disease site. Such nanofactories, therefore, have great potential for next-generation therapeutic platforms including enzyme prodrug therapy⁸. We found a polymeric vesicle of glycol-based polymer with an intrinsically permeable bilayer membrane as enzyme nanoreactors^{9, 10}.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We developed new polymer vesicles which were made of a block copolymer with maltopentaose and poly(propylene glycol). A series of maltooligosaccharide-*b*-PPGs with PPGs of various degree of polymerization and oligosaccharides of different molecular weights were prepared. SAXS data showed that all carbohydrate-containing polymers formed vesicles (CAPsomes) with bilayer membranes and that membrane thickness increased with degree of polymerization. The CAPsomes had molecular weight-dependent permeability for organic molecules and proteins. CAPsomes retained enzymes in the inner aqueous phase and low molecular weight substrates diffused into the enzyme-loaded vesicles. For example, CAPsomes effectively encapsulated β -galactosidase (β -gal), horseradish peroxidase and α -chymotrypsin. The enzymatic reactions occurred in the inner aqueous phase with original activity. We demonstrated the efficacy of β -gal-loaded CAPsome as enzyme reactor in living cells through two applications: hydrolysis of fluorogenic substrate and transformation inert prodrug, 5-*N*-(\square -D-galactopyranosyl)benzyloxy-carbonyl)-doxorubicin (DoxGal) into clinical anticancer drug (Dox) inside the cell.

We focus our attention to the possibility using it as a nanofactory for *in vivo* clinical prodrug activation. In tumour bearing mice, CAPsomes accumulated in tumors by passive targeting, and were retained for up to 48 h. Combined treatment with β -gal-loaded CAPsomes and doxorubicin prodrug (DoxGal) inhibited tumour growth in these mice without any observable toxicity.

CONCLUSION

We described a new approach for enzyme prodrug cancer therapy, based on bio-transporting nanofactories. The nanofactory is composed of a CAPsome, with a bilayer membrane that has molecular permeability. The β -gal-loaded CAPsomes accumulated at tumour sites and transformed a prodrug into a toxic anticancer drug, inhibiting tumour growth.

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Fig 1. Enzyme prodrug therapy by CAPsome

Redefining Identity of Disease, Tissues and Cells – a Biomaterials Paradigm

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Biomaterials are no longer considered innate structures and using functionalisation and biofabrication strategies to modulate a desired response whether it is a host or implant is currently an important focus in current research paradigms. Fundamentally, a thorough understanding of the host response will enable us to design appropriate strategies. The input from the host response needs to be weighed in depending on the host disease condition. In addition, biomaterials themselves provide immense therapeutic benefits which needs to be accounted in the design paradigm. Using functionalisation strategies such as enzymatic and hyperbranched linking systems, we have been able to link biomolecules to different structural moieties. The programmed assembly of biomolecules into higher-order self-organized systems is central to innumerable biological processes and development of the next generation of biofabricated scaffolds. Recent design efforts have utilized a glycobiology and developmental biology approach toward both understanding and engineering supramolecular protein and sugar assemblies. Structural moieties have taken a variety of different forms such as nanofibers and nanoparticulate. This approach has resulted in functionalisation of micro and nanoparticles with biomolecules that include designed peptide motifs, growth factors and a multitude of gene vector systems. In addition, nature itself has abundant structural complexity that can be biofabricated for harnessing in key targeted clinical applications.

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Biosynthetic Materials for Islet Encapsulation and Transplantation

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INTRODUCTION

Hydrogels, highly hydrated cross-linked polymer networks, have emerged as powerful synthetic analogs of extracellular matrices for basic cell studies as well as promising biomaterials for regenerative medicine applications. A critical advantage of these synthetic matrices over natural networks is that the biophysical and biochemical properties of the material can be tuned with high control and precision. For example, bioactive functionalities, such as cell adhesive sequences and growth factors, can be incorporated in precise densities. We have engineered poly(ethylene glycol) [PEG]-maleimide hydrogels that support improved pancreatic islet engraftment, vascularization and function in diabetic models.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two biomaterial strategies have been pursued. We have developed proteolytically degradable synthetic hydrogels, functionalized with vasculogenic factors for localized delivery, engineered to deliver islet grafts to extrahepatic transplant sites via in situ gelation. These hydrogels induce differences in vascularization and innate immune responses among subcutaneous, small bowel mesentery, and epididymal fat pad transplant sites with improved vascularization and reduced inflammation at the epididymal fat pad site. This biomaterial-based strategy improves the survival, engraftment, and function of a single pancreatic donor islet mass graft compared to the current clinical intraportal delivery technique. In a second application, we have developed a localized immunomodulation strategy using hydrogels presenting an apoptotic form of Fas ligand (SA-FasL) that results in prolonged survival of allogeneic islet grafts in diabetic mice. A short course of rapamycin treatment boosts the immunomodulatory efficacy of SA-FasL-hydrogels, resulting in acceptance and function of allografts over 200 days. Survivors generate normal systemic responses to donor antigens, implying immune privilege of the graft, and have increased T-regulatory cells in the graft. This localized immunomodulatory biomaterial-enabled approach may provide an alternative to chronic immunosuppression for clinical islet transplantation.

CONCLUSION

Hydrogel-based strategies to promote islet engraftment and vascularization as well as local immune acceptance in diabetic models have been established. These material-based strategy may significantly impact islet transplantation as a treatment for type 1 diabetes.

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Release Technology of Cell Recruitment Molecules to Induce In Situ Tissue Regeneration Therapy

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A new therapeutic trial based on the natural-healing potential of body itself to induce tissues regeneration and repairing, has been recently expected. To realize this tissue regenerative therapy, there are two approaches of cell transplantation and tissue engineering. For the first cell approach, it is necessary for an enhanced therapeutic efficacy to improve the in vivo viability and functions of cells transplanted. On the other hand, the basic idea of tissue engineering is to enhance the proliferation and differentiation abilities of cells for tissue regeneration. To this end, it is of prime importance to develop a biomaterial technology or methodology to give cells a local environment for their ability enhancement. For example, if a cell scaffold or a key bio-signaling molecule is supplied to the right place at the right time period or concentration by the release technology of biomaterials, the body system initiates to physiologically function, resulting in the natural induction of cell-based tissue regeneration. The tissue engineering technology also enables cells to improve their in vivo viability and functions, promoting the therapeutic efficacy of cell transplantation.

With the recent scientific development of stem cell biology, various molecules which have an ability to enable cells to accelerate their recruitment in vivo to the site necessary, have been available for cell-based tissue regeneration therapy. If the cell recruitment molecule can be supplied to the site to be regenerated by the release technology, it is highly expected that the molecule enhanced the recruitment of key cells at the site, resulting in promoted cell-induced tissue regeneration and repairing thereat.

We have explored biodegradable hydrogels for the controlled release of biologically active stromal cell-derived factor (SDF)-1 of cell recruitment ability. When implanted subcutaneously into the mice back, the hydrogel incorporating SDF-1 enhanced SDF-1-induced angiogenesis around the site of hydrogel implanted to a significantly high extent compared with the injection of SDF-1 solution. The number of cells with the SDF-1 receptor increased around the hydrogel implanted, in remarked contrast to that of SDF-1 solution. It is possible that the controlled release of SDF-1 enabled angiogenic cells to accelerate their recruitment, resulting in a cell-induced in situ angiogenesis. Such a cell-based tissue regeneration by making use of cell recruitment molecule was further promoted by combining with the controlled release technology of growth factors. For example, the controlled release of a cell recruitment molecule can enhance the in vivo recruitment of stem cells, followed by the local functional activation of cells recruited by another drug released, which results in an enhance cell-based tissue regeneration.

It is no doubt that inflammation is one of the essential host responses to pathologically modify the process of tissue regeneration. Tissue regeneration was naturally promoted by positively regulating the inflammation process through the local release technology of an anti-inflammatory drug. The positive regulation of inflammation further enhanced the therapeutic efficacy of tissue regeneration which is induced by the drug release of biomaterial technology.

In situ tissue regeneration through the functional activation of cells originally present in the body by utilizing the drug release technology is one of the promising therapeutic strategies of regenerative medicine.

Silk Protein Modifications for Functional Materials

David L. Kaplan, Tufts University

New strategies to exploit silk chemistry and structure will be presented in the context of functional materials for tissue engineering and regenerative medicine. The options to selectively modify silks via chemical, biological and physical approaches to embrace new functional outcomes will be presented. Some of the latest advances towards new biomaterials based on silks, including selective chemistry, bioengineering designs, 3D printing and related processing options will be discussed.

The Race Towards Bioactive Scaffolds

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INTRODUCTION

Starting about 60 years ago, biomaterials scientists recognized the importance of the integrin-mediated signalling that influences key cellular responses such as attachment, migration, and proliferation. This line of research is now at the centre of a world-wide effort to engineer bioactive scaffolds for the creation of tissues either ex-vivo (e.g., in a bioreactor before implantation) or in-situ (e.g., within the body of the patient).

Bioactivity is defined as the ability to control and direct cell and tissue growth toward desired outcomes. In this sense, natural extracellular matrix (ECM) can be regarded as the most desirable bioactive scaffold. Embedded within the structure of natural ECM is all the information needed to control and direct cell attachment, proliferation, migration, and differentiation. We have not yet been able to decipher this “secret code”, but science has identified (i) mechanical cues, (ii) architecture and topography, and (iii) chemical cues as the three channels by which materials interact with cells. While engineers work on increasingly sophisticated scaffold designs, the biological approach starts from living donor tissue and aims to create whole organs by mild decellularization to preserve the ECM structure, followed by recellularization with healthy, autologous cells from the patient.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 illustrates current work to design bioactive scaffolds for specific cell types. In this case, an attempt was made to build a scaffold for the regeneration of the osteochondral interface, the area in all articulating joints where bone transitions into cartilage. Osteoblasts and chondrocytes require different substrata for optimum proliferation and to retain their respective phenotypes. This requirement is met by a biphasic scaffold consisting of a layer optimized for bone growth and a layer optimized for cartilage. The next step in this work is the addition of appropriate biological signals that can drive the formation of a functional osteochondral interface either ex-vivo or in-situ. Figure 2 illustrates advanced scaffold designs that are facilitated by additive manufacturing (3D printing).

Figure: 3. Hybrid scaffold

Figure 3 illustrates a hybrid scaffold consisting of reinforcing polymer microfibers that provide mechanical strength and improve handleability while a layer of decellularized ECM provides a range of biological signals that improve the bioactivity of this scaffold design. This design strategy seems to be a promising way to combine the advantages of synthetic polymer fibers with the bioactivity inherent in natural ECM.

CONCLUSION

Biological and engineering approaches are now being combined to develop bioactive scaffolds that can control and direct cell growth and tissue formation toward desirable outcomes. This research effort will provide the foundation for significant advances in the near future.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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Keynote Presentations

Electrically Conducting Poly(trimethylene carbonate) and Reduced Graphene Oxide Composites

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INTRODUCTION

One of the key challenges in neural tissue engineering is the development of functional materials to guide and support nerve regeneration. We propose investigating the properties of composite materials consisting of flexible and biodegradable poly(trimethylene carbonate) (PTMC) networks and reduced graphene oxide (rGO) as a conductive filler, and assess their physical and biological properties.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Graphite was oxidized following Hummers' method [1], exfoliated using sonication and subsequently reduced with hydrazine to form thin sheets of rGO. Three-armed PTMC functionalized with methacrylic anhydride (MA) was dissolved in dispersions of rGO in dimethylformamide with desired rGO contents. After precipitation and solvent casting in chloroform, the films were crosslinked under UV light. To enhance the compatibility of rGO with the polymer matrix, rGO was grafted with PTMC chains as well. For this, an rGO initiator was synthesized by azido ethanol reaction with graphene oxide (GO) at high temperatures [2]. This results in thermal reduction of GO and the formation of stable hydroxyl groups on the graphene surface. rGO initiator was subsequently used for the ring-opening polymerization of TMC monomer. rGO-graft-PTMC particles with different PTMC molecular weights were successfully synthesized using different amounts of TMC. PTMC/rGO-graft-PTMC composite fibrous mats were fabricated by electrospinning of dispersions of PTMC and rGO-graft-PTMC. PC12 cells were cultured on the composites to investigate their compatibility with relevant neuronal cells.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The PTMC-MA/rGO composite films with 0, 0.5, 1, 2 and 4 wt% showed increasing electrical conductivity with values up to $6.88 \times 10^{-2} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$. Culturing of PC-12 cells showed that after initial cell adhesion, the cells proliferated on the surface of the PTMC-MA/rGO composite films, regardless of the amount of rGO loading. Upon grafting PTMC chains onto rGO, the graphene nanosheets remained present in single layers, and the rGO-graft-PTMC dispersions were stable in chloroform. The rGO-graft-PTMC composites with PTMC molecular weights of 430-7030 g/mol had electrical conductivities ranging from 0.2-0.016 S/cm. The loading of rGO-graft-PTMC could reach up to 6 wt% relative to PTMC. Upon electrospinning, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images showed that the morphologies and average diameters of PTMC/rGO-graft-PTMC composite fibrous mats were affected by the content of rGO-graft-PTMC. Biological results demonstrated that PC12 cells showed higher cell viability on PTMC/rGO-graft-PTMC fibers of 2.4, 4.0 and 6.0 wt% rGO-graft-PTMC compared to pure PTMC fibers.

CONCLUSION

As electrically conductive materials are expected to increase the rate of axonal regeneration, resulting in improved functional recovery of transected peripheral nerves, these results suggest that PTMC-rGO and PTMC/rGO-graft-PTMC composites hold great potential for neural tissue engineering.

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Effects of polymeric nanostructured membranes on bone healing.

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INTRODUCTION

Functionalization of the polymeric membranes through the incorporation of bioactive components may create a specific chemical context, enhancing their osteoconductive properties¹. The aim of this study was to evaluate the bone-regeneration efficiency of novel polymeric nanostructured membranes and the effect of zinc, calcium, titanium and bone morpho-protein (BMP-2) loading of the membranes, through an *in vivo* rabbit model experimental design.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Membranes of methyl-methacrylate were loaded with zinc, calcium, TiO₂ nanoparticles and recombinant bone-morphogenetic protein (BMP-2). A fifth group of unloaded membrane was also tested. These membranes covered the non-critical bone defects prepared on the skulls of six rabbits. A sixth bone defect was uncovered (control). Animals were sacrificed after six weeks. Micro computed tomography (μ -CT) was used to evaluate bone architecture through *BoneJ* plugging and *ImageJ* script. Three histological processing of samples, including von Kossa (VK) silver nitrate, toluidine blue (TB) and fluorescence by the deposition of calcein were utilized. One-way ANOVA and paired t-tests were applied ($p \leq 0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Zn loaded membranes (M-Zn) promoted the highest amount of new bone and higher bone perimeter than both unloaded and Ti loaded membranes (M-Ti). Ca loaded membranes (M-Ca) promoted higher osteoid perimeter and bone perimeter than M-Zn. The skeleton analysis showed that M-Zn promoted higher branches and junctions of the trabecular bone than BMP loaded membranes (M-BMP). Samples treated with TiO₂ showed less bone formation and bony bridging processes. Both M-Zn and M-Ca promoted higher number of osteoblasts than CG. M-BMP and M-Ca originated higher number of blood vessels than M-Ti and CG. Almost complete union was observed throughout the defects treated with M-Zn showing zones which were occupied by bone-like structures, suggesting that substantial level of new bone was formed in the defect area². New bone appeared at both sides of the membrane after using M-Zn and M-Ca. M-Ca showed small trabeculae structures and maximum branch lengths, but lower osteogenic potential and scarcer angiogenesis than M-Zn.

CONCLUSION

Zn loaded membranes provided higher regenerative efficiency for bone healing at the created non-critical experimental bone defects.

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Cell derived-Extracellular Matrix Scaffolds with Polylactic Acid Microcarriers for Tissue Engineering and Cell Therapy

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INTRODUCTION

The use of cell-derived matrices (CDMs) is a promising alternative for tissue regeneration and disease modelling. CDMs are bioactive and biocompatible materials consisting of a complex assembly of proteins, matrix macromolecules and growth factors. The ability to create different CDM based on the cell source and culture methods, offers the possibility to tailor-made bioactive materials for desired applications. Poly-lactic acid cell-cultured microcarriers have been developed to generate 3D scaffolds for ECM deposition. We have promoted cell adhesion by a fibronectin functionalization. Proliferation and CDM production have been also enhanced by the Macromolecular Crowding (MMCs) effect, which mimics cell culture media to the in vivo conditions.

The aim of the project is to produce large microtissues to be used as scaffolds for tissue engineering and as systems for tumour modelling and cell therapy.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Microtissues (MT) fabrication. Poly-lactic acid (PLA) microcarriers are made by a solution jet break-up and solvent displacement method (Levato et al, 2012) and Fibronectin coated. Cell seeding (Mesenchymal stem cells, hAMSC) is carried out in spinner flasks with intermittent agitation and moved into well plates (10-21 days culture) where more microcarriers are added at different time points. DNA content and total expressed protein were determined. Immunofluorescence has been used to characterize protein deposition. SEM was used to analyse microtissues size and structure. hAMSC and HUVEC co-culture microtissues were produced to evaluate angiogenesis in vivo under subcutaneous implantation. Tumour therapy. Cell-based MTs composed of Thymidine kinase expressing human adipose mesenchymal stem cells (TK-hAMSCs) attached to biodegradable PLA MCs were implanted in human PC3-prostate cancer subcutaneous tumour model in SCID mice.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the end of the 21-day culture period, tissues were analyzed by different techniques to characterize them from a biochemical and physical point of view. MT created under stirring and with macromolecular crowders present significant differences in DNA content and significantly higher amounts of total expressed protein. SEM images show a great increase in MT size. Collagen types I (red) and III (green) expression were enhanced under these conditions.

SEM images of the microtissues. Left show a MT under static conditions (3x1,5mm) and right under stirring and with macromolecularcrowders (8x3mm).

Immunofluorescence image of MT under stirring. ColI, ColIII and nuclei.

TKhAMSCs-MTs plus Ganciclovir (GCV) effectively inhibit PC3 tumour growth, presenting as a promising scaffold for therapeutic mesenchymal cells.

CONCLUSION

Microtissues developed through the use of microparticles and cells have been produced by stirring and macromolecular crowders. These microtissues are big (8cm large and 1,5 cm width) and can be combined to have a reliable decellularized ECM scaffold for tissue engineering applications. Thus, using it as a cell delivery system can be used for tumour therapy.

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PEGylated pH-responsive nanogels for delivery of chemotherapeutic agents to cancer cell-lines

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INTRODUCTION

Nanogels are very promising as drug delivery carriers because their high loading capacity, high stability and responsiveness¹. Surfactant-free emulsion polymerization (SFEP) is presented as a method of choice for the preparation of stimuli-responsive core-shell nanogels. This methodology makes use of a specific type of macromers: methacrylate functionalized polyethyleneglycol (PEG-MA) with two goals in mind: to stabilize the emulsion process and to provide the nanogels with a PEGylated shell chemically attached to the crosslinked core. This methodology has been exploited previously to prepare temperature responsive nanogels², and in this contribution we present its application to prepare cationic and anionic, pH-responsive nanogels.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Figure 1 shows a scheme of the nanogels synthesis. Details on the synthetic method of DEAEEM containing nanogels were reported recently by our group using PEG-MA with M_n : 1100 g/mol³. Drug release studies were performed under sink conditions at two different pH values: 7.4 and 5, while the temperature was maintained at 37 °C. In vitro cell studies were performed by using the colorimetric MTS assay in two types of cell lines HTC-116 (colon cancer) and NCL-H1437 (lung adenocarcinoma); after 4h/24h the absorbance at 490 nm was determined, which is proportional to the concentration of viable cells. The experiments were performed in triplicate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this work, two PEGylated nanogels were synthesized with different cross-linked cores: a cationic system with poly(N,N-diethylaminoethyl methacrylate) (PDEAEM) and an anionic system with poly(2-methacryloyloxy benzoic acid) (P2MBA). A surfactant free emulsion polymerization was carried out at different feed compositions. The synthetic conditions were adjusted to yield nanogels in sizes between 90 nm and 150 nm, resulting also in differences in their pH-responsive swelling behaviour. PDEAEM nanogels show swelling at pH < 7, while P2MBA nanogels show shrinkage at pH < 7. Cis-diamminedichloroplatinum (II) “Cisplatin” and 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) were loaded in the nanogels (Table 1). Results on pH-sensitive drug delivery and viability against different cell-lines will be presented at the meeting.

Figure 1. Monomers used for the nanogels synthesis.

Table 1. Drug loadings in different PEGylated nanogels.

Key	PEG:PDEAEM	D _h (nm)	Loading (wt%)
NC2	80:20	148	25 ^b
NC4	55:45	121	42 ^b
NA455	63:37	93	33 ^c
NC51	85:15 ^a	111	30 ^c

a-P2MBA, b-5-FU, c-Cisplatin

CONCLUSION

Cationic and anionic PEGylated nanogels are excellent candidates for loading and release of 5-FU/Cisplatin with potential application in anticancer therapy.

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Hydrogel and Sponge based on polyelectrolyte complex (Chitosan / Polymer of Cyclodextrins) for application on drug delivery system and tissue engineering

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INTRODUCTION

Hydrogels are 3D polymeric networks swelled by water, that mimic extracellular matrix topography, support cell proliferation and can release biomolecules. Hydrogels and sponges can be used as scaffolds to mimic extracellular matrix topography and to deliver bioactive agents. Chitosan (CS), a natural cationic polymer, is an excellent excipient to prepare hydrogels due to its non-toxicity and biodegradability. Polymers of cyclodextrins (PCD) crosslinked with citric acid demonstrates an anionic character, which is ideal for the formation of polyelectrolyte complexes with CS. The aim of this study was to develop a CS:PCD hydrogel and sponge from a physical hydrogel and to evaluate its potential as a carrier of cells or bioactive molecules for medical application.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The two powders (CS:PCD) were co-milled in different ratios, suspended in ultrapure water. The hydrogel was formed after acidification with 1% w/v acetic acid. The visco-elastic properties of hydrogels were evaluated by rheology (MCR 301, Anton Paar) [1]. After freeze-drying, and a curing step sponges were obtained [2]. The microscopic structure of sponge was observed by SEM (4000 Hitachi SEM FEG), the swelling ratio and degradation rate was determined in different media (PBS, acid condition, enzymatic conditions). In vitro cytocompatibility of the sponges was evaluated by indirect and direct contact with pre-osteoblasts (MC3T3-E1) and human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) by AlamarBlue® method and LIVE/DEAD® assay with confocal laser microscopy (CLSM), respectively.

Sponges were impregnated in a VEGF or ciprofloxacin (CFX) solution (KABI, 2 g/L, 4 hours, 80 rpm), drug release profile was evaluated in a dynamic fully automated flow-through cell dissolution apparatus (SOTAX USP IV) coupled with a UV-vis spectrophotometer. The antibacterial activity of CFX-loaded sponges was determined against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by diffusion tests. The bioactivity of VEGF-Loaded sponges were determined with HUVCs

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Rheological evaluation revealed that only the hydrogel with CS:PCD weight ratio of 3:3 and 3:5 were stable and reproducible. Sponges dipped in PBS buffer directly after freeze-drying step lost 30 to 40% of their mass after 24 hours while no weight loss was observed when an additional thermal treatment was added. Spectroscopies confirmed the occurrence of the polyelectrolyte complex and the formation of covalent bonds formed upon thermal treatment. The swelling properties of sponge increase with the thermal treatment and decrease with the increase of PCD content in the sponge. Its microstructure, mechanical compression properties and cytocompatibility with two cell types: pre-osteoblasts (MC3T3-E1) and primary endothelial cells (HUVEC) were analyzed. High porosity (~ 87%) with interconnected pores was observed by SEM, as well as good adhesion and cell colonization within the sponge.

The CFX (antibiotic) sorption decrease with the PCD content (showing that the drug sorption is more dependent to the swelling properties than the PCD content). Interestingly, the drug release profile and antibacterial activity are in correlation with the PCD content.

VEGF was also loaded into the sponge whose release profile and bioactivity were evaluated. The release of VEGF is rapid (burst) during the first two days, then slowed down to 7 days. VEGF released during the first two days showed a significant pro-proliferation and pro-migration effect on HUVECs.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we developed a biodegradable sponge based on CS:PCD with interconnected porosity and excellent cytocompatibility. The PCD stabilizes the chitosan sponges through ionic and covalent bonds, controls the swelling and the release of CFX in order to provide an initial burst effect provoking the early destruction of bacteria. The sponge was also able to absorb and release growth factors such as VEGF by maintaining its bio-activity. CS:PCD sponges are promising scaffold for bone tissue engineering and bone deep infection treatment.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Bioactive polymeric coatings with antibacterial activity for application in hernia repair mesh

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Implantation of polymeric-based meshes for hernia repair is the general strategy to reinforce the abdominal wall, however infection is one of the most severe postoperative complications with a relatively high impact (more than 15% of the implanted meshes present infections in a short or medium period). On this basis we have developed a novel polymeric antimicrobial coating for commercial hernia repair meshes.

The coating is prepared with a medium molecular weight chitosan, and nanoparticles of PLGA loaded with chlorhexidine (CHX) and Rifampicin (RIF). The coating system was prepared by the emulsion/evaporation process through the formation of nanoparticles of a solution of the biodegradable polymer PLGA and the corresponding mix of drugs CHX (2%) and RIF (5%) in dichloromethane (DCM). The solution was added drop by drop to an aqueous solution of chitosan and the system was stirred at room temperature during 6 hrs, to evaporate the solvent DCM. After that, the solution containing chitosan and nanoparticles of loaded or unloaded drug was applied as coating by casting the corresponding meshes. The amount of coating was analysed by the weight gain and the direct observation by SEM. The results obtained demonstrated that the coating of the mesh is homogeneous and well distributed by all the meshes.

The release of the antimicrobial drugs was analysed by HPLC, after periods of time of 14 days of immersion of coated meshes into phosphate buffer solution at pH=7.4 and 37°C. The result obtained indicated that the CHX is released in a burst way reaching levels of near to 90% in two days, whereas the release of RIF is produced in a controlled linear way during all the period analysed (14 days) reaching an accumulated release near to 90% after 12 days of immersion.

The analysis of cell viability was clear, indicating the very good tolerance by different cell cultures during all the period of treatment, considering skin fibroblasts isolated from the dermis of white rabbits, and the antimicrobial effect was tested using fragments of the coated meshes using a variant agar well diffusion test determining the inhibition zones (ZOIs) of inoculated plates with *S. aureus* or *S. epidermidis*. The results obtained demonstrated that the antimicrobial effect of the coated meshes is excellent during all the time of the experiment (14 days) with the presence of clear ZOIs for both, the systems containing nanoparticles with CHX or with RIF.

Left panel: Scanning electron micrograph of a coated mesh (x20).

Right panel: Macroscopic picture of a typical ZOI developed by the RIF-loaded coated mesh, following 14 days of exposure to *S. aureus*.

The stability of the coating is guaranteed during at least the period of time studied, up to 14 days and the coated meshes can be sutured in the abdominal wall of rabbits, used as model for animal experimentation system, with a clear antiseptic and antibacterial effect offered by the controlled release of the drugs loaded. The most interesting effects are the very low toxicity of the nanoparticle/chitosan system and the controlled release for a relatively long time of the bioactive components, with good antimicrobial activity permanent during at least the period of time studied of 14 days.

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Dynamic Systems Based on Elastin-Like Recombinamers

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The use of recombinant technology in the production of macromolecule-based advanced biomaterials has caused a breakthrough increase in achievable degree of complexity and control on the molecular designs and compositions. Those recombinant macromolecules of polypeptide nature are called recombinamers. They are produced from a purely synthetic gene, in which the amino-acid sequence is not restricted to those found in naturally occurring proteins and it is dictated only by engineering design parameters. The high degree of complexity and control of the recombinamer compositions permit to reach unmatched levels of functionality in the materials produced by this way and on the systems based on them.

The development of functionality in such systems comes by to different ways. In one hand, these materials can display direct functionality. Such functionality is based on the presence in their composition of functional epitopes, typically inspired by functional epitopes found in natural proteins. The other source of functionality is the holistic functionality that emerges by the precise combination and interactions of direct functions in a precise and well designed macromolecular composition. This holistic function is particularly evident in system with a dynamic nature; systems that rearrange and respond to changes in their environment.

Examples of such dynamic systems will be presented. The examples will expand from complex 3D structures for regenerative medicine and tissue engineering that are able to incorporate a designed program of degradation and time evolution, to more fundamental matters such as the hierarchical spontaneous development of morphology and macroscopical shapes in natural and artificial systems.

Silk as a Dress Code for Chronic Wound Healing

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INTRODUCTION

Chronic wounds are currently a global epidemic, causing great morbidity, being the first step to lower extremity amputation.¹ In this context, an ideal dressing should respect each stage of the wound, promoting the gradual refurbishment of injured tissue towards anatomic and functional integrity. However, its selection defies clinical knowledge, when facing the large amount of different materials, its distinctive properties and of course, the uniqueness of each patient needs. Presently there is a large range of material options in use for each specific wound condition, taking into account the key decision aspects defined by the clinicians.

Amongst the several strategies that have been proposed to prepare polymeric matrices for tissue wound healing and regeneration, the use of silk has been gaining momentum. In fact, long standing FDA regulatory approval of silk as a suture, its abundance as raw fiber material and controlled *in vitro* and *in vivo* proteolytic degradability has established the ground for a series of applications involving drug delivery, tissue engineering, or implantable devices.² In all of these approaches, the use of silk is associated with targeted functional microenvironments supporting tissue morphogenesis. This broad range of different applications is justified by its processing versatility and possibility of chemical modification, allowing for further biofunctionalization such as the immobilization of growth factors or cell binding domains able to modulate cell behavior.

This work addresses the potential of silk as a matrix in different wound dressing strategies. Several examples are presented of the use of silk, either in the form of membranes functionalized with phytoconstituents which are able to elicit a wide range of therapeutic activities, as *in situ* forming hydrogels or as non-invasive platforms for sensing the wound environment, each targeting different stages of the wound healing.^{3,4}

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Designing Multifunctionality in Polymers to Create Effects Required in Biomedical Applications

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The successful usage of polymeric materials strongly depends on their ability to fulfill the specific and often complex demands of applications. Scientific challenges originate from the integration of several functions in one material and the design of function-function relations to enable independent, orthogonal or sequentially coupled functions.

In this presentation strategies are presented for designing multifunctional biomaterials. Polymer network architectures allow modular approaches for the creation of multifunctional polymers on the molecular level. Architected materials, such as foams, offer the option to implement functions on different hierarchical organization levels. These principles are illustrated by examples such as cell-instructive gelatine-based 3D architected hydrogels [1], which are able to modulate tissue regeneration in vivo [2,3]. Cell-instruction of materials refers to their ability to modulate behavioral and functional changes in contacting cells in a predictable manner. Physical principles were derived from extracellular matrix (ECM) and ECM-cell interaction and were based on the geometry and mechanics of materials [4,5].

Orthogonal multifunctionality was obtained in devices by integrating shape-memory effect, diffusion controlled drug release and degradability as almost independent functions. An example for a drug releasing system with sequentially coupled functions, container tubes equipped with a shape-switching capacity for diameter reduction were created, which were triggered by NIR light for on-demand release [6]. Drug-polymer affinities can be computationally predicted through molecular dynamics simulation and docking studies, followed by experimental investigation of these interactions. As reference for this approach a model system based on dexamethasone (DXM) will be presented, which is relevant for the treatment of inflammatory diseases. [7].

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Polypeptide-based Conjugates for CNS disorders: Exploring the Intranasal Route of Administration

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INTRODUCTION

The growing incidence and increasing societal costs caused by neurodegenerative disorders in an ageing population, together with the lack of effective treatments, point out the need for novel approaches in order to address their enormous burden. Only in Europe it has been estimated that 35 % of all disease burden is attributable to brain-related disorders. In particular, Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is one of the largest global public health challenges to be faced. Moreover, Central Nervous System (CNS) drug discovery and development is a challenging task due to the presence of the most impenetrable biological barrier in the human body- the Blood Brain Barrier (BBB). Indeed, only 2 % of small-molecule drugs and almost 0 % of biologic drugs do reach the brain, thus limiting the development of efficient treatments for brain diseases.¹

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Focused on designing non-invasive strategies for brain targeting and active delivery through nanotechnological approaches, we are developing targeted polypeptide-based platforms capable to bypass the BBB, on one hand, by means of the i.v. route of administration using LRP-1 receptor as molecular target to trigger transcytosis. On the other side, a non-invasive technique with greater patient compliance in the case of neurological disorders such as Alzheimer's by means of the intranasal delivery using polyglutamates, underpinned on previously established findings of our lab.^{2,3} These versatile, biodegradable carriers with controlled architecture and self-assembled behaviour hold several key features. First, they are crosslinked with reversible chemistries, prone to disassemble under physiological triggers. These have been also modified to facilitate enhance chemical adsorption on the mucosa via disulfide interchange with cysteine-rich glycoproteins and also to allow greater diffusion/penetration rates in brain. In parallel, surface modification with targeting motifs has been exploited to improve the ability to cross the mucosal barrier.

Screening studies have been performed through mucodiffusion evaluation by NMR techniques and *ex vivo* permeation assays in a sheep mucosal model.

Second, they can bear a rationally designed combination therapy. In this regard, we have identified adequate neuroprotectant-neurorescuer drug combination therapy for the treatment of AD and linking chemistry of the resultant combinations is now under development.

CONCLUSION

If successful, this novel delivery method for intranasal delivery will be of interest for other CNS-related diseases.

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Targetting tissue regeneration with the use of Human-based biomaterials and biophysical stimulusManuela E. Gomes^{1,2,3}

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Human blood components play key roles in the modulation of the wound healing process and therefore, the use of blood derivatives in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine (TERM) strategies has awakened as an inexpensive and safe source of multiple therapeutic biomolecules. Our studies have demonstrated that Platelet Lysates, in particular, either reinforced with cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) and/or combined with other biomaterials, such as Hyluronic Acid, can be used as stable pre-formed or injectable formulations for simultaneous delivering biological factors and stem cells, providing a platform for exploring PL based biomaterials in various TE applications. Nevertheless, to trigger the regenerative process in many tissues, biophysical stimulus are also essential as these take part in their proper functioning. The incorporation of magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) within 3D constructs constitutes a novel and attractive strategy towards the development of magnetically-responsive system that may successfully combine therapeutic and diagnostic functionalities. An additional advantage is that cells naturally respond to magnetic forces, and consequently, the application of a magnetic field may enhance stem cells biological performance, and ultimately stimulate cell proliferation and/or differentiation.

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Tissue Engineered Enthesis using Biphasic Silk Fibroin Scaffolds

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INTRODUCTION

Tendon and ligament ruptures occur often and their regeneration remains challenging because of the biomechanical incongruity between the soft and hard tissues involved. Tissue engineering is an attractive strategy for tendon-to-bone interface repair. The structure and extracellular matrix composition of the interface are complex and allow for gradual mechanical stress transfer between tendons and bone. Thus, scaffolds mimicking the structural features of the native interface may be able to better support functional tissue regeneration. We studied a new approach for engineering the entheses using silk fibroin and attached growth factors. Specific zonal differentiation was tested. Finally, the constructs were tested in a novel *in vivo* enthesial patellar tendon model in the rat.

METHODS

In this study, we fabricated biphasic silk fibroin scaffolds. For the bone part, randomly-oriented porosity was desired. Thus, a salt leaching methodology was used. For the tendon part aligned porosity was obtained by directional freezing. Porosity and pore size were determined by μ CT using an iodine-based contrast agent. Biomechanical testing of the constructs was performed using a uniaxial Zwick-machine with a 2.5kN load cell. Adipose-derived mesenchymal stem cells (AMSC) were obtained from liposuctions and cultured for up to 14 days. Cell attachment, viability, proliferation and gene expression in the different zones for zonal entheses markers were tested. Subsequently, we functionalized those scaffolds with heparin and explored their ability to deliver transforming growth factor β 2 (TGF- β 2) and growth/differentiation factor 5 (GDF5). We analyzed the combined impact of pore alignment and growth factors on AMSCs using the techniques described above. Finally, we administered these scaffolds in a novel patellar tendon entheses defect model in the rat. For the experimental groups, the 2 differently produced entheses scaffolds were placed into the defects. A collagen scaffold (Helistat®) and leaving the defect empty were used as controls. Animals were allowed to freely move in their cages without any restriction or immobilization after surgery and received analgesia during the first 5 days and thereafter upon need. The animals (n=12 per group) were observed for 4 and 12 weeks by X-ray, μ CT, histology (HE, Masson trichrome, picrosirius red, IHC for collagen I and II), biomechanics and qRT-PCR.

RESULTS

Entheses scaffolds could be produced and show macroscopic similarity to natural tendon-bone transition. Total porosity ranged from 50 to 80% and the majority of pores (80-90%) were <100-300 μ m. Young's modulus varied from 689 to 1322 kPa. Biphasic scaffolds supported cell attachment and influenced cytoskeleton organization depending on pore alignment. In addition, the expression of tendon, entheses and cartilage marker genes significantly changed depending on pore alignment in each region of the scaffolds ($p < 0.05$). TGF- β 2 and pore anisotropy synergistically increased the expression of tendon/ligament markers and collagen I protein content ($p < 0.05$). In addition, the combined delivery of TGF- β 2 and GDF5 enhanced the expression of cartilage markers and collagen II protein content on substrates with isotropic porosity, whereas entheses markers were enhanced in areas of mixed anisotropic / isotropic porosity ($p < 0.05$). In the *in vivo* model, no failure in any of the scaffold groups occurred. The empty groups and the collagen control showed ossification in the tendon region, whereas the biphasic scaffolds did not. Histology and qPCR indeed confirmed tendon regeneration in the tendon part of the biphasic scaffolds. Picrosirius red polarized light microscopy showed ingrowth of collagen I very similar to natural occurring Sharpey fibers from the tendon into the bone part.

DISCUSSION

Altogether, the data obtained in this study improves current understanding on the combined effects of biological and structural cues on stem cell fate for entheses regeneration. Topography concerning pore and fiber alignment induced different phenotypes within the entheses zones. Growth factors could enhance these effects. However, the mechanisms of growth factor actions and whether they remain on the scaffolds need to be elucidated. The application in a novel entheses model showed very promising results both morphologically as well as biomechanically. However, the model for entheses regeneration needs to be optimized and the surgical attachment of the scaffolds was not easy and is certainly not yet feasible for routine surgical use. Nevertheless, these innovative scaffolds present a promising strategy for tendon/ligament-to-bone regeneration.

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Kinetic Control of Artificial Extracellular Matrix Remodelling as a Way to Increase The Quality of Regenerated Tissues: Osteochondral lesion regeneration by kinetically controlled protease sensitive Elastin-like Recombinamers

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the inclusion of protease-sensitive domains to the different scaffolds used for regenerative approaches has been a ground-breaking advance in the race for improving scaffold efficiency. In this regard, now the cell content of the scaffold or the infiltrating cells coming from the surrounding tissues are able to digest those aECM at their own rate independently of chemically degradative processes. In this sense, such scaffolds retain integrity until the cells in their microenvironment decide to digest them in their vicinities by secreting different proteases such as the different MMPs, cathepsin K, etc. However, the panoply of the different peptide domains able to be cleavable by such protease activity is ample and some of them show clear differences in terms of sensitivity to such proteolytic action. Some of them are very sensitive, meaning that, after protease release by the cell, such proteolytic activity are able to rapidly cleave a substantial number of such domains prior the natural protease deactivation, while others are resistant to be cleavable and the extension of the same proteolytic action over them is much more limited. The presence of such differences in the kinetic of

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Materials.

The composition of the recombinamers used for this purpose can be seen in Figure 1. Details of biosynthesis and characterization can be found elsewhere¹.

UROCHINASE PLASMINOGEN ACTIVATOR- uPA

Figure 1. Scheme of the clickable complementary ELR sequences used in this work.

In vivo experimental model. A osteochondral defect in rabbit knee was generated by drilling a cylindrical area in the femoral condyle. The defect was filled with a two-layer scaffold combining all the different possibilities of rapid and slow cleavage kinetics in the two areas of the defect, cartilage and subchondral bone. The scaffold was also loaded with mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) in the subchondral bone area and mature chondrocytes or MSCs in the chondral layer (Fig.2). The different combinations were tested for lesion recovery. Proteoglycan content and analysis in the chondral layer and histological analysis were carried out for the whole defect at different healing times after implantation.

Figure 2. Osteochondral defect studied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The differences in the kinetics of matrix reabsorption and, partially the type and degree of differentiation of the cell sources used in the two layers of the implant, greatly affected the quality of the regenerated cartilage and subchondral bone. Figure 3 shows the differences in healing for three example combinations of all studied.

Figure 3. Selected examples of the recovery of the lesion after 1 month post implantation. At the right, histology of the defect in a negative control (no treatment) and a combination of fast cleavable hydrogel in both layers with MSCs at the bottom layer and mature chondrocytes on top one (Fast(B)-fast(C)) or a slow cleavable hydrogel + MSCs on the bottom layer and a fast hydrogel + mature chondrocytes on the top layer (Slow(B)-fast(C)). Right panel shows the results of the immunostaining for Chondroitin Sulphate proteoglycans.

While the recovery of the subchondral bone was quite complete and normal in most of the different combinations tested, the quality of the cartilage was much affected by this parameter. In general, all combinations in which a slow degrading gel was used in the bottom layer (bone) yielded a recovered cartilage of good quality. Quantitative and histological determination on the quality of this resulted in scores close to normal and healthy cartilage. In those cases where a fast hydrogel was used for the bone layer, the quality of the recovered cartilage were clearly worse, although significantly better than the negative control. The influence of the cell type is, to a lesser extent, also relevant. In general, the use of MSCs in the bone layer combined with fully mature chondrocytes in the cartilage layer is better than other cell combinations in the two layers

CONCLUSIONS

The use of protease-target epitopes with different cleavage kinetics adds time control to the existing spatial control in 3D structured hydrogels.

The decoupling of protease sensitiveness from other bioactivities in such 3D structured hydrogels has the potential of time controlling both spatial properties and bioactivity of the hydrogel.

The prolongation in time of the recovery process of the subchondral bone by using slow degrading hydrogels in that area improves significantly the quality of the cartilage formed. If the cells types used align with this; i.e. by using immature cells for the bone layer and fully developed chondrocytes above, an additional increase on the recovery process is observed.

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This work is a collaborative effort among Bioforge, providing the materials, the Orthopedic surgery unit (Dr Aurelio Vega) of the Clinic University Hospital (Valladolid, Spain), designing and performing all the in vivo models and surgery and Dr. Angel Gato (University of Valladolid) in charge of the cartilage quantitative assays and all histological evaluations.

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Polysaccharides as building blocks in tissue engineering applications

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Tissue Engineering has been integrating principles of engineering, chemistry, materials science, biology and health sciences in order to develop regenerative-based therapeutic strategies combining stem cells and biomaterials. From the different sources of biomaterials, natural-based polymers have been proposed to produce matrices able to interact favourably with cells. Due to their hydrophilic nature and richness in chemically active groups, such polymers can be used to produce a variety of structures fabricated using aqueous-based or other environmental-favourable procedures. Examples are shown in the precise chemical modification of polysaccharides and processing of devices into different sizes and shapes with structural and functional characteristics suitable to be used in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine applications. The macromolecular design of the systems may be used to produce special hydrogels with improved mechanical properties. Distinct strategies involving bioinspired approaches and nano/micro-technologies will be shown to prepare hybrid soft systems containing cells, in the form of microparticles, microgels or thin films, that could give rise to biomedical devices using bottom-up strategies.

Light-stimulated collagen production: new approaches to reconstruct tissues

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ABSTRACT

Collagen is a major component of the extracellular matrix, and the most abundant structural protein for the mechanical integrity of tissues. In vivo, collagen molecules self-assemble to form collagen fibrils, beaded filaments or network structures depending on the collagen type. This assembly is the basis for achieving tissue-specific mechanical properties: rigid bone, compliant skin, or gradient mechanics in cartilage tissue. The dynamics of collagen synthesis and deposition plays a crucial role in biological processes such as embryogenesis and tissue regeneration, while it gets dysregulated in pathologies like brittle-bone disease, fibrosis or tumour formation. As the main underlying supportive structure for cells, the deposition of collagen typically precedes and guides the development of tissue architectures. For instance, in lungs, salivary and mammary glands, the spatial distribution and density of pre-deposited collagen directs the formation of branched tissue configurations. In spinal cord and arterial injuries, initial collagen deposition by the underlying fibroblasts is vital for the remodelling and healing processes.

The possibility to regulate collagen deposition specifically, on demand and eventually in a spatially confined manner would open therapeutic ways to treat collagen-related pathologies. In this study, we have taken the first steps in this direction by developing and testing a molecular tool that enables spatiotemporal manipulation of collagen synthesis and deposition from cells stimulated by light. We target the collagen-specific molecular chaperone Hsp47 (Heat shock protein 47) which is vital for collagen biosynthesis in cells. HSP47 plays a fundamental role in the folding, stability and intracellular transport of procollagen triple helices. A photoactivatable Hsp47 version was synthesized, delivered intracellularly and allowed photostimulated secretion of Collagen. The ability to promote collagen synthesis on-demand, with spatiotemporal resolution, and in disease state cells is demonstrated in in vitro cultures and ex vivo tissues. Photoactivatable Hsp47 inspires new therapeutic concepts in biomedicine and tissue regeneration.

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Radical Dendrimers. Synthesis, Characterization and Biomedical Applications

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Our interest is focused on the study of molecular materials based on radical dendrimers, their magnetic properties as well as their biomedical applications.¹ Dendrimers are a very special class of hyperbranched macromolecules, which are synthesized step-by-step in order to ensure a good monodispersity. The three-dimensional structure of these molecules proceed from the central core with exponentially increasing number of repeated units and terminal groups.

The term “radical dendrimers” has been used in the case of highly functionalized dendrimers with organic radicals. There are only few examples of fully functionalized dendrimers with organic radicals to study their magnetic behaviour.

Here we present a series of several generations of dendrimers built with phosphorus as branching points and with nitroxyl radicals as end groups. The interaction between pendant stable radicals at the exterior of the dendritic surface and their dynamic behaviour can be studied by Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR)

spectroscopy. This is important to understand the magnetic properties and other related ones like relaxivity of these functionalized dendrimers. The properties of the radical dendrimers depends on the core dendrimer, the size (generation of the dendrimer), the radical and the linker between the kind of radical and the dendrimer branches.

Molecules with many unpaired electrons, which possess high-spin ground state and stability at room temperature, are particularly challenging and promising targets. For example as contrast agents for Magnetic Resonance Imaging as alternative imaging probes to Gadolinium (Gd) and other metal based contrast agents to overcome their established toxicity.

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Synthesis of crosslinked poly(ester-urethane)s, with potential uses as scaffolds for tissue engineering

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INTRODUCTION

The aim of this present work is to obtain aliphatic crosslinked polyester-urethanes, using PCL-polyols with functionalities $f = 3$ (CapaTM 3091) and $f = 4$ (CAPATM4101), and to characterize them using different techniques: FT-IR, NMR, DSC, swelling degree, solubility in THF and mechanical properties.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Synthesis of PCL-diol

PCL-diols with functionality 2 was obtained by biocatalysis from ϵ -caprolactone CL and a) ethylene glycol (EG), b) diethylene glycol (DEG) and c) polyethylene glycol (PEG) according to reference 1

Synthesis of (polyester-urethane)s

The polymerization was carried out in solution from PCL-diols, PCL-polyols and HDI using a OH:NCO ratio of 1. 1,2-dichloroethane was used as solvent, and tin (II) 2-ethylhexanoate, Sn (Oct)₂, was used as a catalyst

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Molecular weight of three different PCL-diols (HO-PCL-OH) were obtained by ¹H-NMR.¹ 24 poly(ester-urethanes) were obtained from different combinations of PCL-diols, HDI and either trifunctional (CapaTM 3091) or tetrafunctional (CAPATM4101) PCL-polyols. By FT-IR, evidence of total consumption of isocyanate is evident as the signal at 2266 cm⁻¹ is not observed in the final products. Ratio of free (≈ 1720 cm⁻¹) to inter-associated (≈ 1700 cm⁻¹) species through hydrogen-bonding decreases by the presence of crosslinking.

Figure 1: FT-IR spectra (carbonyl zone) of linear (black) and crosslinked (red) poly(ester-urethane)s

The polymer with the highest degree of crystallinity is the poly(ester-urethane) obtained from DEG PCL-diol, the trifunctional monomer Capa 3091 and the diisocyanate HDI, using a ratio 90:10 PCL-diol: Triol. Polymers that have a higher degree of crystallinity (obtained by DSC) also exhibit a higher resistance to the maximum stress of the break and a higher value of the Young's modulus. Poly(ester-urethane)s are more soluble in THF when they are synthesized from the HDI diisocyanate, tri-functional polyo and the PCL-diols DEG and PEG, as expected.

CONCLUSION

Differences in certain properties of the polyurethanes are observed as a function of the degree of crosslinking. At lower degree of crosslinking in the urethane polyesters, higher crystallinity percentage are observed in the polymer chains. As expected, degree of solubility decreases with the presence of crosslinking. Lower degrees of crosslinking and crystallinity led to polyurethanes with elastomeric (TPE) properties; this is the case for samples obtained from PCL-diols containing DEG and PEG; on the other hand, higher crosslinking and crystallinity (PURs containing EG units) led to the formation of thermoplastic-elastomeric (TPE).

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Bioinspired materials and strategies for the fabrication of functional devices

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INTRODUCTION

Bioinspired composites of naturally derived and synthetic polymers provide exciting opportunities to develop soft, flexible, biocompatible, and physiologically compliant devices for diverse applications in healthcare. Bioinspired materials can serve not only as the structural, but also as the functional components of such devices. This poses material-specific functionalization, and fabrication related challenges in the design and fabrication of these systems. Materials such as natural protein biopolymers (e.g. silk) and polysaccharides (e.g. chitin) show tremendous promise in this regard due to intrinsic properties of tunable mechanical performance, optical transparency, biocompatibility, biodegradability, and processability. We will discuss some of the recent work from our group in transitioning from the raw materials to biocomposites that can be used as biosensors, electrodes, biophotonic elements, drug delivery vehicles, and energy storage devices.

Figure 1: Flexible substrates with microscale resolution can be formed as devices or for spatial patterning of cells

The surface of these films can be tailored by decorating with functional patterns (e.g. conducting ink) using a photolithographic technique, which permits the formation of complex, high resolution architectures at high throughput and scale (over several cm). These patterns may be used as a biosensor for detecting analytes [2, 3]. These flexible micropatterns can be used as energy storage devices [4]. Cell-adhesive micropatterns are able to spatially direct cells. In addition to the patterns, it is also possible to modulate the mechanical characteristics of the patterns.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Photo-crosslinkable conjugates were synthesized as previously described [1]. Microfabrication of flexible devices is realized using light-reactive conjugates and facile photolithographic techniques. For instance, patterns of sericin-based biocomposite ink with the conducting polymer PEDOT:PSS was shown on flexible fibroin substrates using different solvents (viz. sericin in water, fibroin in formic acid or HFIP). Similarly, photocrosslinking of a chitin conjugate was accomplished as both the substrate and the patterns.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The use of photolithography provides a rapid route to form complex patterns that are not easily prepared using microcontact printing or molding [1]. The facile fabrication of micropatterned, free standing films of the silk proteins that are flexible and can be used for controlling cellular organization. The films themselves are mechanically robust, can be formed at various thicknesses ranging from ultrathin (<1 μm) to thick (10s of microns), and can be controllably degradable (**Figure 1**). The

CONCLUSION

In summary, we show the use of bioinspired materials and strategies for the formation of functional devices using microfabrication techniques. These devices can be used as active functional tools as biosensors, biophotonics, as well as active cellular substrates. The ease of fabrication, biochemical functionalization, biocompatibility, as well as tunable mechanical properties and biodegradation of these biomaterials provide unique possibilities as sustainable, bioresorbable microdevices.

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Methods for silk scaffolds fabrication

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Silk fibroin is one of most studied biopolymers for applications as scaffold for tissue engineering, thanks in turn to its peculiar biological properties coupled with biodegradability mainly depending on the adopted processing conditions and final material/scaffold morphology. “Traditional” fabrication methods comprise salt leaching or freeze-drying of fibroin-water solutions, casting, electrospinning and gel formation by sonication, temperature cycling, or addition of acids.

Other methods have been more lately developed, some passing through the chemical modification of fibroin and its crosslinking, suggested, for instance, for additive manufacturing or bioprinting techniques. We have recently fabricated solid fibroin structure by a low temperature sintering procedure based on an optimized thermal-reflow technique.

The term thermal reflow generally defines a mechanism that takes place when the glass transition temperature of the material is lower than the temperature used to process it. We have succeeded in the application of the sintering manufacturing on lyophilized silk fibroin at already 40 °C, associating water addition through moisture absorption and a high-pressure compression.

The technique allowed the fabrication of solid monoliths from fibroin powder in a single compression mold step at low temperature, with the possibility to produce large objects can be produced in few minutes with a high reproducibility and also to add temperature degradable bioactive additives thanks to the mild processing conditions.

The lecture will review some of the fabrication methods used to process fibroin with emphasis on the lately developed ones and in particular on the powder sintering.

Chemical Strategies to tailor the properties of hyaluronic acid-based materials

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INTRODUCTION

Over the past years, research attention has been focused on natural polymers (i.e. hyaluronic acid (HA)) which can be employed as efficient drug delivery systems, as scaffolds for tissue engineering and recently also as bioink for additive manufacturing¹. In this study different chemical strategies were pursued and combined to improve HA's properties: i) HA was chemically modified through two different methods to endow it with a shear thinning behaviour, ii) an innovative HA-based double network (DN) hydrogel, was developed for load bearing tissues, iii) a nanocomposite material was synthesized by HA biomineralization through sol-gel reaction, and employed for osteochondral tissue and for anti-inflammatory molecules delivery.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

HA functionalization strategy - HA ($M_w \approx 340$ kDa) was functionalized to obtain methacrylated (MEHA) and maleated hyaluronic acid (MAHA) and investigated in terms of physico-chemical properties. Furthermore, the ink printability was optimized and materials were processed using a modified 3D Bioprinter® system from MedPrin Regenerative Medical Technologies Co., Ltd- (Guangzhou-China). Scaffolds were morphologically and mechanically characterized.

DN approach - DN hydrogels were obtained by a two-step procedure. Crosslinked hydrogels (1st network) were immersed in a poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate (PEGDA)/water solution (10 wt %) until reaching equilibrium and further crosslinked (2nd network). The effect of 2nd network and concentration of each component on the properties of the DN hydrogels were analysed.

Biomineralization by in situ sol-gel approach - Composite materials were produced by *in situ* sol-gel synthesis in distilled water. Nanocomposites were characterized in terms of inorganic filler size and distribution. Nanocomposite materials were loaded with Diclofenac Sodium (DS). Biological assays were performed using fibroblasts and macrophages for cytotoxicity and anti-inflammatory tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance highlighted the peaks related to the introduced methacrylate and maleic moieties. Morphological analyses of 3D printed scaffolds showed a well-organized structure able to retain the structure without collapsing in the Z direction. Mechanical properties of MEHA scaffolds revealed values of the storage modulus (E') higher than MAHA ones. For DN hydrogels a 10-time increase of E' was observed. The *in situ* biomineralization of modified HA allowed the formation of hydroxyapatite and dicalcium phosphates. Cell adhesion studies demonstrated that the presence of 25% of calcium phosphate (CaP) improves cell vitality and differentiation. Release test showed a strong correlation between chemical modification and DS release kinetics. Furthermore, the presence of DS in composite hydrogels reduced TNF- α release, stimulating the production of an anti-inflammatory cytokine such as IL-10.

CONCLUSION

The three different approaches, based on the chemically-modified HA, either alone or in combination with other polymers or CaP, allowed to obtain biomaterials useful for the specific application.

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Engineering of bioactive surface coatings and hydrogels with polysaccharides

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INTRODUCTION

Polysaccharides belong to the most abundant biomaterials on earth. They form structural elements of plant and animal tissues, but many of them have also important regulatory functions towards cells, tissues and organs. Glycosaminoglycans (GAG) and other carboxylated and sulfated polysaccharides possess a bioactivity that is due to their high affinity to a plethora of proteins forming insoluble and soluble components of cell environments, but performing also in direct interaction with receptors that control cell fate.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Making surface coatings for implants from natural or semisynthetic GAG that guide cell behavior requires different strategies of covalent or physical attachment. Simple covalent binding mechanisms can be based on oxidation of pendant hydroxyl groups of monosaccharide subunits forming aldehyde groups or introduction of reactive side groups like thiols that permit direct coupling to surfaces. Physical immobilisation can exploit the inherent charge of these molecules that permits formation of multilayers kept together by ion pairing, but also intrinsic cross-linking of activated GAG with with pendant groups of polyelectrolytes using layer-by-layer technique. Both mechanisms can be also applied to form 3D structures as biocompatible in situ gelling hydrogels systems that permit embedding of growth factors and cells.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We will present here multilayer systems made sulfated cellulose [1] that possesses a bioactivity towards growth factors and cells similar to heparin [2, 3]. Furthermore, we will show how intrinsic cross-linking of multilayer coatings by imine and disulfide-bond formation affects cells adhesion, growth and differentiation [4, 5]. We will also demonstrate that oxidized polysaccharides in combination with polysaccharides like chitosan can be used to develop biocompatible in situ gelling systems that can be used to differentiate mesenchymal stem cells in chondrocytes for tissue engineering of cartilage [6].

CONCLUSION

These 2D and 3D systems are instructive controlling cell spreading, growth and differentiation, which will be shown with examples on chondrogenic and osteogenic differentiation of cells.

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Functional Nanofibrous Scaffolds Combined with Stem Cells for Advanced Biomedical Devices and Therapies**N.M. Neves**^{1,2,3}

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INTRODUCTION

Among the various possible embodiments of Advanced Therapies and in particular of Tissue Engineering the use of temporary scaffolds to regenerate tissue defects is one of the key issues. The scaffolds should be specifically designed to create environments that promote tissue development and not merely to support the maintenance of communities of cells. To achieve that goal, highly functional scaffolds may combine specific morphologies and surface chemistry with the local release of bioactive agents.

Many biomaterials have been proposed to produce scaffolds aiming the regeneration of a wealth of human tissues. We have a particular interest in developing systems based in biodegradable polymers. Those demanding applications require a combination of mechanical properties, processability, cell-friendly surfaces and tunable biodegradability that need to be tailored for the specific application envisioned. Those biomaterials are usually processed by different routes into devices with wide range of morphologies such as biodegradable fibers and meshes, films or particles and adaptable to different biomedical applications.

In our approach, we combine the temporary scaffolds populated with therapeutically relevant communities of cells to generate a hybrid implant. For that we have explored different sources of adult and also embryonic stem cells. We are exploring the use of adult MSCs, namely obtained from the bone marrow for the development autologous-based therapies. We also develop strategies based in extra-embryonic tissues, such as the perivascular region of the umbilical cord (Wharton's Jelly).

We are currently involved in a European consortium aiming at developing films with antimicrobial properties to be used in hospitals to cover surfaces that are prone to facilitate the transmission of infections. Those films use surface topographies and natural-derived oils to ensure the needed antibacterial properties to the films.

This talk will review our latest developments of functionalized biomaterials and scaffolds in combination with stem cells for advanced biomedical devices and therapies.

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3-D Neural Culture System to Study Neuroinflammation and Neurotoxicity

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INTRODUCTION

Preclinical cellular test-beds are useful tools to test cell response to drugs, materials, toxins, and cell-based therapies. We have developed an iPSC-derived 3-D multitypic brain-on-a chip system in which we are able to perfuse the culture wells individually with a small amount of media, permitting *in vivo*-like nutrient-waste exchange, superior viability (versus 2-D or unperfused cultures), and concentrated secretome and metabolome for sensitive assessment of chemokine release.

Inflammation of the central nervous system is of particular interest in injury, disease, and off-target therapeutic effects. We have previously shown that 3-D neural cultures shown an inflammatory response when mechanically injured¹ or exposed to lipopolysaccharide (LPS), and that neural stem cells introduced to injured cultures have poor survival². Here, we study off-target neurotoxicity of T-cell cancer therapy by introducing CD3/CD28 Ab-activated Jurkat cell conditioned media or activated human T cells to 3-D neural cultures.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Human iPSC cultures (10^6) were plated in medium into SeedEZ™ scaffolds coated with poly-D-lysine (PDL) (100 µg/mL) with an overall cell ratio of 2:2:1 neurons:astrocytes:microglia. Jurkat and human T-cells were treated with antibodies against CD3 and CD28 for 24 hrs to produce conditioned medium. In separate cultures, T-cells (100,000, 2 weeks post activation) were co-cultured with neural cultures to simulate a blood-brain barrier breach. Positive controls consisted of lipopolysaccharide (LPS) (100 ng/mL) and/or interferon gamma (IFN γ) (10 ng/mL) treatment for 24 hours. Levels of cytokines in the medium were quantified using ELISAs specific for human TNF α and human CXCL10. Data were analysed by one-way ANOVA and Tukey's post-hoc test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A pro-inflammatory phenotype was confirmed by gene expression and protein release from 3-D cultures in response to LPS and IFN γ treatment. 3-D brain cultures exhibit a stark inflammatory response when treated with CD3/CD28 Ab-activated Jurkat cell conditioned media compared to LPS stimulation. Direct exposure to activated primary human T-cells with either conditioned media or fresh media demonstrated that T-cells in conditioned media as well as the conditioned medium alone elevated the levels of CXCL10 release, while T cells in fresh medium did not, suggesting that the cytokines themselves are the key actors in producing the inflammatory response.

CONCLUSION

The brain-on-a-chip system can be used to elucidate mechanisms of inflammation-induced cell death and test mitigating strategies, providing a tool to streamline clinical translation of treatments for brain injury and therapies that negatively impact neural function.

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Antibacterial Systems for Dental Applications

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INTRODUCTION

A major challenge in healthcare is the maintenance of oral health. Decayed or damaged dental tissues is a prevalent condition that affects nearly all adult population and over 60% of children in the world. Endodontic diseases including dental caries and infection consequent to trauma or operative procedures are usually characterized by loss of integrity of the crown, invasion by microorganisms and destruction of enamel, dentine, and ultimately the dental pulp. Root canal treatment (RCT) is often required after endodontic disease when the tooth becomes infected or is severely decayed. Although the RCT success rate is good, the complex anatomy of the root canal system in addition to the presence of resilient pathogenic bacteria, limitations of current chemo-mechanical instrumentation and obturation methods often limit the success of the treatment. Dental root canal infections are biofilm mediated and the properties of bacteria that inhabit a biofilm are different from those of planktonic cells as bacterial congregations show higher resistance to antimicrobial agents. The first step of RCT involves mechanical debridement and irrigation of the root canal with sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) solution, which remains the gold standard but often, is not enough to rid the root canal off bacteria that tend to form a biofilm. The subsequent steps involve restoration of the tooth with obturating materials such as gutta percha that are used with a cement and in some instances an endodontic post is required to provide retention of the final coronal restoration.

There is a rising interest in endowing dental restorative materials with sustained antibacterial activity to enhance long term performance, which is expected to lower the risk of reinfection and secondary caries. Different antibacterial agents such as chlorhexidine, fluoride, quaternary ammonium and metallic agents (silver, gold and zinc) have been incorporated in acrylic based composite formulation in order to achieve this goal. However, most of these additives can cause adverse effects on mechanical properties, discoloration of material, toxicity and short-term antibacterial effectiveness. More recently, the unique properties of nanoparticles with potential antibacterial action, physical and biological properties have seen applications in dental treatment and early evidence suggests encouraging therapeutic potential.

This paper firstly describes the synthesis of silver nanoparticles on graphene oxide (Ag-GO) with results of the antimicrobial and biofilm disruption ability in comparison to conventional methods used for irrigation and cleansing of dental root canal using a new tooth model developed by us to validate the in vitro findings. Secondly, the synthesis and application of eugenyl methacrylate, a methacrylate derivative of eugenol is described and its efficacy as an antibacterial agent in dental bonding, post and core is discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Ag NPs were prepared by reducing AgNO_3 with NaBH_4 in presence of GO suspension to obtain Ag-GO particles and compared with other commonly used irrigating fluids and agitating systems. For quantitative measurement of the microbial viable counts, 3-point sampling was performed with sterile paper points and dispersed into 1ml of Brain-Heart infusion Broth, Lab M) and vortexed for 2min, diluted, plated onto FAA plates and incubated anaerobically at 37°C for a week, then numbers of colonies and their \log_{10} ($\log_{10}\text{CFU}$) were counted.

Eugenyl methacrylate (EgMA) was synthesized as reported earlier¹. The composites were prepared with bisGMA, TEGDMA and EgMA with hydroxyapatite/zirconia filler whilst bonding agents were formulated with commercial mixes.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The microbial killing and biofilm disruption capacity of Ag-GO was successfully achieved using a novel ex vivo infected tooth model. Although NaOCl 2.5% showed superior antimicrobial efficacy at all sampling sites, ultrasonic activation selectively enhanced the microbial killing and biofilm disruption with Ag-GO in lateral canals. Acrylic resin composites containing eugenol methacrylate derivative EgMA was obtained by dual polymerization mechanism that exhibited outstanding properties as potential new luting/core resin composite materials for post placement in with remarkable enhanced features in comparison with currently used dental composite core materials.

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Rational Design of Responsive Prodrug-based Nanomedicines for Antitumor Therapy

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INTRODUCTION

The field of polymer therapeutics is evolving rapidly and thus producing a multitude of different drug delivery systems (DDS). In general, these systems are composed of water-soluble polymers that act as inert functional nanocarriers for improved drug, imaging agent, protein, or gene delivery¹. Polymer drug conjugates can overcome the limitations of small molecule drugs due to a reduced body clearance, passive targeting, and controlled drug release all leading to a higher concentration of drugs at the site of action and minimized toxic side effects². Gathering information about successful delivery and intracellular drug release of polymer-drug conjugates before expensive and time-consuming in vivo investigations are performed is of great importance. Cytotoxicity assays and fluorescence microscopy are nowadays the main tools for evaluating the performance of DDS in vitro. Although they provide valuable information, e.g. cytotoxicity and details about intracellular fate, these assays do not allow to correlate the performance of DDS with their cellular uptake and drug release. Herein, we present smart fluorescent probes that overcome such limitations and enable the fast and simultaneous screening of DDS in simple yet meaningful fluorescent assays. The gathered information was used to rationally design a size-changing nanogel as a multistage DDS.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this work, we developed a series of dendritic polymer-based conjugates that enabled the study of the intracellular drug/dye release triggered by acidic environment or enzyme overexpression. Several methodologies, such as fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM), life cell imaging³, and cell-based microplate assay^{4,5}, were used to track the recovery of the conjugates fluorescence as signal of conjugate cleavage.

The conjugates were applied to obtain characteristic release profiles for doxorubicin (Dox) in different cell lines using a facile microplate assay which allows high throughput screening of different cell lines and DDS simultaneously. The correlation of the cell-mediated Dox release profiles with the cytotoxicity of the conjugates demonstrated the theranostic character of the conjugates and gave valuable information about the implication of the linker design. For the linkers investigated, we found that the pH-cleavable linker was more suitable for the drug delivery approach, because premature, extracellular Dox release was observed for the protease-sensitive system. This was particularly important for the treatment of multidrug-resistant KB-V1 cells where the intracellular drug release is crucial in order to circumvent the resistance mechanism. However, we found that for MDA-MB-231 cells, the protease-sensitive conjugate was more effective to inhibit the cell proliferation. We further developed matrix metalloproteinase (MMP)-sensitive peptide-crosslinked nanogels (pNGs) with beneficial size shrinking property for deep tumor penetration. The intrinsic reporter moiety of the crosslinker was exploited to study the degradation of pNGs with different compositions in detail. In addition, Dox was conjugated to the pNGs by a pH-sensitive linkage yielding a two-stage delivery system. The degradable multistage pNGs demonstrated enhanced penetration into multicellular tumor spheroids compared to their non-degradable counterparts.

CONCLUSION

The correlation of the fluorescence recovery with the cytotoxicity profiles of the conjugates demonstrated the theranostic character of the developed smart probes. Since neither cell disruption nor organelle isolation was needed, but rather the measurement could be done in real time, we postulate that such smart probes should be able to unfold more easily the implications from the linker design on drug toxicity. Furthermore, we performed a proof of concept study demonstrating that the size-changing property of the pNGs can facilitate the infiltration into tumor resembling multicellular tumor spheroids models to promote the penetration of the nanocarrier and the delivery of a chemotherapeutic drug.

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Dendritic nanosystems of carbosilane nature as a versatile platform for the treatment of different pathologies

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INTRODUCTION

Dendrimers and dendrons are multivalent macromolecules, they are monodisperse, with well-defined structure and size, as consequence of their controlled synthesis.^{1,2} These characteristics are very attractive for biomedical applications.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Carbosilane dendrimers are made of C-C and C-Si bonds. This framework is stable and highly hydrophobic. For biomedical applications, it is very important to give them solubility in water. This is achieved introducing ionic moieties at the periphery. The modification of this periphery is mainly done using hydrosilylation reactions, thiol-ene and azide-alkyne additions, and Si-Cl bond substitution. Antibacterial, antiviral and antitumoral assays were made according to established methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The type of peripheral group at dendrimer periphery determines the application. On one hand, cationic carbosilane dendrimers show antibacterial activity.³ On the other hand, anionic dendrimers present relevant antiviral ability. The multianionic periphery of dendrimers blocks viral capsid proteins or cell receptors related with virus infection.⁴ Finally, metallodendrimers are active in different cell lines, including advanced prostate cancer (PC3).⁵

CONCLUSION

Combining different synthetic procedures it is possible to prepare a library of carbosilane dendrimers for biomedical applications. The peripheral groups of dendrimer determine the application in biomedicine, highlighting the antibacterial, antiviral and antitumoral properties.

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Oligopeptides and Recombinamers at Surfaces and Interfaces to Address Oral Infections

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INTRODUCTION

Infections of the oral tissues are widely prevalent diseases with high social and economic consequences worldwide. We are in need of preventing and/or treat oral infections using strategies that are aimed to combat bacteria access, adhesion, growth and formation of biofilms on oral surfaces and dental devices. Functionalization of biomaterials and human tissues with multiple bioactivities is desired to obtain surfaces with improved clinical performance.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

We treated oral tissues and titanium with peptides or elastin-like recombinant polymers (ELRs) containing peptide bioactive sequences. The GL13K peptide and laminin-derived peptides are the two peptides that we have more frequently used in our lab. Control of pH and concentration of the biomolecules in solution has been used to induce assembly of the biomolecules and/or reactivity with linkers to tether the biomolecules to synthetic surfaces, such as titanium or zirconia. We have performed thorough physical-chemical characterization of the biomolecular coatings, including their characterization after simulative oral challenges. We assessed antimicrobial and antibiofilm properties of the coatings against mono- and multi-species oral bacteria. This included the use of a drip-flow bioreactor that simulates the flow conditions of oral fluids in the mouth. We also assessed the cytocompatibility of the antimicrobial peptide coatings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We have developed bio-inspired coatings and interfaces made of ELRs or oligopeptides for bone and dental pulp regeneration, protection of dentinal tissues, and antimicrobial properties. ELRs containing motifs for biomimetic mineralization or antimicrobial activity; amphipathic and antimicrobial peptides derived from the parotid salivary protein; and laminin-derived peptides for inducing permucoosal healing are examples of synthetic biomolecules we have used to biologically activate titanium, zirconia, collagen fibers/scaffolds, dentin, and enamel.

GL13K is an amphipathic and antimicrobial peptide based on the sequence of the salivary protein BPIFA2. The control of the secondary structure of the peptides and their ability to form organized and assembled layers to provide highly hydrophobic interfaces on synthetic and natural materials are key parameters that we have explored to increase their potential clinical use to prevent and treat highly-prevalent oral infectious diseases.

CONCLUSION

The use of biomolecules to modify the surfaces of tissues and synthetic materials constitutes a versatile and powerful strategy to address oral infectious diseases; that is, the most prevalent diseases worldwide.

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Making the literature of lactic acid-based polymers profitable to everyone

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INTRODUCTION

For more than 60 years scientists and users have studied and exploited polymers and copolymers containing lactic acid-based segments primarily for applications taking advantage of degradability. The frequent lack of identification makes most data and conclusions of little interest to compare their structures, properties and performances. The IUPAC Subcommittee on Polymer Terminology made new nomenclature and terminology recommendations to be applied in all fields concerned by the science and the applications of lactic acid-based polymers, especially those the biomedical one.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Literature was explored to collect information on the influences of the existence of different chiral monomers, of different routes to transform them in polymers, and of structural factors that affect material properties, hydrolytic degradation and aging.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Eight rules were issued to name lactic acid-based polymers and copolymers and abbreviate the names while respecting the IUPAC rules of polymer nomenclature [2].

Rule 1 and 2 recall that names must be constructed according to the IUPAC structure-based or source-based naming modes. **Rule 3** recalls that chain ends are to be specified as “ α -end _{α} - ω -end _{ω} ” before “poly”, whereas **Rule 4** indicates that the chiral unit composition of lactic acid-based polymers is to be indicated as (*a:b x*) separated by a space from the name of the polymer, *x* indicating that numerals *a* and *b* correspond to the amount-of-substance fractions of lactic enantiomeric units, respectively. According to **Rule 5**, the chiral unit distribution in stereocopolymers deduced from the contents in *m* and *r* diads is indicated as (*z % m diads*), *z* being the numeral corresponding to the percentage [$100m/(m+r)$] of *m* diads. This specification is inserted after the composition in chiral units and a comma within the same set of parentheses. **Rule 6** recalls that in the case of copolymers composed of lactic acid-based monomers and achiral monomers, the IUPAC recommendations for indicating the composition is italicized *a, b, c, ...n x* where *a, b, c ...n* are the amount of substance fractions of the corresponding monomers or constitutional units expressed in the name as roman numerals when they are known, and according to the order of the corresponding monomers or constitutional units [2], which are usually cited in alphabetical order. **Rule 7** proposes PLA as generic acronym applicable to abbreviate the name of lactic acid-based polymers, complemented by the structural descriptors included in rules 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 whenever these descriptors play critical roles relative to material properties and hydrolytic degradation. The recommended generic abbreviation is then:

$$\text{end}_{\alpha}, \text{end}_{\omega}\text{-PLAX}, z$$

where *X* is a variable representing the content in *S* units present in the polymer ($X = 100a$ or $100b$ or $100c$ or ... $100n$ depending on the location of the (*S*) lactic unit in the name), and *z* is the percentage of *m* lactic unit diads. **Rule 8** specifies that for copolymers of lactic acid and lactide monomers with at least one other monomer, the generic abbreviation (rule 7) must be complemented by the abbreviation of the other unit and a number for the corresponding content. Typical examples will be discussed.

CONCLUSION

These new IUPAC recommendations [1] provide means to better define and exploit lactic acid-based polymers. They are presently under public reviewing (<https://iupac.org/recommendations/under-review-by-the-public/>).

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In vitro degradability of strontium delivery systems based on oxidized bacterial cellulose and strontium apatite

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INTRODUCTION

Guided bone regeneration (GBR) is a surgical procedure that involves the use of materials that serve as a physical barrier preventing the migration of non-osteogenic tissues to sites where osteogenesis should occur¹. However, some commercial membranes used in this type of procedure are not absorbable, implying a second surgical procedure for its removal, which could cause psychological stress to patients, and risks of lesions and infections in the regenerated tissue^{2,3}. The present work aimed to expand the possibilities of application of strontium release systems based on oxidized bacterial cellulose (BC) and strontium apatite as reabsorbable and bioactive membranes for use in GBR, evaluating its biodegradability and bioactivity against fluids that mimic the saline and ionic concentration of human blood plasma.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

To produce reabsorbable BC membranes, oxidations with sodium periodate were carried out, evaluating the influence of the oxidation degree on the degradability of the material in phosphate buffered saline (PBS), the degradation product was quantified by HPLC and also evaluated by its mass loss. The samples were characterized by the swelling degree, FTIR, TGA, MEV-EDS and XRD. In addition, the membranes were also evaluated for their bioactivity in the simulated body fluid (SBF).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The quantification of the degradation products by HPLC confirmed the results of mass loss. These results showed that there was an increase in the amount of glucose (BC basic unit) in both PBS and SBF supernatants, giving evidence of BC degradation. After 60 and 90 days of immersion in PBS the main components found were glucose and butyric acid. As expected, the glucose concentrations in the SBF solutions were lower than in PBS justified by the occurrence of bioactivity confirmed by SEM-EDS with the visualization and chemical composition identification of mineral deposits on the membrane surfaces.

CONCLUSION

We conclude that oxidation with sodium periodate is an alternative chemical modification to optimize material biodegradability in physiological conditions. It was also possible to observe the bioactivity of the materials produced by identifying mineral depositions of calcium, magnesium and potassium under their surfaces. The mentioned elements contribute in the mechanisms of bone formation.

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Silks: spider and silkworm, where the differences?

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INTRODUCTION

Silk from silkworms have attained increasing interest in the last 10-15 years for applications in medicine and namely in tissue engineering. In addition to silkworms, other animals produced materials commonly named as silks, as spiders, wasps, bees, and other insects.

The different silks differs for composition and properties, tailored from nature to the requirements, i.e., prey catching and also preserving for spiders and nest where the transformation from moth to butterfly will occur, for silkworms.

While silkworm produces filaments with constant composition in the cocoons, spiders use for the same web filaments with different composition properties and role.

For obvious procurement reasons, silkworm silk has found practical applications in medicine, the relevance of the spider silk being limited by the difficulties in harvesting spiders and collecting large amounts of silks.

In this presentation, we compare degummed (DS) and undegummed (SC) silk produced by *Bombyx mori* silkworms, and by two different spiders, *Linothele megatheloides* (LM), which produces a single type of silk in a relatively large amount, and *Cupiennius salei* (DL) spider.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Silks from *Bombyx mori* silkworm, *Linothele megatheloides* spider, and of the web-dragline of *Cupiennius salei* spider, isolated in our spider farm, have been compared in terms of aminoacidic composition, mechanical properties, morphology and biological properties in cell culture, by using standard apparatus and procedures.

In particular, biological properties have been assessed comparatively in arrays of couples of fibers to evidence the biological competition between the different types of silks. In addition, samples of nets or web have been used, to better determine cell adhesion and metabolism.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All the results will be presented and discussed in the lecture.

In this abstract the results of the single fiber cultures are evidenced in the figure, where the confocal images at day 1 and 2 of the NIH 3T3 cell culture tests are reported.

Well evident is the much larger preferential early adhesion of cells on the LM silk filament with respect to the DL, SC and DS silks at day one, persisting at day 2 for the silkworm silks.

Considerations about the aminoacidic compositions of the different silks, as well as on the practical exploitation of the spider silks, will be subject of analysis at the conference.

Plasma Pyrrole Polymers as Implants In Spinal Cord Chronic Injury: MRI Study

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INTRODUCTION

Several studies have shown an efficient use of the iodine-doped polypyrrole (PPyI) implant, synthesized by plasma, for functional recovery, as a treatment after a Traumatic Spinal Cord Injury (TSCI) ^{1,2} in the acute phase of the injury. This paper shows the results of the application of the PPyI implant as a treatment after a TSCI, in a chronic phase, studied by Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI).

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Twelve rats were occupied, Long Evans, adult females, weighing between 215-240 g, divided into 2 groups: implant and control. An LTME was caused at the height of the 9th thoracic vertebra, placing PPyI in the implant group 4 weeks after the injury. Weekly, recovery of locomotors function was measured, under the Basso, Beattie and Bresnahan (BBB) evaluation scale.

A longitudinal study of MRI 7T was performed in the following times after the injury: 2 days, 3 weeks (before implantation), 5 weeks (after implantation), 8 and 11 weeks. Fractional Anisotropy (FA) values were obtained by processing in DSI Studio software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Significant differences were found between the means of both groups for BBB [Figure A] and FA [Figure B], showing a better recovery after a TSCI for the implant group with respect to the control group. For apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) there were significant differences with respect to the time in each week of evaluation. Statistical significance was found in the correlation of the values obtained for the ADC and FA variables for all the data. The MRI's morphometric analysis showed qualitative and quantitative differences, such as the coalescence of cysts derived from the lesion's physiological events, with greater coalescence for the control group.

CONCLUSION

This work shows the viability of the use of PPyI as a treatment of LTME in the chronic phase. In addition, we present data and tools that could expand the use of quantifiable variables and morphology using MRI, as a complementary evaluation in the diagnosis of the aforementioned injury.

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The Goldilocks principle applied to nanomedicine design

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ABSTRACT

The Goldilocks principle, named by analogy to the fable The Three Bears, states that a given output must fall within certain margins of its corresponding input. In simpler words is the concept of “just the right amount” and applies to a wide range of disciplines and Nanomedicine is no exception. In last years we have to explore this concept varying critical parameters of a given carrier including size, ligands affinity and avidity and combining both theoretical and experimental physics we disclose non-linear relations where we identified particular ranges where a given nanomedicine can effectively enter a cell, target a specific cellular population, escape immune riddance etc. I will discuss these concepts in detail using the brain as a case study, where we developed synthetic vesicles, known as polymersomes, with long circulation time in the blood, target phenotypically brain endothelial cells, cross them and access the brain to target either specific local cells or neoplastic cells subsequently.

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Complement proteins regulating macrophage polarisation on biomaterials

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INTRODUCTION

The prevalence of the lack of correlation between *in vitro* and *in vivo* is a significant problem on biomaterial evaluation for clinical purposes, specifically on dental implantology¹. This problem can be minimized conditioning protein attachment by introducing new surface modifications. Protein adsorption might condition biological response and consequently the implant successfulness. (3-glycidoxypropyl)-trimethoxysilane (GPTMS), an organically modified alkoxysilane, is highly regarded as a precursor in the synthesis of various types of sol-gel materials, which can be employed as implant coatings to enhance bone formation on titanium dental implants². In the past, this compound was associated with biocompatibility problems, impairing osseointegration³. On the adsorption of complement-related proteins to this material and their consequent effect on immune cell conditioning may reside the reason for this impairment.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

MC3T3-E1 and RAW 264.7 cell lines were cultured on coated titanium discs at a concentration of 1×10^4 cells well¹, in 24-well culture plates. qRT-PCR was used to define osteogenic markers ALP, IL-6, COL I and TGF- β . Protein liberation of the pro-inflammatory markers TNF- α and IL1 β and the anti-inflammatory markers IL-10 and TGF- β by RAW 264.7 was quantified by ELISA.

Immunostaining using IL7-R (M1 marker) and CD206 (M2 marker) for mouse macrophages was performed. Proteomic analysis was made using mass spectrometry analysis (LC-MS/MS), followed by statistical analysis carried out using Progenesis software.

In vivo experimentation was done using New Zealand rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) as experimental model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Upregulation of TGF- β on MC3T3-E1 osteoblastic cells was observed on the materials with GPTMS in a dose dependent manner, showing a probable osteogenic behaviour on this type of materials. At the same time, an increased release of TNF- α and IL-10 by RAW 264.7 macrophages and higher IL7-R fluorescence tops up the pro-inflammatory potential of GPTMS-doped materials. Higher concentrations of complement activators of distinct pathways, namely FCN2 and CRP, were found on a dose dependent manner, with consequent higher attachment of complement proteins, such as C3 and C5, showing a probable correlation between macrophage differentiation onto M1 phenotype and higher complement protein adsorption.

This fact is corroborated by their worst osseointegration when it is implanted on the rabbit animal model, boosting higher density of multinucleated giant cells surrounding the GPTMS-containing materials.

CONCLUSION

A correlation between the adsorption of complement-related proteins and the higher presence pro-inflammatory phenotype M1 of RAW 264.7 macrophages was observed. The increased adsorption of this type of proteins and consequent predominance of this type of phenotype onto the material surface could compromise the material osseointegration.

Our results suggest the possibility of an alternative *in vitro* approach to assess *in vivo* performance of bone biomaterials, using proteomic analysis and macrophage phenotype characterisation.

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Engineering bacteria to produce added value biomaterials from wastes

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INTRODUCTION

Bacterial biopolymers are very attractive materials due to their biodegradability and non-toxicity. In a Circular Economy context, they can be produced using wastes as feedstocks in sustainable bioprocesses. Our group is interested in the production of biomaterials derived from polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) and bacterial cellulose (BC), and their application in biomedicine by their functionalization with antimicrobial proteins such as enzybiotics (1).

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

PHA and BC were produced as previously described (2, 3). *MinP-fusion proteins*: Based on hydrophatic profile of the N-terminal region of PhaF responsible for PHA binding in *Pseudomonas putida* KT2440, several potential PHA affinity tags were constructed and fused to GFP as a reporter system. The fusion proteins were produced in *P. putida* and their affinity and stability were tested *in vivo* and *in vitro*. *CBD-enzybiotic fusion protein*: The coding gene sequence of the synthetic gene EZB1-CBD was cloned in the expression vector pET29 and cloned in *Escherichia coli* BL21(DE3) cells. Expression conditions were optimized by varying the temperature, inducer concentration and culture time. Purification and immobilization of EZB1-CBD was performed by binding affinity of the CBD domain of the fusion protein to BC membranes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The aim of this work was to design and produce peptide/protein functionalized biomaterials based on the bacterial biopolymers PHA and BC produced from wastes. We have developed two approaches by using specific affinity tags to display functional proteins on i) PHA beads by MinP affinity tag, derived from PhaF phasin of *P. putida* and ii) and BC hydrogels by a Cellulose Binding Domain from *Clostridium cellulovorans* (CBD_{clos} tag) for the immobilization of enzybiotics on BC-based devices. Firstly, we have designed the PHA affinity tag MinP based on the predicted model of PhaF, a protein with surfactant properties able to associate to PHA (4). Various polypeptides were tested differing in polarity, amphipaticity and length. MinP was selected as the best candidate. The stability of the MinP functionalized PHA particles were demonstrated. Secondly, we have achieved the production of a fusion protein with antimicrobial activity able to bind to BC hydrogels through its CBD affinity tag. The antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* of EZB1-CBD was demonstrated by a particular antimicrobial assay that was specifically designed for these materials.

CONCLUSION

Bacterial biopolymers produced from wastes can be converted into antimicrobial scaffolds for medical applications.

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Nanotechnology for the treatment of sensorineural hearing loss

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Sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) is caused by the degeneration or degradation of the hair cells in the cochlea or damage to the auditory nerve [1]. One of the most important causes of SNHL is ototoxicity or the functional impairment and cellular degradation of the inner ear tissues due to the use of therapeutic agents, such as platinum-based chemotherapeutic agents [2]. *Cis*-diaminedichloroplatinum(II) or cisplatin (CDDP) is widely used in the treatment of neoplastic entities, however it presents associated severe side effects, including associated hearing loss, tinnitus and dizziness due to cochlea damage. CDDP induces apoptosis of the inner ear cells by different mechanisms, being hearing impairment observed when the clinical doses are higher than 100 mg/m² affecting first to the high frequencies and progresses to midrange.

Actual pharmacotherapy to palliate CDDP ototoxicity (*i.e.* corticoids, antioxidants or caspase inhibitors) is not efficient enough due to the difficulty to reach the inner ear because of the multiple barriers that protect this organ. The aim of this presentation is to show how nanotechnology can palliate the current limitations of traditional treatments such as low solubility, low stability, molecular size, related side effects and offer a sustained and targeted drug delivery approach.

Our group has developed a series of nanoparticles (NP) [3-5] that encapsulate corticoids (*i.e.* methylprednisolone or dexamethasone) using self-assembled amphiphilic polymeric drugs as nanovehicles with associated bioactivity, including antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. This presentation will show the synthesis, characterization, *in vitro* and *in vivo* evaluation of these NP that encapsulate and controlled release corticoid for the treatment of CDDP-induced hearing loss. The influence of the composition of the polymers on the hydrodynamic properties of the NP will be discussed. The incorporation of pH sensitive moieties to respond to the slightly acidic microenvironment of the inflamed tissue to induce the release of the corticoid will also be mentioned.

As conclusions of this research line, it is worthy to mention that the use of NP based treatments offer a more efficient solution against CDDP-induced ototoxicity than systemic or local administration of naked drugs. NP improved the capability of the therapeutics to reach the inner ear by crossing the biological barriers, which protect it. Local administration of these NP bearing oto-protective drugs provides an efficient treatment to CDDP-induced hearing loss and avoids interaction with the chemotherapeutic effect of CDDP in undesired tissues.

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Chitosan based Nanoformulations for Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Applications

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INTRODUCTION

Chitosan has been recognised with superior properties as a building block of different type of nanostructured materials (e.g., nanoparticles, coated emulsions and liposomes, nanofibers, injectable gels, scaffolds) used in biomedical and pharmaceutical applications. Some of its key biological properties include, *inter alia*, its mucoadhesion¹, antimicrobial^{2,3}, and ability to deliver genes intracellularly⁴. The structural features of chitosan that underpin its utilisation in different type of applications, namely, gene, antimicrobial phytochemicals and therapeutic peptide delivery, are yet to be uncovered. This lecture will address our current progress and gaps of knowledge in this remit.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Chitosans samples were supplied by either Sascha Mahtani Chitosan PVT Ltd (Veraval, India; “parent” chitosan sample Code 113 Batch No. 17/12/04; DA = 1.5 %, Mw = 543,000 g.mol⁻¹) or HMC+ Hepe Medical Chitosan (Halle, Saale, Germany). A series of chitosans of varying molar mass and degree of acetylation were prepared chemically from sample 113 as described elsewhere⁵. Chitosan-microRNA nanocomplexes were prepared at different charge ratios (+/-) and [miRNA]=5 μM.⁶ Chitosan-coated systems, namely oil core nanocapsules and liposomes, were prepared as described elsewhere^{7,8}. All biological experiments were carried out in triplicate and technical replicates varied from three to eight.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our results on microRNA delivery to breast cancer cells (MCF-7) revealed that chitosan (Mw 30,000 g/mol and DA 30 %) outperformed other chitosans to deliver microRNA (Figure 1a)⁴. An optimal association affinity of CS and microRNA is consistent with these results. In regard to antibacterial activity against an *E. coli* Top 10 strain (Figure 1b)⁹, not only the net charge is determinant, but also the presence of deacetylated polymer stretches. In turn, chitosan-coated liposomes have been found to expand the wound healing window of Substance-P (Figure 1c)⁸, presumably due to its effect on cellular internalisation and retarded delivery.

CONCLUSION

Only a deep knowledge of the mechanistic aspects that underpin the interactions of different chitosans at the physical-biological interface will lead to a more rational design of effective biomaterials for drug and gene delivery with potential of translation to the bedside.

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3D printing: From “ink” to medical devices

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INTRODUCTION

Contrary to the vast majority of the 3D constructs printed to date, which are static in nature, our work aims at engineering dynamic architectures that change “on command” or over time. This contribution focuses on the development of a series of environmentally responsive 3D printable polymers and the generation of 3D printed constructs responsive to temperature, pH or a magnetic field.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

3D printable polyethylene oxide-polypropylene oxide-polyethylene oxide (PEO-PPO-PEO) triblocks and acrylic acid were co-printed and are responsible for the reverse thermo-responsive and pH sensitive behavior of the 3D printed structures.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The water absorption behaviour and dimensional changes exhibited by the different environmentally responsive 3D printed constructs, markedly responded to temperature and pH changes. Our findings revealed that the 3D printed structures absorbed more water when below the thermal transition and also when at a pH above acrylic acid's pK_a value. All the printed structures showed a fast and reversible swelling-deswelling response, as they fluctuated between pH 2.0 and pH 7.4 and between 6°C and 37°C. Additionally, by adding magnetic nanoparticles (MNP) to the “ink” being printed, shape memory displaying structures able to be remotely actuated by an alternate magnetic field were engineered. By controlling the MNP content, temperatures between 47°C and 75°C were achieved, allowing the shape memory response of different polymers.

CONCLUSION

The distinctive spatial resolution of 3D printing technologies was successfully harnessed to produce environmentally responsive biomedical structures, with unique properties.

Novel Targeted and Stimuli-Responsive Amphiphilic Nanobiomaterials

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INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology made sound contributions to the treatment of disease in general and cancer in particular due to the ability to target drug-loaded nanomaterials by the enhanced permeation and retention effect (passive targeting). Furthermore, the design of nanocarriers surface-modified with ligands recognized by receptors overexpressed in specific cell types (e.g., cancer cells) is an extensively investigated (though still unrealized in the clinical practice) strategy for active targeting and reduce off-target accumulation and toxicity; e.g., sugared nanocarriers improved the diagnosis and chemotherapy of solid tumors overexpressing glucose transporters (e.g., breast cancer). I will initially introduce the design, characterization and preclinical evaluation of self-assembled nano-drug delivery systems that capitalize on the overexpression of glucose transporters to target pediatric solid tumors by the intravenous route.¹ Then, I will present and discuss a novel simple pathway for the synthesis of a novel type of hybrid ceramic/polymer sono-responsive nanomaterial with very good size control for potential application in the sonodynamic therapy of cancer².

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Novel Collagen from Natural Origin for Organ Regeneration

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INTRODUCTION

Many attempts have been made and suggested to form new bone for skeletal fracture, replace and regenerate diseased, traumatic, or infected bone. Among them, a method of using scaffold in tissue engineering perspective has been widely applied. The basic concept to consider in designing a scaffold for tissue engineering (TE) is biocompatibility and biodegradability. The materials should not cause toxicity, chronic inflammation, and immunological reactions. The answer to this is in materials derived from nature. This is due to their similarity with the extracellular matrix (ECM) and biological macromolecules of a target tissue¹. Collagen is one of the most commonly used nature-derived material in bone tissue engineering and demineralized bone powder (DBP) is also a well-known biomaterial variously used in new bone formation². Herein, the effect of collagen derived from duck's feet and demineralized bone powder originated from *Gallus gallus var. domesticus* in bone and osteochondral tissue will be discussed. The properties of scaffolds were characterized in chemical and mechanical perspective. The *in vitro* and *in vivo* study was proceeded to confirm the effect of the scaffold in bioactivity, biocompatibility, and biodegradability. Lastly, the feasibility and therapeutic aspects of these materials will be proposed.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

DC and GD DBP were prepared according to our previously reported study³. The DC scaffolds were prepared by applying other biomaterials. GD DBP was incorporated into gellan gum (GG) scaffold to obtain the bone-like model. The properties such as morphology, chemical structure, and mechanical characters of the materials were tested by FTIR, SEM, XRD, TGA and compressive modulus study. In addition, GD DBP was characterized by histological study and bioactivity of GD DBP/GG scaffold was measured by incubating the scaffolds in a simulated body fluid (SBF) solution. In addition, *in vitro* study was analyzed by MTT, RT-PCR, live/dead staining, morphology study by SEM, and histological study by H&E, and Von kossa staining. *In vivo* study was proceeded by implanting scaffolds in a calvarial defect. The result of *in vivo* study was measured by micro-CT and histological staining.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The specific amount of biomaterials (5 μ M EGCG/DC/HAp sponges, 100 μ M Smn/DC/HAp, and 25 μ M Qtn/DC/HAp) incorporated in DC scaffold displayed higher cell proliferation, growth, and differentiation *in vitro*. This represents that the application of other biomaterials can enhance the property of DC by providing enhanced biological environment and attachment sites. Furthermore, *in vivo* shows higher regenerated sites compared to pristine DC. These results suggest that composite of DC and beneficial components can lead to the ideal scaffold for bone tissue engineering.

GD DBP showed rich collagen type-1 and large amount of melanin. Composite of GD DBP and GG showed enhanced mechanical properties. Bioactivity of GD DBP/GG scaffolds displayed a high amount of crystal shape apatite formation on the surface of the scaffolds. The cell viability and mRNA expression was highest in 1% GD DBP/2% GG. The cell attachment was enhanced as GD DBP was incorporated. *In vivo* study displayed larger regenerated site when the defect tissue was implanted with GD DBP/GG scaffold. These results are due to the advantageous effect of rich melanin and collagen in GD DBP.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, DC scaffold and GD DBP which are originated from nature are studied to be beneficial in bone tissue engineering. DC and GD DBP are not only biocompatible and biodegradable but also are sufficient in sources and economical. Therefore, DC and GD DBP are regarded as a prospective candidate to apply in bone tissue engineering.

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Biodegradable composites for musculoskeletal regeneration bearing osteoinductive and antibacterial cations

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INTRODUCTION

Composite biomaterials play a key role in the development of advanced medical devices intended to be used for treatment of diseases, replacement, modification or support of the anatomy or of a physiological process. Truly, the recent discover of new functional carriers of antibacterial and osteoinductive metallic cations such as zinc and strontium, together with the use of biodegradable based biomimetic macromolecules and current advanced manufacturing techniques have made possible to expand the biomaterials science beyond the restorative and replacement horizons towards a new era where the regeneration of tissues, organs and biological functions are driven by polymer therapeutics, bioactive coatings and biomimetic functional macromolecules with tailored micro and nanostructures^{1,2}.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Strontium and zinc coordinated with folic acid (SrFO and ZnFO respectively) and/or natural macromolecules such as alginate, and hyaluronic acid have been incorporated into interpenetrated injectable hydrogel formulations and cryopolymerized 3D cell-scaffolds in which a population of osteoblast, chondrocytes and mesenchymal stem cells are able to drive the regeneration of different musculoskeletal tissues such as bone and cartilage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In vitro evaluation of strontium and zinc bearing constructs showed their significant effect in tissue formation and cell activity enhancing the capacity of cells to colonize the 3D scaffolds and upregulating bone and cartilage markers such as RUNX2, collagen I (COL1A1), bone sialoprotein (BSP), and ALP protein activity. In addition, ex vivo cultured organs and critical sized calvarian defects in rat models demonstrated the significant effect of scaffolds increasing the amount of the newly formed bone and enhancing the maturation and remodelling of the newly formed.

CONCLUSION

SrFO/ZnFO derivatives combine the benefits of nonprotein-based morphogens with antibacterial activity. Composite scaffolds containing Sr and Zn are biocompatible and provide an excellent system in the regeneration of bone and osteochondral tissues.

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Figure 1. Example of scaffold containing folic acid derivatives and its microstructure and osteoinductive activity.

Oral Presentations

Mixed Ad Layers of Poly(Lysine)-Based Copolymers to Dynamically Control Cell Adhesion/Migration

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INTRODUCTION

Current challenges in tissue engineering and cell biology often require control over when and where cells can attach, migrate, or proliferate. In addition, it's highly desirable to allow a dynamic control of the cell-substrate interactions; to this aim, surface properties of the substrate should be switchable by localized non-toxic stimuli. In this context, stimuli responsive polymer brushes are exiting tools although highly demanding surface chemistry is often required especially if mixed ad layers containing two or more polymer chains are requested. This constraint potentially hinders their adoption by non-specialists.¹ We explore here a straightforward method to functionalize anionic surfaces with controlled densities of diverse polymer grafts and applied it to modulate specific and non-specific adhesion/deadhesion patterns of mammalian cells via stimuli-triggered properties. It relies on tight spontaneous adsorption of comb-like polycationic derivatives of poly(Lysine) (PLL) that allow the formation of stable adlayers by simple immersion of anionic surfaces (glass, metal oxides...) in aqueous solutions of these polymers.²

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The adsorption of PLL based copolymers on surfaces was characterized by QCMD experiments. Accessibility of the ligand was checked by beads capture experiments followed by QCMD and fluorescence measurements. Finally, cell culture experiments were performed in standart conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three families of PLL based copolymers have been synthesised by different chemical pathways (RAFT polymerization, click chemistry)³. We show that adjustment of surface composition and interactions is obtained by coadsorption of different poly(lysine) derivatives. Accessibility of the ligand can be tuned via in situ click chemistry, red-ox cleavage and/or temperature sweep. Dynamic guidance of living cells is achieved by fine-tuning and spatiotemporal modulation on artificial polymer layers enabling reversible peptide display. As an example, the reversible polarization of HeLa cells along orthogonal stripes mimics guidance along natural matrices.

Fig.1: Examples of mixed brush based on PLL-PEG and thermo-responsive PLL-NIPAM

CONCLUSION

PLL based copolymers are useful tools to tune peptide densities and achieve control display of peptides on cell culture substrates. The straightforward, benchtop procedure for surface coating can be implemented on most common substrates (glass, PDMS, polystyrene) including nonplanar ones (e.g., colloid particles⁴), which offers to biologists a broad space of parameters to explore, including the possibility to co-deposit polymer strands of different chemical natures in the same layer. Possible applications include on-demand guidance of cell growth and migration, stimulation of a subpopulation of cells in the culture (e.g., controlled coculture), and studies of the rate of cell attachment or migration in response to local activation (e.g., to trigger and study stem cell differentiation, cancer cell migration, etc.).

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The ElastinGrafts: biohybrid compliant grafts as off-the-shelf small caliber vascular substitutes

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INTRODUCTION

Coronary artery disease accounts for 20% of all deaths¹, but by-pass grafting is restricted by the limited availability of autologous vessels, and the inadequate performance of prosthetic vascular grafts. In this contribution, we aim at developing biohybrid vascular implants that combine the hemocompatibility and remodeling ability of native vessels with the off-the-shelf availability, normally provided by synthetic grafts.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The vascular grafts (ElastinGrafts) were fabricated by combining elastin-like recombinamers (ELR)², ³ with technical textile components (warp knitted polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) and polycaprolactone (PCL) meshes). ELRs were cross-linked by click-chemistry. The fabrication materials were processed by injection-molding, salt-leaching/gas foaming and electrospinning. The graft microstructure was investigated by SEM. The hemocompatibility of the grafts was assessed by platelet adhesion. The mechanical characterization included burst strength, suture retention and compliance tests. Cellular studies were carried out with smooth muscle cells and endothelial progenitor cells.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The resulting vascular grafts showed minimal platelet adhesion, in contrast to the GORE-TEX grafts used as control. Besides the hemocompatibility, they also featured adequate suture retention and burst strength for implantation. Different from the clinically available prosthesis, the ElastinGrafts were able to match the compliance of the native vessels in the low, normal and higher pressure ranges. Cellular studies showed cell infiltration, ECM production, and endothelialization, which make these grafts of high interest for in situ tissue engineering.

CONCLUSION

Overall, our biohybrid fabrication strategy has resulted in promising off-the-shelf hemocompatible vascular grafts that address the known limitations of current vessel conduits and offer a great potential as small caliber substitutes for endogenous tissue regeneration.

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Polymers for Cartilage Tissue Supplementation and Lubrication

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Osteoarthritis (OA) is characterized by the breakdown of hyaline cartilage and synovial fluid (SF) in articular joints. This debilitating disease affects millions of people worldwide. Pathophysiologic changes associated with OA result in a decrease in the equilibrium compressive modulus and lubricity. Today, no pharmacologic treatments have been proven to ameliorate the progressive destruction of articular cartilage associated with OA. In this lecture, I will describe two polymeric biomaterial-based approaches for the treatment of OA. In the first approach, a tissue-supplementing technique is described in which a polymer is polymerized in situ throughout cartilage tissue to form an interpenetrating network. The treatment restores the inferior compressive properties of osteoarthritic cartilage to that of healthy cartilage, preferentially localizing to weaker regions of tissue. The treatment technique also preserves cartilage under harsh articulation conditions. In the second approach, novel hydrophilic polymers lubricate healthy and worn cartilage, provide cushioning, and reside in the joint after intraarticular injection for months. For both approaches, I will discuss the synthesis and characterization of the biomaterials, their performance in ex vivo and in vivo models, and the design requirements.

Recent Publications: *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, **2016**, 55, 4226-4230; *Osteoarthritis and Cartilage*, **2017**, 25, 1143-1149; *Osteoarthritis and Cartilage*, **2018**, 26, 414-421; *Biomaterials*, **2018**, 181, 210-226; *Biomaterials*, **2018**, 182, 13-20.

Controlled anchoring of iron-oxide nanoparticles on polymeric nanofibers: a simple approach towards hybrid and multifunctional scaffolds

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INTRODUCTION

Composites combining superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) and polymers are largely present in modern (bio)materials.^{1,2} However, while SPIONs embedded in polymer matrices are classically reported, this approach strongly impacts their mechanical and degradation properties. Therefore, the controlled anchoring of SPIONs on polymer surfaces is still a major challenge. Herein, we propose an efficient strategy for the direct and uniform anchoring of SPIONs on the surface of functionalized-poly(lactide) (PLA) nanofibers via a simple free ligand exchange procedure to design PLA@SPIONs core@shell nanocomposites to be used as multifunctional scaffolds.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Electrospun PLA nanofibers are chemically modified to generate alkyne surface groups.³ Bifunctional thiol-phosphonic ligand is covalently bound to the surface by thiol-yne photoaddition. Finally, SPIONs are anchored on the PLA fibers via a free ligand exchange procedure. PLA@SPIONs hybrid biomaterials are characterized by electron microscopy (SEM and TEM) and EDXS analysis, to probe the morphology and detect elements present at the organic/inorganic interface, respectively. Imaging properties, magnetic properties and cytocompatibility are assessed in vitro and in vivo in rats.⁴

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A monolayer of SPIONs with a complete and homogeneous coverage is observed on the surface of PLA nanofibers (Fig.A). Magnetization experiments prove that the magnetic properties of the SPIONs are well-preserved after their grafting on the PLA fibers and that no aggregation occurred. The absence of any significant cytotoxicity, combined to a high sensitivity of detection using standard T2-weighted spin echo sequence and a pre-clinical MR scanner in rat (Fig.B) confirm that the PLA@SPIONs hybrid biomaterials are highly attractive candidates for the development of magnetic scaffolds usable in tissue engineering applications.

CONCLUSION

We demonstrate here for the first time an efficient surface grafting method for the preparation of PLA@SPIONs hybrid biomaterials that be readily adapted to other polymers and inorganic nanoparticles for the development of enhanced and multifunctional biomaterials

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Constructing a Three Dimensional in Vitro Embryo Implantation Model Using Alginate Macroporous Scaffold

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INTRODUCTION

Implantation failure remains an unsolved obstacle in reproductive medicine and is a major cause of infertility in otherwise healthy women. Indeed, only about 20% of embryos transferred to the uterus, following in vitro fertilization (IVF), lead to the birth of a healthy infant. Estrogen receptor- α (ER- α) and E-cadherin in this process were previously suggested to be involved in the process¹. Due to obvious ethical restrictions there is an unmet need to establish an in vitro model that mimics the events in the uterine wall during the implantation process¹. Our main goal was to establish a long-term endometrial tissue-like structure, hormone-responsive that would serve as a model for human implantation process. Alginate macro-porous scaffold, previously proved to have several advantages for tissue engineering applications², was hypothesized to support long term endometrial cell viability, endometrium tissue-like formation and functionality.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Alginate scaffolds were prepared by a freeze-dry technique. Endometrial cell lines, RL95-2 or HEC-1A, expressing high and low levels of ER- α , displaying receptive and non-receptive endometrial properties, respectively, were used. Cells were seeded into alginate scaffolds and cultured in sequential hormonal treatment, one week priming of estrogen, following by two weeks of progesterone containing medium. E-cadherin mRNA expression levels were evaluated by qPCR. E-cadherin protein expression was evaluated by specific immuno-staining of cell constructs' thin cryo-sections, or by Western blot analysis. JAR spheroids (blastocyst model) were seeded on top of 3 week-old cell constructs, and incubated for 24 h. Attachment of JAR spheroids to RL95-2 culture was evaluated by H&E staining. ER α -transfected HEC cells were cultured and analysed similarly. Statistical analysis was performed with GraphPad Prism. E-cadherin mRNA and protein comparison was performed by 2-way repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA). Benferoni's post-hoc test was carried out to determine differences. Quantification of spheroid attachment to epithelial monolayer culture, and ER- α mRNA expression levels in transfected and WT HEC-1A, were compared by two-tailed unpaired t-test. $P < 0.05$ was considered for statistical significance

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cultivation under 3D conditions within macro-porous alginate scaffolds enabled long-term viability of the cells for at least 4 weeks. E-cadherin mRNA expression levels were shown to be significantly higher in 3-weeks old RL95-2 cell constructs, cultured in sequential hormonal treatment, compared to HEC-1A cells. E-cadherin immuno-staining revealed pronounced protein expression in RL95-2 cell constructs, compared to HEC-1A. These finding imply to the possible regulation of E-cadherin by ER- α . JAR spheroid attachment to 3-weeks old RL95-2 culture was confirmed by H&E staining, pointing out to the functionality of the implantation model (Fig. 1, left). No such spheroid attachment was evident in HEC-1A (Fig.1, middle). Moreover, transfection of HEC-1A cells with ER- α indicated restored capability of JAR spheroid adhesion (Fig. 1, right).

Fig. 1 JAR spheroid attachment to epithelial endometrial 3D culture models in alginate scaffolds. (Bar: 100 μ m).

CONCLUSION

Our 3D culture models within macro-porous alginate scaffolds enabled long-term culture of viable endometrial cells. These cultures may serve as a research model for studying the regulatory mechanism governing implantation process and evaluation of potential novel therapeutic strategy for regulating implantation defects.

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**Advanced antimicrobial recombinant polymers:
Insights onto the self-assembly - bactericidal properties relationship**

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INTRODUCTION

Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are cationic peptides with broad-spectrum and immunomodulatory properties¹, which represent one of the most promising alternative for the increasingly common bacterial antibiotic resistance². In this study, anti-bacterial nanovehicles based on AMPs and Elastin-like block co-Recombinamers (ELbcRs) have been developed based on a modular design. Two AMPs (GL13K³ and 1018¹) were cloned on the hydrophilic corona of diblock ELbcR (SI) that self-assemble into monodisperse micelles. We aim to develop nanocarriers for AMP that enhance their antimicrobial properties increasing the local concentration and improving the delivery.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

All the chimeric biopolymers (AMP-ELbcRs) were designed and constructed by recombinant DNA technology, produced by *Escherichia coli* fermentation and purified by ITC⁴. Circular dichroism, DLS and TEM were carried out to characterize the nanostructuration of the chimeric biopolymers. MICs and Killing Assays against Gram negative *P. aeruginosa* PAO1, *E. coli* (25922) and Gram positive *S. aureus* (25923), *S. epidermidis* (12228, 35984) and *S. gordonii* DL-1 were performed to evaluate the antimicrobial profile of the new biopolymers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TEM, DLS and CD studies revealed that the AMP-ELbcRs self-assembled into nanofibers (Fig. 1 A, B) or spherical nanoparticles (Fig. 1 C, D). Depending on the incubation conditions, self-assembly was triggered by the AMP or by the ELbcR. Antibacterial assays suggested that the nanostructuration of the chimeric ELRs could be crucial to promote the antimicrobial activity. At physiological temperature, the AMP-ELbcR self-assembled into a micellar conformation, exposing the antimicrobial domains on the corona surface, thus enhancing their antimicrobial potential.

Fig. 1. Nanostructures formed by the chimeric ELbcRs at 4 °C and 37 °C. Scale bar = 50 nm.

CONCLUSION

We developed an innovative and scalable method for the bioproduction of antimicrobial nanostructures. The combination of the smart behaviour of ELbcRs and the AMPs provide a promising nanocarrier for AMP delivery to treat resistant infections and a platform to study the molecular mechanism that control the bactericidal properties of the AMP linked to biopolymers.

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Localized siRNA delivery by collagen/lipid nanoparticle hybrid scaffolds

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INTRODUCTION

Achieving prolonged and localized delivery of small interfering RNA (siRNA) at a specific site is highly desirable since SiRNA therapy appears as a very promising strategy for many medical applications.¹ Collagen has attracted attention as a biomaterial for local sustained drug delivery in wounds, due to its biocompatibility, safety, and hemostatic properties.² We here investigated the ability of collagen scaffolds obtained by a lyophilization method to act as localized siRNA delivery systems when loaded directly with SiRNA, or loaded with SiRNA/lipid nanoparticles (LNP) acting as nucleic acid carriers.³

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Dye-loaded LNP with shell comprising cationic lipids (cLNP) or chitosan lipids (CSLNP) for SiRNA complexation were formulated by sonication.³ Free SiRNA, cLNP/SiRNA or CSLNP/SiRNA were loaded in a collagen gel (1% in acetic acid buffer) and after stirring, the homogeneous slurry was lyophilized in order to obtain porous cryostructures. *In vitro* release of fluorescently labelled SiRNA when incubating collagen scaffolds in 1X PBS buffer was measured by fluorescence titration. The uptake of SiRNA and LNP by NIH3T3 cells when seeded onto scaffolds was evaluated by flow cytometry. Down regulation in NIH3T3 cells of ERK1 protein, involved in the wound healing process, was then measured by fluorescent protein titration using FITC-labelled anti-ERK1 antibody.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

cLNP and CSLNP dispersions presented respectively 50 and 105 nm diameter particles, low dispersity index (<0.2), and positive zeta potential (15.5 and 53.8 mV resp.) for efficient SiRNA complexation.³ After their mixing with collagen gels and scaffolds synthesis by freeze-drying, the materials presented large interconnected macropores of about 100 μm , a favourable structure for efficient drainage of wound exudate.⁴ Material structure and swelling ratio were not affected by the presence of LNP.

Collagen loaded with cLNP nanoparticles achieved the most prolonged SiRNA release (60% in 4 days) and prolonged *in vitro* downregulation of ERK-1 protein (at least 7 days).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, lipid nanoparticle templates were useful to prolong and promote siRNA delivery from collagen scaffolds.

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Coordination polymers for biomedical applications

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INTRODUCTION

The synthesis of coordination polymers (CPs) for biomedical applications is increasing enormously since their tailorable compositions and structures, excellent porosity, and easier surface modification make them ideal as drug carriers. Furthermore, in the case of bio-CPs, the therapeutic molecule is a constitutive part of the CP framework itself, in which the drug is released through the degradation of the CP. In this work we have explored the use of supercritical carbon dioxide (scCO₂) as a new green synthetic approach for the preparation of Zinc(II) based CPs (called ZIF-8) suitable for drug delivery¹, and Bio-CPs where the bio-active compounds were curcumine (ccm)² and ferulic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Materials. All reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich but compressed CO₂ (99.95 v%) that was supplied by Carbueros Metálicos S.A. **Supercritical Synthesis:** Sample preparation under scCO₂ was carried out in a high pressure equipment using 100 mL stainless steel reactor. Typically, the autoclave was charged with ~100 mg of the metal precursor and the corresponding stoichiometric amount of linker. The reagents were introduced in a 10 mL Pyrex vial capped with filter paper and placed within the reactor under stirring (1-90 h). For ccmCP synthesis, 2% ml of EtOH as co-solvent was also added. The system was pressurized up to 20 MPa, heated at a temperature of either 313 or 333 K and operating in batch mode. Finally, the reactor was slowly depressurized and samples were collected as powders.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The CP namely ZIF-8 was obtained by reacting its precursors Zn(acac)₂ and Hmim in pure scCO₂. The final product was characterised by XRD elemental analysis and BET confirming that indeed the target material was obtained pure, with high surface area (1620 m²g⁻¹). The synthesis of the ccmCP was prepared from a mixture of Zn(acac)₂ and ccm in scCO₂. For this type of bio-CP **Fig (a)**, no pores were required, since the release of the drug molecule is achieved only through the degradation of the solid **Fig (b)**.

Drug dissolution profiles at neutral pH of raw curcumin (orange) and synthesized (black) curcumin bioMOF.

CONCLUSION

A straightforward synthesis of CPs for biomedical applications in scCO₂ was carried out in scCO₂. This process methodology would enable the scaling-up and thus promoting their industrial use.

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Self-assembling ELR nanoparticles as smart drug delivery systems

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INTRODUCTION

One of the limitations of modern medicine is the lack of efficient drug carriers so as to achieve two benefits: an increase in drug efficacy and a reduction in possible adverse side effects. One of the most recent therapeutic approaches is based on smart biomaterials¹. Among novel biomaterials, Elastin-Like Recombinamers are useful biomaterials for most applications in biomedicine, given their cell-friendly behaviour, tunable mechanical properties, thermal sensitivity, and ability to self-assemble². In particular, nanoparticles are promising approaches to improve treatment efficacy in targeted cells⁴ as they are able to overcome the limitations of chemotherapy and improve the action of therapeutic agents³. The protein kinase B, also known as Akt, plays a key role in multiple cellular processes such as cell proliferation, cell migration or apoptosis⁴. Moreover, Akt is overexpressed in many types of cancers, including breast, colorectal and pancreatic cancer. Targeting Akt is therefore a highly attractive anti-cancer strategy and different Akt inhibitors are now in clinical development for the treatment of cancer.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Taking advantage of the recombinant DNA technology, the constructs were formed by an amphiphilic backbone and certain bioactive sequences, including an Akt inhibitor. The final ELRs were produced by *E. coli* fermentation and fully characterized, after purification process, by SDS-PAGE, NMR, MALDI-TOF/MS and DSC. Self-assembled nanoparticles were analyzed by Dynamic Light Scattering and Transmission Electronic Microscopy. The therapeutic activity, specific inhibition of phosphorylation and consequent activation of Akt was evaluated by western blot analysis. Moreover, the effectiveness of ELR nanoparticles was evaluated *in vitro* in three breast and colorectal cancer cell lines and three human primary cell lines, such as fibroblasts, mesenchymal and endothelial cells by LIVE/DEAD assays. Furthermore, the internalization pathway and cellular activation of nanoparticles were studied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ELR polymers were able to self-assemble into homogeneous nanoparticles with a mean diameter of 72nm when temperature was increased above 16°C. The ELR-based nanoparticles treatment proved to be specific for cancerous cells. Indeed, nanoparticles showed increased effect on breast and colorectal cancer cells, whereas non-cancerous cells were not affected. Cell viability was significantly reduced after incubation with smart nanoparticles in a time- and concentration-dependent fashion. Results also evidenced the primary influence of clathrin-mediated endocytosis for the internalization and endosomal/lysosomal acidification for the activation of nanoparticles. Furthermore, nanoparticles properly inhibited phosphorylation of Akt protein and triggered apoptosis-mediated cell death.

CONCLUSION

Hence, we conclude that the design of a complex ELR molecule able to drive cell internalization, escape from lysosomes and inhibition of Akt kinase activation, leads to achieve successful drug delivery in targeted cells and could be a promising approach as nanocarriers with bioactive peptides in order to modulate multiple cellular processes involved in different diseases.

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Aryl-sulfonated chitosan: synthesis, characterization, anticoagulant properties and electrospinning

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INTRODUCTION

Sulfonated or sulfated chitosans present a structure close to natural glucosaminoglycans (GAGs) and are known for their anticoagulant properties [1] resulting in high potential for developing biomaterials with anti-thrombogenic properties. We synthesized sulfonated chitosan derivatives through a reductive amination strategy using arylsulfonic aldehyde compounds [2]. After their structural and physicochemical characterizations, their anticoagulant properties were demonstrated and we finally shaped them into nanofibers by electrospinning.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Synthesis of CHT-S: CHT was dissolved in aqueous acetic acid 1% (v/v). Two sulphating reagents, 2-formylbenzenesulfonic acid, sodium salt dihydrate (BZ1S) or 4-formyl-1,3-benzenedisulfonic acid, disodium salt hydrate (BZ2S), in methanol were added to the CHT solution, followed addition of sodium cyanoborohydride as reductor. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed and freeze-dried. Monosulfonated (CHT1S) and disulfonated (CHT2S) derivatives with variable substitution degrees were obtained upon variation of the reactants molar ratio (R).

Electrospinning: CHT1S or CHT2S dissolved in NaOH (0.05M) were blended with Poly (ethylene oxide) (PEO) (weight ratio CHT-S/ PEO = 8/2). Solution and process parameters were varied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sulfonate groups introduction in raw CHT skeleton was confirmed by ¹H-NMR that revealed the presence of grafted aromatic substituent through peaks appearing above 7 ppm. The FTIR study showed new bands relative to sulfonic acid hydrates at 2400-2000 cm⁻¹ and 1230-1235 cm⁻¹, and to substituted benzene groups below 800cm⁻¹. Elemental analysis of both CHT1S and CHT2S revealed that degree of substitution (DS) were about 0.16 - 0.63 and 0.08 - 0.41, respectively. Contrarily to CHT, SCHT was soluble over a wide range of pH, highlighting its amphoteric character. Viability assay using fibroblasts NIH/3T3 evidenced the biocompatibility property of all SCHT synthesized. Besides, the anticoagulation assay revealed that the clotting time was significantly dependant on the DS and the concentration. The CHT2S, that possesses more sulfonate groups than CHT1S, showed a better anticoagulant activity, which increased with the increase of concentration. The optimal electrospinning conditions were determined for CHT2S and homogeneous nanofibers were obtained.

CONCLUSION

CHT-S derivatives with controlled DS were successfully synthesized and exhibited an anticoagulant activity depending on their DS. Defect-free nanofibres of CHT-S were obtained by electrospinning. In short term, the study will lead to application in the vascular field, by covering a stent with CHT-S nanofibers for thrombosis prevention.

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Peptide and non-Peptide modified Surfaces specific for the Adhesion and Growth of Valvular Interstitial Cells

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INTRODUCTION

The valvular interstitial cell (VC) is the predominant cell type of the heart valve whereas endothelial cells (ECs) form the blood-contacting luminal layer. Aiming at tissue engineering of valves, surfaces that spatially favor either the adhesion and growth of VCs or ECs would be very beneficial. Here we report on the bioconjugation of a peptide and the polysaccharide hyaluronic acid (HA), ligands specific for $\alpha 9\beta 1$ and CD44 respectively^{1,2}, both receptors highly expressed on VCs. Modifications were performed on a non-degradable as well as on a bioerodible polymer.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and polycaprolactone (PCL) were used as substrates and amino-functionalized as previously reported^{3,4}. HA was immobilized using hexamethylene diisocyanate (HMDI) as the crosslinker under non-aqueous conditions. Coupling of the peptide CPLAEIDGIELTY (VCsP) via a thiol and amine reactive heterobifunctional crosslinker was carried out in an aqueous buffer. Pristine and modified samples were subjected to cell culture with primary sheep VCs and human umbilical vein ECs for up to 1 week. Surfaces were additionally tested for platelet adhesion. Cells were fluorescently stained and micrographs were analyzed with ImageJ software. Data were expressed as percentage coverage of total area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Both untreated materials are poor substrates for cell adhesion and colonization (Figures 1 and 2). On PTFE modified with VCsP or HA confluence was reached after one week of VC culture. Compared to this, VC growth on untreated material was negligible. All three surfaces prevented EC colonization to a large extent suggesting that the modifications may be considered as specific. Platelet attachment was considerable for the pristine PTFE surface (ca. 14 % coverage), whereas both treatments were found to be thrombo-resistant, possibly due to the hydrophilic nature of the coating. For PCL, similar but less pronounced results were obtained: modified surfaces stimulated VC adhesion (confluent after 1 week), prevented colonization by ECs almost completely during 1 week culture and simultaneously reduced platelet adhesion considerably. Given that VCs show a much higher growth rate compared to ECs it maybe assumed that endothelialization is expected to be suppressed on modified surfaces. In addition, the non-thrombogenic properties created in this way might facilitate colonization and avoid the need for initial anticoagulation.

CONCLUSION

Covalent bioconjugation of appropriate ligands onto biomaterials affords surfaces which exhibit a pronounced preference for a specific cell type, here VCs. This approach might provide a novel route for the tissue engineering of heart valves.

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Design of gold (Au)/cyclic polymer hybrid materials for biomedical applications

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INTRODUCTION

Particular polymer topologies such as cyclic polymers, beyond linearity, have been shown to alter significantly the properties of diverse polymer preparations in both bulk and solutions, when compared to their linear counterparts.¹ Click chemistry and in particular, copper-catalyzed alkyne–azide cycloaddition (CuAAC) has allowed access to a variety of cyclic architectures.²

On the other hand, gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) continue to attract much attention across a broad range of fields mainly due to their optical properties,³ biocompatibility⁴ and catalytic activity.⁵ In this work, we explore the possibility of applying cyclic polyethylene glycol (PEG) on inorganic AuNPs, with particular attention to how this polymer topology might affect the colloidal stability of them in biological media. The exchange of surfactant (used in the synthesis of AuNPs) with thiol functional group of cyclic PEG will allow to form a strong covalent bond with the gold surface,⁶ decreasing the final toxic response. Moreover, PEG by providing neutral surface charge (~5mV), is expected to reduce “protein crown” formation due to non-specific interactions, thus preventing the assimilation of AuNPs by the cells and having a longer circulation time in living systems.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Thiolated cyclic polymers were obtained by performing CuAAC between a PEG bis(azide) of $M_n=2$ or 6 kg/mol and a previously synthesized thiolated di-alkyne molecule. MALDI-ToF MS, NMR spectroscopy and size exclusion chromatography (SEC) techniques were used in this work to verify the formation and purity of the cyclic polymers. Colloidal stability of AuNPs modified with cyclic PEG was monitored using UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy, accompanied by dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements and TEM. This stability was also compared to the linear analogues of PEGs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Purity and mono-dispersity of synthesized thiolated cyclic polymer were confirmed by MALDI-ToF MS, NMR and SEC techniques. UV-Vis-NIR spectra of initially stabilized AuNPs exhibits a maximum of localized surface plasmon band at 517 nm. Upon addition of cyclic PEG, the plasmon band shifted to 522 nm, suggesting the ligand exchange. The width of the plasmon band remained constant after washing confirming the colloidal stability of AuNPs (front figure).

CONCLUSION

Pure and monodisperse monocyclic structures of PEG were generated by CuAAC “click” reaction. They were used as stabilizers of AuNPs, allowing an improvement of the stability of AuNPs in physiological medium compared to linear analogues.

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3D Printing of Spatially Patterned Magnetically Responsive Hydrogels

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INTRODUCTION

Smart and responsive functional nanocomposites continue to be a huge focus of scientific effort worldwide due to their numerous applications, particularly in biomedicine, from cancer treatment to biomolecules/drug delivery¹. Their bulk responses can be engineered through precise physicochemical modifications across multiple length scales to the response of electric and/or magnetic fields, temperature, salts, pH, and light but also by their spatial patterning using 3D printing technologies². Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) and their clusters are used in the biomedical field in a wide range of applications from cancer treatment to MRI imaging³. The combination of MNPs and typically used 3D printable polymeric hydrogels can therefore lead to multifunctional and stimuli-sensitive nanocomposites delivery systems with spatial-, temporal- and dosage-controlled biomolecules/drug release for tissue engineering applications (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Scheme showing the heating of magnetic nanoparticles encapsulated in hydrogels.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

An open-source 3D printer was successfully built and modified to allow extrusion of Pluronic F127 hydrogels with parameters of moderate temperature and pressure that would support cell viability. Magnetic nanoparticles were synthesised, stabilised and incorporated homogeneously into a printable F127 Pluronic hydrogel with concentrations of up to 120 mM Fe and the alternating magnetic field hyperthermia was measured to yield increases in the temperature. Human embryonic kidney 293T cell line (HEK-293T) was cultured in sterile cell culture flasks and used to confirm biocompatibility and applicability of the produced hydrogels.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We successfully fabricated homogeneous MNPs-Pluronic F127 hybrid hydrogels. The oscillatory rheology measurements confirmed the viscoelastic properties with G' (storage modulus) values in the ~ 20 kPa range providing ideal materials for 3D printing defined architectures with high fidelity. We printed various structures with high resolution (~ 100 μm) and confirmed that incorporated magnetic nanoparticles retain sufficient properties to facilitate control over magnetic response leading to temperature gradients control for unique stimulus-responsive applications. The cultured HEK-293T cells on the hydrogels with/out MNPs showed good viability confirming biocompatibility of materials.

CONCLUSION

In summary we demonstrate; (i) reproducible and robust extrusion of hybrid hydrogels; (ii) spatial patterning of thermally active components and drug loading, and; (iii) in situ manipulation using applied magnetic fields with high resolution thermal mapping; (iv) biocompatibility of hybrid hydrogels using the HEK-293T cell line.

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Engineering Responsive and Biomimetic Hydrogels for Biomedical Therapeutic and Diagnostic Applications (BIOGEL)

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INTRODUCTION

The goal of this research project, with the participation of DWI, RU, UVa, AIT, CERTH, NovioSense, Pepsan, LTG, TPNBT, MPI, EPFL, SYNO, PENN and Osaka is to engineer novel biologically active and responsive hydrogels for integrative coatings, and diagnostic and regenerative matrices. More specifically, the project is focused on synthetic and biohybrid macromolecules to build clinically translatable hydrogels with specific, application directed bioactivities. In order to enable efficient biohybridization and minimal invasive application, emphasis is set on *in situ* gelation of precursors that do not affect the viability of cells and can interlink bioactive subunits to stimulate tissue regeneration, and serve as a functional component in biomedical devices. Translational aspects focus on coatings of medical devices, diagnostic hydrogels, cartilage and bone repair, tissue engineering for cardio-vascular implants, and nerve regeneration.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Silk Elastin co-Recombinamers (SELRs) were synthesized, and optimized via a pre-annealing treatment based on the evolution of silk motifs into β -sheet structures in order to exhibit the required mechanical properties of hydrogels for cartilage repair.

Additionally, *in situ* forming hydrogels based on methacrylated hyaluronic acid (MeHA) and MeHA biofunctionalized with a chondroitin sulfate (CS) binding peptide, were synthesized using an MMP7-degradable peptide as crosslinker. The ability of SELRs and (CS)MeHA hydrogels incorporating chondrocytes to induce repair of cartilage lesions was tested in an *ex vivo* cartilage model (see Figure). Polyisocyanides (PIC) gels were also synthesized as cell culture platforms with decoupled mechanical inputs and biological cues. For this purpose, different types of cells were encapsulated in PIC gels with varying adhesive peptide (GRGDS) density, polymer length, and concentration. In addition, chitosan hydrogel coatings with antifouling properties were synthesized by the grafting of polymer brushes in order to be used as implant coatings impeding inflammation after implantation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The new pre-annealed SELRs were found to accelerate the β -sheet formation without losing the injectability of the material. An appropriate gelation onset, corresponding to the time required for the *in vivo* injection, could be achieved with the (CS)MeHA hydrogels as well as rheological properties favoring the differentiation of hMSCs to chondrocytes. After 4 weeks of culturing in an *ex vivo* model, the biochemical analysis of both hydrogels revealed the production of glycosaminoglycans and collagen. Regarding CS(MeHA) hydrogels, the histological analysis indicated the formation of extracellular matrix (ECM), whereas for the SELRs hydrogels the immunohistochemistry showed the absence of fibrocartilage and the presence of hyaline cartilage. Both cancer and smooth muscle cells grew into multicellular spheroids in PIC gels with proliferation rates that depended on the adhesive GRGDS density, regardless of the polymer length, suggesting that for these cells, the biological input prevails over the mechanical cues. The functionalization of chitosan with polymer brushes resulted in hydrophilic coatings of 180 nm which significantly reduced the protein fouling and eliminated platelet activation and leukocyte adhesion.

CONCLUSION

Innovative hydrogel chemistries and systems for biomedical applications were developed during the BIOGEL project such as, novel hydrogels with controlled mechanical properties that effectively promote tissue formation, and antifouling coatings that improve hemocompatibility and pave the way for enhanced device integration in tissue.

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3D printing of PEG-based hydrogels with dynamic metal coordination crosslinking

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INTRODUCTION

3D printing allows precise material deposition in 3 dimensions and has become an attractive tool for constructing hierarchical structures resembling native tissues.¹ Hydrogel-based, cell-friendly systems are broadly investigated for extrusion printing²; nevertheless, inks for high resolution printing are still needed. Recently, inks based on non-covalent dynamic crosslinking have gained interest due to their self-healing and shear thinning properties, which facilitate printing.³ Inspired by dynamic networks used by sea mussels⁴, we have explored printability of catechol end-functionalized PEG-based system with metal-coordination crosslinking (PEG-Dop/M³⁺)(Fig.1.).

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Proposed PEG-Dop/M³⁺ formulations were crosslinked with Al³⁺, Fe³⁺ or V³⁺ ions at close-to-physiological conditions. The printability range and shape fidelity as function of ink composition (metal ion type and concentration, pH, PEG molecular weight) and printing parameters (extrusion pressure and printing speed) were investigated. The rheological properties of the inks (i.e. relaxation time, recovery rate and viscosity) were measured and correlated with the thermodynamic and kinetic constants of the metal-coordination crosslinking, and, further, with the shape fidelity of the printed structures. The viability of the cells seeded in contact with the material was tested.

Fig.1. Schematic representation of PEG-Dop/M³⁺ ink extrusion, with indicated rearrangement of the network under shear force

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.2. Influence of head moving speed on printing of different inks at pressure of 250 kPa; scale bars: 500 μ m (left). Storage (closed symbols) and loss (open symbols) modulus of inks as a function of frequency at 1% strain (right).

Designed formulations were successfully used for extrusion printing with optional secondary crosslinking. They revealed printability and shape fidelity dependent on the used metal ions (Fig.2 and Fig.3.). Rheological properties of the inks, i.e. relaxation time, recovery time after strain-induced network breaking, and viscosity, were visibly related to the strands shape fidelity, optimal printing parameters (Fig.2.) and ink printability range. Well-defined strands were obtained with PEG-Dop/Fe³⁺ and PEG-Dop/Al³⁺ networks, with relaxation time < 1 s. PEG-Dop/V³⁺, with significantly longer relaxation time (~ 40 s), gave irregular structures. The relaxation time

of a metal-ligand crosslinked network is expected to be influenced by the coordination degree of the metal-ligand complex, the ligand exchange kinetics and the thermodynamic stability constant⁴, which were different for each of proposed formulations. PEG-Dop/Fe³⁺ ink gave the best outcome in terms of shape fidelity and prints resolution in 2D (Fig.2). Interestingly, well-printed 3D scaffolds were also obtained with PEG-Dop/V³⁺, indicating that at larger scales the irregular shape of the filaments might not be decisive parameter for successful printing.

Moreover, the proposed system showed great adhesive properties in both, dry and wet conditions, and revealed biocompatibility, indicating high potential for biomedical applications.

Since development of new, functional bioinks is a challenging task, we believe that knowledge about relation between rheological parameters and material performance, highlighted in our study, is of high significance.

CONCLUSION

Proposed PEG-Dop/M³⁺ inks are characterized by remarkable design flexibility allowing to tune material properties according to the requirements of particular printing process and application. Additionally, rheological studies of the system allowed to define relaxation time and recovery time after strain-induced breaking of the network as main parameters indicating printability of ink with reversible bonds.

Fig.3. 3-layers construct printed with PEG-Dop/M³⁺ crosslinked with (from left to right): Al³⁺, Fe³⁺, V³⁺ ions. Scale bars: 5 mm.

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Antibacterial hydrogels based on bacterial cellulose and PHACOS

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INTRODUCTION

Bacterial cellulose (BC) is an excellent wound dressing device due to its favourable characteristics, such as its biocompatibility, non-toxicity, mechanical stability and high moisture content. However, it has no antimicrobial activity, which is a critical function of the skin-barrier that is compromised during wound healing¹. In this work, antimicrobial BC membranes were obtained by chemical blending with a naturally functionalized bacterial polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHACOS) with demonstrated antibacterial properties². This second generation biopolymer, shows antibacterial activity specifically against *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates. This ability has been ascribed to the functionalized side chains containing thioester groups.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

BC was blended with poly-3-hydroxyoctanoate-co-3-hydroxyhexanoate (PHA) or PHACOS, using the ionic liquid (IL) BMIMCl as solvent³. Blends with compositions of 80/20 and 50/50 BC/PHA or BC/PHACOS were prepared. The structure and morphology of these new hydrogels were studied by infrared spectroscopy (IR), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and rheological tests. The antimicrobial activity was tested against *S. aureus* by colony forming unit reduction after exposure to the blend for 24 h.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Homogeneous mixtures of BC and PHA or PHACOS were obtained using BMIMCl as solvent. This IL disturbs hydrogen bonding formation and dissolves both biopolymers at 90°C. The solutions were poured in Teflon petri dishes and placed in deionized water. The IL was displaced by the water and transparent and consistent hydrogels were formed. Hydroxyl groups of BC and carbonyl groups of PHA form new hydrogen bonds as demonstrated by the FTIR experiments. Moreover, the intensity of the vibrational bands at 2923 (C-H) and 1743 (C=O) cm⁻¹ increases with the proportion of polyhydroxyalkanoate.

In the analysis of the TGA, it can be concluded that not only the blends show T_d (decomposition temperatures) values in between the individual components, but also the T_d increases with the cellulose content in the mixture. The thermal degradation of the hydrogels occurs in two steps: firstly, the degradation of the polyhydroxyalkanoate is observed, and secondly, the cellulose is degraded.

The rheological analysis shows a clear dependency with frequency at high angular frequency values, which means that the blends formed by PHACOS50 are the least stable, being the PHACOS20 mixtures the most stable.

Regarding to the SEM images, the morphology of the blends shows a phase separated structure as the proportion of the polyhydroxyalkanoate increases.

The antimicrobial activity of the regenerated BC, BC/PHA and BC/PHACOS hydrogels was tested and it showed a 1-log reduction in bacterial viability for *S. aureus* bacterial strains after 24 h only for the hydrogels that contains PHACOS.

CONCLUSION

In this study, new biodegradable blends based on BC and PHACOS with antimicrobial activity were obtained. The study of the characteristics of the new hydrogels makes them good candidates for wound healing.

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Design of Biodegradable Anti-Adhesive Membranes in Orthopaedic Surgery

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INTRODUCTION

Post-surgical tissue adhesions are late complications in several surgical specialities including upper limb tendon and nerve orthopaedic surgery. A promising approach to prevent adhesions is the implantation of a polymeric physical barrier at the injured site^{1,2}. This work aims at synthesizing a polyether urethane (PEU)³ to further synthesize a multi-degradable poly(lactic acid)-*b*-PEU-*b*-poly(lactic acid) triblock copolymer .

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

All reagents were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and were used as received. Polyethylene glycol (PEG) was dried by azeotropic evaporation with toluene. Polyether urethane (PEU) was synthesized by a polycondensation process with 1,6-hexamethylene diisocyanate (HMDI). Poly-(lactic acid)-*b*-polyether urethane-*b*-poly (lactic acid) (PLA-PEU-PLA) triblock copolymer was synthesized by a ring opening polymerization pathway initiated by PEU. Gel permeation chromatography (GPC), Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR), ¹H-NMR analyses, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetry (TGA) analyses were performed for all products.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Polycondensation of PEG low molecular weight with HMDI allowed to synthesize PEU.

Figure1. Synthesis of biodegradable membrane for orthopaedic surgery application

Starting from a PEG 2000 Da, GPC analysis of the related PEU showed a molecular weight of 18000 Da and a polymerization degree around 9. FT-IR analysis confirmed the formation of the urethane groups. PLA-PEU-PLA triblock copolymer was synthesized by a ring opening polymerization of D,L-lactide at 130 °C. ¹H-NMR and GPC analyses allowed to determine the copolymer composition. Different batches of PLA-PEU-PLA have been realized to prepare these membranes.

CONCLUSION

A polyether urethane (PEU) has been successfully synthesized by a one-step polycondensation route. Based on this PEU, PLA-PEU-PLA membranes have been prepared; their mechanical and degradation properties as well as their cytocompatibility are currently under investigation.

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Filling the kinetic gap: a new thiol-X crosslinking chemistry for 3D cell culture hydrogels

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INTRODUCTION

Within the biomaterials field, a prominent application of hydrogels is 3D cell culture. They are used as extracellular matrix mimics for the basic study of cell function, high-throughput drug screening and therapeutic delivery. Several covalent coupling chemistries have been described for simultaneous hydrogel crosslinking, biofunctionalization and cell encapsulation. Non light dependent, state-of-the-art crosslinking chemistries are usually based on the Michael addition of thiol groups to activated alkenes, e.g. thiol-maleimide (Mal) and thiol-vinyl sulfone (VS) coupling reactions. Despite their widespread use, thiol-Mal and thiol-VS are not ideal coupling reactions for 3D cell encapsulation, which is inherent to their respective reaction rate: thiol-Mal gels present too fast curing kinetics while thiol-VS gels cure too slowly. The lack of proper control over gelation kinetics of the system leads to inadequate mixing with consequent gel inhomogeneity in the first case, and to cell sedimentation and clustering in the second. Both situations may lead to non-reproducible response of embedded cells at the microscale. Here, we propose a novel crosslinking system that fills the kinetic gap between these two available models and enables a trade-off between proper kinetic control and gel homogeneity. We present hydrogels crosslinked by nucleophilic aromatic substitution (NAS) of thiol groups over activated aromatic (AAR) substrates. NAS crosslinking chemistry develops under physiological conditions with excellent conversion and adduct stability,¹ therefore is an ideal covalent crosslinking chemistry for gel preparation.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

4-arm, 20 kDa poly(ethyleneglycol) (PEG) macromers carrying AAR functional groups were synthesized and used for crosslinking under physiological conditions (37°C, 10 mM HEPES buffer pH 8.0) with an enzymatically cleavable dithiol crosslinker, following established protocols.² Hydrogel crosslinking, biofunctionalization with cyclo(RGDfC) cell-adhesive peptide and encapsulation of fibroblast L929 cells took place one-pot. The cell-laden hydrogels were cultured for 1-3 days, and cell viability was evaluated by live/dead assay over time. Mechanical properties and curing kinetics of the resulting hydrogel were characterized in situ by rheology. Analogous thiol-Mal and thiol-VS hydrogels were also prepared for comparison.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

NAS coupling chemistry proved to be cytocompatible (cell viability > 90% at 1 day of culture, Fig 1a,c) and to offer a curing speed that was intermediate between thiol-Mal and thiol-VS gels. The practical consequence of this difference was that during hydrogel preparation and cell encapsulation, the system allowed for proper mixing of the gel precursors while homogeneous curing took place and cell sedimentation was avoided (Fig. 1b). Conversely, thiol-Mal and thiol-VS gels presented inhomogeneous cell distribution throughout the material; cells in thiol-Mal gels clustered on top due to too fast crosslinking while in thiol-VS gels cells sedimented due to too slow curing. Finally, mechanical properties of NAS gels also proved intermediate, since elasticity (G') of the diverse gels followed the trend $VS > NAS > Mal$.

CONCLUSION

We demonstrated that NAS coupling reaction, a novel thiol-X curing chemistry, is a superior alternative to state-of-the-art thiol-Mal and thiol-VS chemistries. 3D cell culture gels based on NAS chemistry are expected to become valuable as both implantable and injectable culture models for applications in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine.

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Fig. 1. Viability (a,c) and spatial distribution (b, Z-stack) of fibroblast cells encapsulated in diverse PEG gels.

Poly(decanediol-co-tricarballylate) Elastomeric Nano-Fibrous Mesh Fabricated by Photoreactive Electrospinning for Cardiac Tissue Engineering Applications

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INTRODUCTION

Reactive electrospinning is capable of producing in situ crosslinked scaffolds resembling the natural extracellular matrix efficiently with tunable characteristics. In this study, we aimed to synthesize, characterize and investigate the *in vitro* cytocompatibility of electrospun fibers of acrylated poly (1,10-decanediol-co-tricarballylate) (APDT) copolymer prepared utilizing photoreactive electrospinning process using ultraviolet radiation for crosslinking to be used for cardiac tissue engineering applications.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The APDT pre-polymer was synthesized and characterized as reported by our research group^{1,2}. The 3D elastomeric mesh was fabricated by means of assisted photo-reactive electrospinning (ES) using polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP) as chain entanglement enhancer. APDT with high molecular weight PVP in ethanol solution was prepared and stirred until a clear solution was obtained. The prepared solution was transferred to a syringe and was electrospun to produce an elastomeric mat via optimized electrospinning parameters. The polymer jet was crosslinked in situ using ultraviolet (UV) lamp that lead to the deposition of elastomeric electrospun mat on the collector. At the end of the ES process, the deposited fibers were left under UV for 10 minutes for complete crosslinking of any un-crosslinked residues. The produced scaffolds were fully characterized using different methods. Cell viability and cytotoxicity of the fibers on cultured cardiomyoblasts and cell-scaffolds interaction studies were conducted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical, thermal and morphological characterization confirmed successful synthesis of the polymer used for production of the electrospun fibrous scaffolds with more than 70% porosity. Mechanical testing confirmed the elastomeric nature of the fibers required to withstand cardiac contraction and relaxation. Cell viability assay showed no significant cytotoxicity of the fibers on cultured cardiomyoblasts and cell-scaffolds interaction study showed a significant increase in cell attachment and growth on the electrospun fibers compared to reference.

CONCLUSION

The data support the successful preparation of photocrosslinked electrospun APDT based elastomers as promising scaffolds for cardiac tissue engineering applications.

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Influence of Substrate Stiffness on Cell Response. Focus on Collagen

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INTRODUCTION

Although integrin ligation with ECM is essential for cell signalling, the overall cell response depends on a combination of mechanical, architectural and chemical cues. It has become increasingly apparent that the mechanical properties of the matrix can play a significant role in determining the cell program¹. However, isolating the effect of mechanical cues is experimentally challenging. Collagen (Col), especially fibrillar type I, has been the prime choice of material for biomedical purposes. It provides mechanical support for resident cells and contains cell-recognition motifs that support cellular activity, mainly through their interaction with $\alpha 1\beta 1$, $\alpha 2\beta 1$, $\alpha 10\beta 1$ and $\alpha 11\beta 1$ integrins².

In this work we probe cellular response to changes in stiffness of collagen substrates by using a model system where surface stiffness can be tuned without alteration of its integrin engagement properties.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Well plates with different surface stiffness (elastic modulus of 0.5, 16 and 64kPa) (*CytoSoft*® products) were coated with collagen and peptides (GFOGER, GLOGEN) and used for observing (morphology) and quantifying (adhesion) the effect of mechanics on cellular response independently of other factors. Different cell types were tested: human dermal fibroblasts (HDF), human umbilical vein epithelial cells (HUVEC) and cardiomyocytes (CM, from hESC). ELISA was used to study the possible influence of substrate stiffness on both (1) the density of adhesive ligands and (2) the affinity of the cell adhesion receptor. In first case, primary antibodies COL-1 anti- $\alpha 2$, clone 13, and secondary GOAT anti-mouse HRP DAKO and anti-flag HRP, were used for Col and peptide detections, respectively. For receptor affinity tests the attachment of $\alpha 1$ and $\alpha 2$ -I domains to Col and peptides were determined. Adhesion was quantified by colorimetric assay (A_{490}). Imaging studies were carried out using fluorescent microscopy (ZEISS).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We successfully produced samples of different stiffness, but with comparable controlled levels of adhesion ligands (the same values of Col and peptide densities on plates with different stiffness were observed). Furthermore, $\alpha 1$ and $\alpha 2$ I-domains attachment levels were independent of substrate stiffness. However, cellular adhesion profiles were influenced by substrate rigidity, with response being cell-type dependent. For example, HFB attachment was largely insensitive to changes in substrate stiffness (similar adhesion levels for all studied rigidities, Fig.1A), while CM adhesion was clearly favored on softer substrates (as shown in Fig.1B). The morphology of HFB though was responsive to substrate rigidity (Fig.2): the formation of stress fibers and focal adhesion was promoted on rigid substrates. Other differences in cell adhesion and morphology, as a consequence of stiffness changes, will be discussed in detail in the presentation.

Fig.1 Adhesion profiles of HFB (A) and CM (B) on different substrates/stiffness

Fig.2. HFB morphology on softer (0.5kPa, A) and harder (64kPa, B) substrates (GLOGEN coatings)

CONCLUSION

The cell response to substrate rigidity was assessed independently of other factors. The level of this response was highly cell-specific. The cell receptiveness to their surrounding can be used to influence their behaviour by tuning mechanical properties of cellular supports for specific TE applications.

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High-Throughput 3D Microfluidic Platform for Vascularized Micro Physiological System Applications

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INTRODUCTION

Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) has been widely used in fabricating microfluidic devices for prototyping and proof-of-concept experiments. Due to several material limitations, PDMS has not been widely adopted for commercial applications that require large-scale production. This presentation will describe a novel Injection-Molded Plastic Array 3D Culture (IMPACT) platform that incorporates microfluidic design to integrate patterned 3D cell culture within a single 96-well (diameter = 9 mm). Cell containing gels can be sequentially patterned by capillary-guided flow along the corner and narrow gaps designed within the 96-well form factor. Compared to PDMS-based hydrophobic burst valve designs, this work utilizes hydrophilic liquid guides to obtain rapid and reproducible patterned gels for co-cultures. When a liquid droplet (i.e. cell containing fibrin or collagen gel) is placed on any part of the corner, spontaneous patterning is achieved within 1 second. Optimal dimensionless parameters required for successful capillary loading have been determined. To demonstrate the utility of the platform for 3D co-culture, angiogenesis experiments were performed by patterning HUVEC (human umbilical endothelial cells) and LF (lung fibroblasts) embedded in 3D fibrin gels. The angiogenic sprouts (with open lumen with tip cells expressing junctional proteins) are comparable to those observed in PDMS based devices. The IMPACT device has the potential to provide a robust high-throughput experimental platform for vascularized microphysiological systems.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Neuro-IMPACT design for replicating a 3D in-vitro nervous system. a) Schematic top view of the Neuro-IMPACT for high-throughput experiments and drug screening. The 96-well plate-format Neuro-IMPACT includes two hydrogel injection ports, two media reservoirs (pink), two hydrogel channels (yellow), and micro-post arrays. b) Schematic cross-sectional view of the Neuro-IMPACT. The Neuro-IMPACT consists of an injection-molded polystyrene (PS) piece (gray) and pressure sensitive adhesive (PSA) film (dark yellow). The cells are plated and cultured in the cell culture area (inner dotted line). The wall enables treatment with two different media on two types of cells. c) Schematic of liquid patterning in the Neuro-IMPACT. After plasma treatment

on Neuro-IMPACT, liquid (blue) is introduced through the injection port and patterned in a hydrophilic hydrogel channel between the beam and PSA film by capillary force. d) Schematics of 3D neural circuit, BBB, and myelination. These in-vitro models were reconstructed in the Neuro-IMPACT.

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3D bioprinting of soluble chitosan-lactate conjugate bioinks

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INTRODUCTION

Chitosan (Ch) is one of the most widely applied polysaccharide for tissue engineering and drug delivery applications. Ch is non-toxic, biocompatible, biodegradable and easily manageable through different bio-fabrication techniques [1]. The use of Ch in the 3D bioprinting field has been explored in the last few years [2-6]. Nevertheless, its limited solubility at physiologic pH hampers its use as cell-loaded bioink. Thus, development of water soluble Ch derivatives is of high interest [7]. In this work, we present the synthesis of Ch conjugates by grafting D,L-lactic acid (LA) onto amine groups present in Ch. This versatile modification provided an accurate control over the modification degree of the conjugates, and therefore over their solubility properties. The Ch-LA conjugates are able to ionically crosslink with phosphate groups and eventually provide the successful printing of the inks. Developed bioinks demonstrated appropriate rheological properties, and they were suitable for 3D printing of cell-loaded solutions with excellent biocompatibility.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Synthesis reaction of Ch-LA conjugates was carried out by reacting Ch solution (2 wt-%, 1 v/v-% acetic acid) with the corresponding LA volume (30% molar ratio LA respect to Ch) in presence of 4-(4,6-dimethoxy-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl)-4-methylmorpholinium chloride (DMTMM, twice molar excess respect to LA). The reaction was allowed to proceed for 12 h. The subsequent reaction product was dialyzed against water for 5 days and lyophilized. The degree of substitution was determined by the formation of *N*-salicylidene. The conjugates were characterized by H¹ nuclear magnetic resonance and infrared spectroscopy. Viscosity of bioink solutions at different concentrations (5-7 wt-%) was measured by rheology. Biocompatibility of the developed formulations was assessed in different cell lines (human chondrocytes, human fibroblasts, and MG-63) using live/dead assay. Finally, cell-loaded Ch-LA bioinks were printed using an extrusion 3D printer (Inkredible, CELLINK) directly over an aqueous glycerolphosphate (G₁Phy) crosslinker⁸ solution. 3D printed scaffolds morphology was evaluated by scanning electron and light microscopy. Cell viability in the 3D printed scaffolds was analysed through live/dead assay and fluorescent staining at different time points.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The synthesized Ch-LA conjugates with substitution degree of 25-30% demonstrated excellent solubility at pH 7.4 in PBS at different polymer concentrations (5-7 wt-%). These solutions were successfully printed over a G₁Phy solution thanks to the instantaneous ionic crosslinking that take place between phosphates groups of G₁Phy and amine groups of Ch-LA. This behaviour was not observed in other water-soluble Ch derivatives (e.g. carboxymethyl chitosan). Thus, unloaded 3D scaffolds with high shape fidelity were obtained. Then, Ch-LA formulations biocompatibility was assessed in human chondrocytes, human fibroblasts, and MG-63, demonstrating high cell viability after 24 h of incubation for every cell line and concentration. Polymer concentration was optimized for 3D printing of cell-loaded bioinks to obtain 3D scaffolds with excellent shape fidelity and cell viability. The final 3D structures showed high viability and stability at physiological conditions over time, arising as potent candidates for musculoskeletal regeneration.

CONCLUSION

Cell-loaded hydrogels bioinks based on Ch-LA of control substitution degree provide 3D bioprinting scaffolds that have promising applications in regeneration of musculoskeletal system.

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Interface spontaneous membrane formation by two elastin-like recombinamers

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INTRODUCTION

Liquid/liquid interfaces in combination with physical and covalent interactions have demonstrated their potential to lead the assembly of different materials into sacs¹, tubes² and toroid-shape³ structures. Nonetheless, to the best of our knowledge, no example concerning the exclusive use of elastin-like recombinamers (ELRs) in presence of these environments has been presented to date. In order to explore this scenario, a particular mixture of two immiscible solvents and two click-bearing ELRs were studied to prepare easy-to-handle and thickness controlled elastin-like membranes. Additionally, a study of the effective diffusion coefficients (D_{Eff}) throughout these membranes, concerning a range of fluorescent-labelled molecules in molecular weight and particle size, was performed.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Two ELRs presenting the structure of [VPG(VK)G]₁₄₄ and [(VPG(VSVKVS)V)G]₂-RGD-(VPG(VSVKVS)V)G]₂ were produced in E. Coli bacteria introducing a posteriori the adequate click chemistry moiety to proportionate the crosslinking ability. A piston device was built to hold the immiscible solutions and facilitate the isolation of the membranes. Franz cells were employed to study the diffusion properties in presence of FITC-Dextran molecules whilst scanning electron microscopy was followed to perform a microstructural characterization of the ELR-membranes. Furthermore, a video to study the nucleation and growing stages with time was recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A set of manipulable and controlled in thickness ELR-membranes in the range from 5 to 26 nm were built. As found, the porous interior provided the capacity to control the diffusion of 4, 20, 40, 70 and 150 kDa FITC-dextran molecules in water depicting curves from logarithmic to sigmoidal shapes. Found D_{Eff} values were up to three times lower than the inherent diffusion coefficient (D_0) of such molecules in pure water.

CONCLUSION

A technology able to produce tailored ELR-membranes with controlled shape, thickness and bioactivity has been developed. Furthermore, the obtained data from the diffusion experiments demonstrated the interesting accompanied transportation properties in aqueous solutions for small molecules in both size and molecular weight. These characteristics, in combination with the inherent biocompatible feature of the employed ELRs building blocks, opens the possibility to use these systems as advanced scaffolds for tissue engineering applications.

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Highly Hydrophobic PLA Films and Their Degradation Over Time

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INTRODUCTION

The use of polylactic acid (PLA) in bone repair has certain drawbacks such as inadequate mechanical properties. Moreover, the continuous degradation of PLA inside the human body would affect directly to its surface properties and, by consequence, to its interaction with the environment. This research would focus in two objectives: the development of a methodology for preparing and modifying the chemical composition of PLA to attenuate and/or eliminate its drawbacks, and the characterization of the surface physical properties of the biomaterial before and after being degraded.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

PLA and PLA10Mg films were prepared by the solvent-casting method using PLA from NatureWorks and magnesium particles ($\leq 100 \mu\text{m}$). The topography and roughness (RMS) were evaluated by using an AFM and the distribution of magnesium particles in the composite was observed with a SEM. Crystallinity was evaluated by XRD. Degraded films, PLA_PBS and PLA10Mg_PBS, were obtained after immersion of samples in phosphate buffer saline (PBS) at 37 °C for 28 days. Hydrophobicity was quantified through water contact angle measurements (WCA) by the sessile drop method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the WCA and RMS values. The films are highly hydrophobic. The WCA, 106.6°, is higher than those reported in literature^{1,2} (70-80°). Li *et al.*³ point out that the hydrophobicity of PLA increases when its crystallinity does, due to the orientation of the methyl groups on its surface. SEM images and X-Ray diffractograms

of our films confirm that the crystallinity varies according to the solvent. Packaging of the polymer chains is also affected and therefore the number of methyl groups on the surface of the film may increase, which could explain the difference in contact angles. The roughness of the films increases when the PLA is reinforced with Mg. This roughness also increases when PLA10Mg films are immersed in PBS during 28 days, due to the formation of a MgP layer, which makes it impossible to quantify by AFM. Presence of this insoluble salt also affects WCA of films.

Table 1. Water contact angle and RMS values of the films.

	WCA	RMS (nm)	σ (nm)
PLA	106.6° ± 1.1	11.71	5.45
PLA10Mg	105.6° ± 0.6	36.53	16.82
PLA_PBS	103.8° ± 2.8	56.79	11.80
PLA10Mg_PBS	85.6° ± 14.6	-	-

CONCLUSION

Solvent-cast PLA and PLA10Mg films are more hydrophobic and smoother than those manufactured by other methods. This higher hydrophobicity can improve the cellular adhesion and the smooth surface can be considered as a good control for further degradation studies. Films reinforced with magnesium are less hydrophobic after degradation probably due to the formation of a MgP layer.

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A New Synthesis Route of Amphiphilic Polyester-g-Oligosaccharide Copolymers for Anticancer Drug Delivery

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INTRODUCTION

Biocompatible and biodegradable amphiphilic copolymers with well-defined architectures are one of the challenging areas in nanomedicine field for controlled drug delivery applications^{1,2}. In this field, aliphatic polyesters, such as poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL), are interesting hydrophobic synthetic polymer candidates as a result of their biodegradability, biocompatibility and FDA approval. Furthermore, oligosaccharides, such as dextran or chitosan, are hydrophilic naturally occurring polymers of choice because they are renewable, biocompatible, protein repellent with numerous functionalities along their chains. Here, we described a general route to synthesize an original polyester-g-oligosaccharide structure. Nano-systems based on these novel copolymers have been prepared and loaded with an anti-cancer drug, Doxorubicin, to deliver it specifically into tumoral cells³.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Functionalization and Chemical Modifications: i) Propargylated PCL was synthesized by a one-pot “anionic activation-substitution” reaction. ii) Dextran was chemically modified onto its reductive chain extremity *via* a reductive amination and a substitution step to get azidopropyl-dextran. iii) PCL-g-dextran copolymer synthesis by a CuAAC click chemistry reaction. A fluorescent copolymer derivative has also been synthesized by reaction with FITC.

Preparation of nano-objects. Copolymeric doxorubicin-loaded or fluorescent nano-systems were prepared by a nanoprecipitation process. Cytotoxicity, confocal imaging and flow cytometry experiments have been realized.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PCL has been functionalized at a substitution ratio of 8 % according to the ¹H-NMR analysis. Azidopropyl-dextran derivative has been synthesized and grafted to the propargylated PCL backbone. Different PCL-g-dextran copolymer batches have been realized with various lipophilic-hydrophilic balances. Nano-objects based on these copolymers have been prepared and loaded with doxorubicin. Cytotoxicity experiments allowed to compare the therapeutic efficiency of such nano-systems between colorectal cancer cells and healthy fibroblasts.

Fig. 1: Preparation of a new amphiphilic graft copolymer based on functionalized PCL and dextran derivative

Moreover, thanks to the various functionalities present on oligosaccharide chains, a fluorescent PCL-g-dextran copolymer has been prepared by covalent coupling of a fluorescent probe to prepare then fluorescent nano-objects. Cell internalization of these nano-carriers has been studied by confocal imaging and flow cytometry.

CONCLUSION

New polyester-g-oligosaccharide copolymers have been successfully synthesized and anti-cancer drug loaded copolymeric nano-systems have been prepared. Biological studies showed a poor internalization of nano-systems by healthy cells in comparison with cancer cells. Consequently, it has been shown that drug loaded copolymeric nano-objects killed cancer cells without affecting healthy cells.

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Injectable Hydrogel based on Chitosan Derivative, Galactomannan and Chitin Whiskers

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INTRODUCTION

Hydrogels demonstrate great potential to be applied in tissue engineering (TE) due to their high water content, high porosity, and three-dimensional connectivity. Injectable or *in situ* forming hydrogels are biomaterial that can be injected in liquid form and then solidify at the administration site. As a result, they can be applied in a minimally invasive way, avoids the need of surgery, fill any cavity (regardless of the shape) and have the ability to encapsulate cells and/or drugs. For the production of injectable hydrogels, the use of polysaccharides is appealing due to their specific properties such as: resemblance with native extracellular matrix (ECM), biodegradability, and favorable cell-adhesion property. In this work, water-soluble chitosan derivative and oxidized galactomannan were used to prepare injectable hydrogels by the formation of Schiff bases or imine bonds (-CH=N-), reinforced with chitin nanowhiskers.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

N-succinyl-chitosan and oxidized *Delonix regia* galactomannan were used as raw material. The chitosan derivative was obtained by the reaction of chitosan with succinic anhydride. Galactomannan was extracted from *D. Regia* seeds and further oxidized with sodium periodate. The chitin nanowhiskers (CNWs) were prepared from chitin flakes. After characterization 3 wt/v% polysaccharides solutions were used to prepare a series of injectable hydrogels. The amount of chitin nanowhiskers used varied from 0.2 to 1.0 wt/v%. The characterization was carried out by gelation time, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), injectability, rheology, swelling, porosity, and cytotoxicity assay.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The hydrogel without CNWs was translucent and as the amount of CNWs augmented, the turbidity increased. The gelation time decreased as the concentration of chitin increased. Molecular interaction between the two polysaccharides was necessary for the Schiff base formation. The CNWs acted as an obstacle, increasing the gelation time. The swelling degree was 30±5 g water/g of dried gel for all chitin concentration. Injectability of the hydrogel was assessed by extruding the components of the hydrogel through the tube of a 22 G syringe. It is noteworthy that even with the presence of CNWs, the hydrogel can flow easily. The rheological studies demonstrated that all gels behaved as a viscoelastic material, but stronger gels were obtained in the presence of chitin. The elastic modulus G' of hydrogel with 0.5% of CNWs was 250 Pa, more than twice of the gel without chitin (118 Pa). The viscous modulus G'' of hydrogel without and with 0.5% reinforcement were 51 and 41 Pa, respectively. Cytotoxicity studies are on progress, but the preliminary results are encouraging.

CONCLUSION

Hydrogels with high swelling capacity, porosity, and injectability were obtained from oxidized galactomannan and N'-succinyl chitosan by the formation of Schiff bases. The presence of chitin whiskers increased the gelation time, made the gel stronger but didn't change the swelling or the injectability. The results so far meet the requirements for the injectable hydrogel to be used in TE.

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PP peritoneal meshes covered with PCL nanofibers functionalized by cold plasma with antiadhesive properties

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INTRODUCTION

During intra-abdominal operations, postoperative adhesions, resulting in pain, occur in more than 50% of cases¹. This phenomenon consists in the formation of a fibrin matrix between organs and peritoneum 5 to 7 days following the surgery and induced by the coagulation cascade. So, it is necessary to produce a long-term anti-coagulant active implant to limit these post-operative adhesions. Nowadays, a large variety of processes is used to design biomedical textile implants. Among them, electrospinning offers advantages for biomedical applications especially due to the nanoscale diameter range of electrospun fibers and their high porosity and surface area². In addition, cold plasma process can be used to activate and/or functionalize electrospun fibers. In the literature, cold plasma is indeed mainly used to enhance hydrophilicity or to graft polymers at the nanofibers surface³. In this context, our strategy is to develop polypropylene (PP) implants, coated with polycaprolactone (PCL) electrospun nanofibers and functionalized by 2-acrylamido-2-methylpropane sulfonic acid (AMPS) (monomer with heparin-like functions) thanks to a cold plasma technique.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

PCL, in a mixture of formic/acetic acid, was electrospun onto PP meshes and then immersed in AMPS solution. Low pressure cold plasma treatment was optimized through experimental design in order to graft-copolymerize these monomers on the PCL nanofibers. Adequate physico-chemical characterizations were performed (FTIR, SEM, TGA...) at each step of the process. Then, cytocompatibility was evaluated, on appropriate cell line (fibroblasts, NIH3T3). Finally, coagulation and haemocompatibility assays were carried out in order to evaluate the anticoagulant properties of these membranes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First, the electrospinning conditions of PCL solutions was optimized in terms of concentration, voltage, flow, tip-to-collector distance. The graft-copolymerization of AMPS was optimized to obtain cytocompatible nanofibers rich in SO₃H groups at the surface. SEM images revealed an increase in the nanofibers diameter after the plasma induced graft polymerization, and mapping confirmed the presence of AMPS onto nanofibers. Biological *in vitro* assays revealed promising results for anti-adhesive applications of these membranes.

CONCLUSION

We have successfully optimized the electrospinning of PCL and AMPS grafting onto these mats by cold plasma, and we highlighted the presence of sulfonate groups onto the surface of the nanofibers. The cytocompatibility, haemocompatibility and anti-coagulant activities of the functionalized implants were demonstrated. Future work will focus on the grafting of other bioactive monomers such as antibacterial ones in order to extend the field of potential biomedical applications.

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Hyaluronic acid/chitosan titanium multilayers with antibacterial properties

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INTRODUCTION

Titanium metal and its alloys have been used for the development of non-organic permanent implants for the last decades. Prosthesis based in these materials present high biocompatibility, elasticity, resistance to corrosion,¹ ability to integrate into local bone stock, and as a consequence, they do not cause allergies and, therefore, reduce the probability of rejection.² Nevertheless, bacterial contamination of implant surfaces, including titanium, is a critical concern because it can lead to infection and implant failure, compromising patient's health and increasing treatment costs. The main cause of these infections is the formation of the biofilm, being the first 24 hours crucial for bacterial attachment.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Ti-6Al-4V samples with different surface patterning, smooth and with micrometric grooves, were used for this work. Previously washed titanium samples were hydrolysed by treatment with a mixture H₂SO₄ (96%): H₂O₂ (30%) (3:1) under stirring during one hour. Samples were immersed in a solution of 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) and kept stirring for an hour, and then samples were thoroughly washed.

5 bilayers of HA / CHI were deposited upon amino-functionalized titanium samples. For this, alloys were immersed in a solution of hyaluronic acid and subsequently cleaned in acetate buffer solution. Then, hyaluronic acid covered samples were dipped into a CHI solution and washed by rinsing in acetate buffer solution. Alternating dipping process was repeated until the number of layers desired was developed. Finally, samples were washed in distilled water to remove traces of salt. The antibacterial activity of these surfaces were analysed against *Staphylococcus aureus* by testing the adhesion and viability of these microorganisms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, three strategies have been used to avoid biofilm formation; one based on the micro patterning of the surface, second based on the increase of the hydrophilicity of the surface and third by obtaining a "contact-killing" surfaces. To this, hyaluronic acid and chitosan biopolymers have been used to build up a multifunctional cover onto Ti-6Al-4V by using layer-by-layer assembly. To improve the attachment of the layers, the substrates were activated generating anchoring groups (-NH₂ groups) on the substrate and functionalization was corroborated by XPS analysis. The multilayers formation was monitored by labelling chitosan with fluorescein isothiocyanate (FTIC) and using fluorescence confocal microscopy. The fluorescence intensity increases with the number of layers (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Fluorescence of titanium samples with A) 0 layers, B) 5 and C) 10 HA/FTIC-CHI bilayers.

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Modification and optimization of polysaccharides for hydrogel formation for bone tissue regeneration

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INTRODUCTION

Recently, polysaccharide-based hydrogels have attracted considerable attention as bioactive agents in regenerative medicine.¹ The main goal of this study was to use different approaches to modify and optimize the synthesis of oxidized polysaccharides to act as hydrogel precursors for preparing stable hydrogel systems that favor bone tissue regeneration.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Different amounts of NaIO₄ were used in order to oxidize Alginate (ALG) and Hyaluronate (HA), forming reactive dialdehyde derivatives. The amount of aldehyde groups was determined by using Schiff's reagent and detected by a UV-Vis spectrometer and acid base titration after reacting the aldehyde groups with HONH₂·HCl. Gel Permeation Chromatography was used for molecular weight determination. Biocompatibility of the products was tested using Qblue® assay and CFDA staining.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data obtained from both UV-VIS spectroscopy and titration show that the different polysaccharides have more aldehyde groups when high concentrations of NaIO₄ were used and the reaction times were extended. The weight average molecular weights of all the products were lower after the oxidation step. Products with high oxidation degrees showed low biocompatibility.

ALG and HA with high oxidation degrees are required to prepare stable hydrogel systems. The hydrogel formation is driven by Schiff base crosslinking reaction between the amino functionalities of carboxymethyl chitosan (CMChi) and the aldehyde groups of the different oxidized polysaccharides resulting in an imine bond formation.

CONCLUSION

The dual utility of using CMChi and oxidized polysaccharides as both structural and bioactive component is promising for the formation of biocompatible hydrogel systems that can be used for bone tissue regeneration.

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Micellar HPMA Polymer-Drug Conjugates for Immunooncotherapy

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INTRODUCTION

Herein, the micelle-forming amphiphilic *N*-(2-hydroxypropyl) methacrylamide (HPMA)-based polymer conjugates with the anti-cancer drug doxorubicin or docetaxel designed for enhanced tumor accumulation were investigated in detail.^{1,2} The drugs were attached to the polymer carrier by a hydrazone bond enabling pH-controlled drug release. While the polymer-drug conjugates were stable in a buffer at pH 7.4 (mimicking blood stream environment), the drug was released in a buffer under mild acidic conditions modelling the tumor tissue or cells. Moreover, the drugs were used also in combination to improve anticancer activity. Besides polymer conjugates for oncotherapy, polymer conjugates with various signal transducer and activator of transcription 3 (STAT3) inhibitors, i.e. phosphopeptides or cucurbitacin, were synthesized and characterized *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Their combination with polymer-bound chemotherapeutics should help the immune system to treat cancers more effectively.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Various HPMA-based polymer carriers were synthesized by free or controlled RAFT radical polymerization. All polymer carriers and their drug conjugates were characterized by determination of molecular weight, hydrodynamic size, critical micelle concentration, content of functional groups or drug, etc. Also biological properties, besides cytostatic activity *in vitro* namely biodistribution, tumor accumulation and antitumor activity were evaluated using EL-4 T-cell lymphoma or 4T1 mammary carcinoma in mice.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The amphiphilic polymer carriers differed in the structure of hydrophobic cholesterol derivative moieties bound to the HPMA copolymers via a stable or hydrolytically degradable hydrazone bond, exhibiting different rates of micellar structure disintegration at various pH values. The final therapeutic outcome was strongly determined by the stability of the micellar structure, showing superior tumor-specific drug delivery and the best therapeutic effect in the most stable micellar carrier structure. Also, the combination of drugs, such as doxorubicin and docetaxel, with different mechanism of action enhanced the therapeutic effect during the treatment of poorly treatable 4T1 carcinoma. Notably, the micelles carrying both drugs showed better anti-tumor activity and less systemic toxicity at doses close to maximal tolerated dose (MTD) than combination of two micelles delivering either drug at the same dosage.

Conjugation of cucurbitacin D, a potential immunomodulatory agent, to the polymer carrier, resulted in a conjugate with good water solubility, suitable drug release profile, and applicability as a drug delivery system *in vivo*, which cannot be applied for the parent free drug. Linear or micelle-forming conjugates with cucurbitacin D bound by pH-sensitive hydrazone bond showed strong inhibitory effect in tumor cell lines with overexpressed STAT3, which in many human tumors promotes their initiation and progression. Moreover, in the combination with polymer conjugates bearing doxorubicin, the cucurbitacin D-containing conjugates proved anti-tumor capacity in murine carcinoma model. The polymer conjugates with peptide inhibitor of STAT3 signaling, phosphopeptide pYLPQTV bound either by biodegradable or stable spacer, did not show any cytostatic/cytotoxic effect *in vitro*.

CONCLUSION

Micelle-forming polymer drug conjugates with chemotherapeutics, especially in the combination with the stimulation of the immune system are very promising to be used for the future personalized medicine.

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Light-responsive drug release from living hydrogels

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INTRODUCTION

Living materials are an emerging class of smart materials that contain living organisms that are genetically modified to perform enhanced functions. We are developing living hydrogels containing bacteria that act as productive, adaptable and replenishable on-demand drug delivery repositories.^{1,2} The polymer matrix of the hydrogel maintains the structural integrity inside the bodily environment while the living organisms produce the optimal amount of drug at the required time of delivery. Here we demonstrate the development of a pluronic F127-based hydrogel system to encapsulate genetically engineered *E. coli* bacterial strain, in 3D bioprinted constructs and thin films, leading to a light-regulated, localized, tunable and prolonged release of deoxyviolacein (dVio), an anti-microbial and anti-tumoral drug.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The light-regulated dVio-producing *E. coli* strain was engineered by incorporating the genes related to the metabolic synthesis of dVio into a blue-light responsive optogenetic plasmid, pDawn.² Bacteria was encapsulated in 3D-bioprinted constructs and thin films made of pluronic F127 and its diacrylated derivative (Figure (a) and (b) respectively) capable of being crosslinked on UV light exposure using a free-radical photoinitiator. These constructs were used to study the effect of change in the crosslinking density and thus the mechanical properties on the bacterial growth rate. Thin films of bacterial hydrogels were casted on the porous membrane (0.4 μm diameter pores) of transwell inserts to detect the drug production after 48 h irradiation at 470 nm light exposure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After 48 h within the physically crosslinked hydrogel (PluronicDA:Pluronic::0:1, Storage Modulus ca. 19 kPa), maximum bacterial growth and dVio production of 9.22 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ was observed (Figure (c)). Whereas with increasing pluronic diacrylate ratio (upto PluronicDA:Pluronic::1:0, Storage Modulus ca. 48 kPa) and thus the increasing chemical crosslinking density, the bacterial growth was limited and the dVio production was regulated to 0.89 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Figure (c)).

CONCLUSION

Genetically engineered bacteria were successfully encapsulated inside 3D bioprinted constructs using a pluronic F127 diacrylate hydrogel system. We demonstrate the possibility of controlling the bacterial growth and drug release *in situ* in a light-regulated manner by tuning the mechanical properties of the hydrogel.

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Vinyl-based microfluidic chips for human skin models

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INTRODUCTION

In this work we present a new disposable biochip based on a vinyl design, overcoming the limitations of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) microfluidic devices¹, that can mimic skin physiology and architecture. This biochip supports the development in the upper channel of a *in situ* bioengineered skin equivalent that is properly maintained through a lower channel that is continuously perfused with culture medium supporting the correct development of the skin equivalent.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The vinyl chip is composed of an upper channel (height: 0.9 mm) that holds the dermis compartment (fibrin hydrogel + human dermal fibroblasts) and the epidermis (immortalized keratinocytes) allowing enough space to expose it to the air-liquid interface. A lower channel (height: 0.3 mm) is continuously perfused with culture medium. A parallel flow protocol was carried out to introduce the dermis compartment inside the chip's upper chamber with one syringe loaded with PBS and a second syringe loaded with a pregel fibrinogen solution, thrombin and calcium chloride (CaCl₂) with human dermal fibroblasts with the help of two syringe pumps. Then, DMEM is pumped for 24 hours through the free space left in the upper channel by PBS to let the human dermal fibroblasts spread. The day after, immortalised keratinocytes are seeded to confluence on top of the gel. Characterization of the dermis and epidermis inside of the chip was carried out with an inverted microscope and a confocal microscope using fluorescence human dermal fibroblasts and immortalised keratinocytes. Live/dead assay was carried out in order to check the viability of the skin cells.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We were able to obtain a dermis of 400 µm (height) as predicted by our parallel flow model. Human dermal fibroblasts were spread within the fibrin along the upper channel and alive after 24 h. Then, immortalised keratinocytes were pumped through the free space left in the upper channel with the help of a syringe pump and seeded to confluence on top of the dermis. After 24 hours, we were able to distinguish and characterize the two compartments (dermis and epidermis) inside of the chip.

CONCLUSION

Preliminary tests indicate that this biochip allows the correct development and maintenance of dermo-epidermal skin equivalents and it is good alternative to PDMS-based microfluidic devices. This skin-on-a-chip system has the potential of replacing the actual *in vitro* and animal models, reproducing skin structure, physiology and pathology suitable for cosmetic/drug testing and biomarker identification in a human scenario.

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Photoresponsive biomaterials for light-triggered angiogenesis

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INTRODUCTION

Angiogenesis, defined as the growth of new blood vessels, is a critical process in wound healing. In the body, various adhesive proteins and growth factors are presented around a wound site and act as cues to guide angiogenesis.¹ Mixtures of these molecules are administered in the clinic to promote wound healing, but their short shelf lives and difficulties in controlling their distribution in the target site are outstanding concerns. This work aims to address both the stability issue and the distribution challenge by developing synthetic 3D hydrogels which offer improved stability and controlled presentation of angiogenic factors through on-command light activation. RGD, the key cell adhesion motif in extracellular matrix proteins, and QK,² a synthetic peptide which mimics the active α -helical region of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), were selected as the two angiogenic species. Light-responsive analogues of QK and RGD were designed to be biologically inert in the hydrogels until activation using various wavelengths of light. Precise spatiotemporal control of blood vessel formation was envisaged through this strategy.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Peptides: Photo-responsive versions of RGD (^pRGD) and QK (^pQK) were prepared bearing appropriate termini for conjugation to hydrogels. The photoresponsive groups were introduced by either incorporating pre-synthesised amino acids bearing the photo-responsive group into the peptide using Fmoc-based solid phase peptide synthesis (SPPS), or by directly linking of the photo-responsive unit to pre-formed peptide. **Hydrogels:** Maleimide-terminated 4-arm poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) was reacted with the thiol-bearing peptide(s) and dithiol crosslinker. For 3D gels, enzyme-degradable crosslinker was used, and human umbilical cord endothelial cells (HUVECs) were added prior to crosslinking. **Photoactivation:** Gels were irradiated at the required wavelengths in a Zeiss 880 LSM confocal microscope. **Imaging:** Samples were observed over 3 – 7 d. Cells were fixed and stained using standard procedures, and imaged with a Zeiss Azio Observer epi-fluorescence microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Control experiments demonstrated that the angiogenic phenotype in HUVECs is induced when cell-adhesive peptide (RGD) and growth factor (VEGF or its peptide mimetic QK) are both present. In the absence of either component, no angiogenesis is observed. Two strategies were therefore explored for on-command angiogenesis using light; a) incorporating light-activatable RGD as the adhesive component bound to the hydrogel,³ and b) employing light-activatable analogues of the growth factor component QK.

Using approach a), ^pRGD bearing a 2-photon-active photocage could be efficiently decaged with precise spatiotemporal control using 740 nm light at doses that did not compromise cell functionality. Angiogenesis could be induced selectively in the irradiated regions of the HUVEC-embedded hydrogel (in the presence of soluble VEGF) (Fig. 1). The ^pRGD was hydrolytically and enzymatically stable over > 7 days, with non-irradiated areas showing an absence of angiogenesis equivalent to RGD-free control systems. Light-triggered angiogenesis can also be achieved with strategy b) by using RGD-functionalised hydrogels containing photoresponsive variants of QK either tethered to the hydrogel or used in soluble (unbound) form. We are continuing to explore this approach.

Figure 1. 3-Day confocal microscopy image of HUVECs embedded in ^pRGD-functionalised hydrogel in the presence of VEGF. Only the region inside the yellow rectangle was activated (740 nm light), showing selective onset of microvasculature formation. High magnification of the region in the white rectangle is shown on the right. Nuclei were stained with DAPI (blue), actin fibers with phalloidin (red), and cell body with PECAM-1 (green). Reproduced with permission from Wiley (ref. 3).

CONCLUSION

Light-triggered angiogenesis was achieved with precise spatiotemporal control in hydrogels functionalized with light-responsive angiogenic factors, and is promising for the development of clinically-relevant angiogenic biomaterials.

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Long-term anti-inflammatory capacity of layer-by-layer coatings embedding naproxen-based polymeric nanoparticles

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INTRODUCTION

Long-term use of biomaterials is limited by the inflammatory response elicited upon implantation¹. Glycosaminoglycans-based coatings have demonstrated promising immediate anti-inflammatory activity² but there is still lack of definitive long-lasting solutions¹. This work aims to develop anti-inflammatory surface coating combining the immediate anti-inflammatory capacity of heparin (Hep) and the long-term controlled release of naproxen (NAP) from cationic polymeric nanoparticles (NAP-NPs).

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Multilayered films formed by four bilayers of Hep (polyanion) and NAP-NPs (polycation) were prepared by **dip coating** on top of a PEI anchoring layer (PEI(Hep-NPs)₄). Real-time film formation kinetics and viscoelastic properties were assessed using quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring (**D-QCM**). Topography and surface charge was studied by **SEM** and **AFM**, and **Z-potential** measurements, respectively. The controlled release of the NPs was indirectly assessed by **flow-cytometry** as the percentage of THP1-derived macrophages that has internalized immobilized-coumarin-6-loaded NPs after 1 and 15 days. Short-term (24 hours) IL-1 β released levels and macrophage adhesion was determined by **ELISA** and **Giemsa staining**, correspondingly. Finally, surfaces were evaluated for long-term (15 days) Foreign Body Giant Cells (FBGCs) formation by **Giemsa staining**.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

D-QCM data revealed effective film growth and viscoelastic behaviour of the system according to the decrease in vibration frequency and the increase in energy dissipation (ΔD) after each layer deposition, respectively. SEM (**figure 1**) and AFM micrographs showed a homogenous distribution of the NPs across the surface with a certain roughness indicating successful immobilization of the NPs. Z-potential measurements revealed a negative surface charge at physiological pH which is above the pK_b of NPs (5.5-6.0) and above the pK_a of Hep.

Figure 1. SEM micrograph of the top layer of the PEI(Hep-NPs)₄ system.

Endocytosis studies indirectly revealed a controlled release of the NAP-NPs from the multi-layered system. Reduced macrophage adhesion was observed after 24 hours attributed to the high hydrophilicity and negative charge of the surface. Moreover, short-term studies demonstrated a significant reduction in IL1- β released levels attributed to the previously described immediate anti-inflammatory capacity of heparin². After 15 days, a significant reduction in FBGCs formation was observed that might be attributed to the controlled release of NPs from the surface.

CONCLUSION

A novel multi-layered system based on Hep and NAP-containing NPs was successfully prepared. *In-vitro* results demonstrate that the previously described immediate anti-inflammatory activity of Hep is not compromised by the immobilization of NPs as terminal layer and the controlled release of NPs translates into a promising long-term anti-inflammatory activity by reducing FBGCs formation after 15 days.

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Characterization of polyelectrolyte complexes by inline coupling of capillary electrophoresis to Taylor dispersion analysis – Application to polyplexes

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INTRODUCTION

In non-viral gene transfer, analysis of polynucleotide-polybase polyelectrolytic complexes (PEC) is necessary¹. The inline coupling of capillary electrophoresis (CE) to Taylor dispersion analysis (TDA) was proposed as a new method to assess charge stoichiometry and hydrodynamic radii of PEC components within less than 20 min using a standard commercial CE apparatus with single detection point². Frontal TDA was used in the case of the analysis of polyplexes because of its higher sensitivity³.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Dissociation and electrophoretic separation of polyelectrolyte constituents of PEC formed by stepwise mixing of poly(L-lysine citramide) (PLCA) and poly(L-lysine) (PLL) taken as PEC model was achieved using 1.3 M NaCl background electrolyte. The PEC stoichiometry was determined by using CE at each step of the neutralization. By differential measurement, the diffusion coefficient and thus the hydrodynamic radius of the two polyelectrolytes were obtained by TDA. The size of polyplex of DNA from salmon testes and linear and dendrigraft PLLs with various DP was obtained by frontal TDA together with the amount of the free polycation chains in excess in solution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data confirmed that the (+/-) stoichiometry of PLL/PLCA complexes depended on the mixing order, i.e. it was found close to 1 when PLL was added to PLCA and above 1 when PLCA was added to PLL. The experimental results demonstrated that strong molar mass selectivity occurred on the titrated polyelectrolyte². CE/TDA was found much faster and straightforward than off-line ion-exchange chromatography coupled with size-exclusion chromatography that required much more time and much greater injected quantities, and could not be fully automatized (dialysis and freeze-drying steps between chromatographic steps)⁴. In the case of DNA-polycation polyplexes, hydrodynamic radius (R_h) values obtained by TDA were systematically higher than those obtained by dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements³.

CONCLUSION

The CE/TDA methodology appeared very powerful for the characterization of polyelectrolyte complexes. TDA and DLS were found complementary techniques. TDA gives access to the weight-average R_h , in contrary to DLS that basically gives access to the intensity-average (harmonic z-average) R_h value. The ratio of the R_h values given by the two methods corresponds to the polydispersity of the sample. The interest of the CE and TDA techniques in PEC-based gene vectors designing and optimizing will be discussed.

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The biocompatibility of electrically conducting polymers

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INTRODUCTION

Conducting polymers (CP) intrinsically combine electronic and ionic conductivity. This properties of CP can be employed in preparation of biointerface between the conventional biomaterials and electro-sensitive tissues. Two most common studied CP are polypyrrole (PPy) and polyaniline (PANI). Both has been previously tested in number of copolymers and composites with aim to provide a biomaterial with advanced properties¹⁻³. There is however no study comparing their biological properties such as. Thanks to the broad experience of our laboratory with determination of biological properties of materials, we decided to study both mentioned CP and compares their biocompatibility.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

PPy and PANI were synthesized by the most common procedures. Two parameters of biocompatibility were studied; the first, basic one - cytotoxicity was investigated using common fibroblasts NIH/3T3 cell line and embryonic stem cells. The second, advanced parameter - embryotoxicity was studied in terms of the impact of each of the polymers on the erythropoiesis and cardiomyogenesis within the embryonic bodies. Moreover, the impurity content was determined by mass spectroscopy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The novelty of the study lies, among others, in the elimination of inter-laboratory variations within the testing, such variation making the comparison of previously published works difficult. The direct comparison of both polymers using the same methodology showed that the form of the polymer (salt vs base) is more important than its type (PPY vs PANI) when cytotoxicity and embryotoxicity are taken into consideration. Especially the polymers in the form of bases proved low cytotoxicity and embryotoxicity. To clarify the reasons for determined differences in biological properties of PANI and PPY, the mass spectroscopy was used to determine their impurity profiles. The detected impurities can't, however, fully explain observed differences. For example, with respect to presence of major molecular ions, the extract of PPY base exhibited simpler mass spectra in comparison with extract of PANI base. PANI and PPy can, therefore, be similarly applied in biomedicine when solely their biological properties are considered.

CONCLUSION

Polypyrrole and polyaniline were synthesized by the most common procedures and studied within one laboratory to eliminate the inter-laboratory differences. The biological properties of both conductive polymers were similar. Therefore, the presented results should mainly provoke the scientific community to compare also other biological properties of both conducting polymers as, according to currently presented results, they are more similar than previously assumed and their application potential can be, at least, comparable.

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Selective block copolymer films with antibacterial and biocompatible properties

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INTRODUCTION

Bacteria contamination is one of the most important threats to biomaterial implantation. New strategies with no risk to generate antibiotic resistance are needed to control bacterial adhesion and growth [1]. Herein, we describe the self-assembly of block copolymers (PS-*b*-P2VP) to create versatile antibacterial nanopatterns on large surface areas.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Block copolymers were spin coated and annealed with vapor of different solvents to obtain nanopatterned surfaces. The “contact killing” capacity was evaluated for 30 and 90 minutes with *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) as examples of gram negative and gram positive bacteria, respectively. The cytocompatibility of the nanopatterns was tested against L929 cell line. AFM, SEM, contact angle and immunocytochemistry were performed to characterize the surfaces with and without cells.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three different nanopatterns (one micellar, and two cylindrical with different morphology) were obtained changing the experimental conditions. SEM images and live/death experiments showed that both cylindrical nanopatterns, where the P2VP is exposed, affected tremendously the integrity of the bacterial membrane and caused bacterial death, being the *E. coli* membrane more damaged.

SEM and immunocytochemistry revealed the cell-material interaction and the normal behaviour for L929 cell line if compared with the control.

Figure 1. SEM micrographs of L929 cell line (A), *E. coli* (B) and *S. aureus* (C) cultured on the nanopatterned surfaces.

CONCLUSION

The nanopatterns generated are efficient tool in the fight against bacteria. At the same time, they allowed the normal mammalian cell growth making them good candidates for the “race for the surface” step, where the cells compete for the biomaterial invasion.

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Chondroitin Sulfate A-based PEM films: Biomimetic matrices for tissue engineering

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INTRODUCTION

Bioinspired extracellular matrices (ECMs) are up-to-date trends in the fields of implant integration and tissue modelling, as they can mimic cell microenvironments by integrating bio-chemico-physical parameters. In this line, we developed a versatile biomimetic ECM-like platform, based on polyelectrolyte multilayer films (PEMs)¹, composed of chondroitin sulfate A (CSA, anionic), and poly-L-lysine (PLL, cationic), that were stiffened by a biocompatible crosslinker (genipin, GnP)². First, we developed these PEMs for the surface functionalization of bone biomaterials to improve their bioactivity towards pre-osteoblasts (MC3T3-E1). Then, we applied them for the design of a tumorous ECM-mimicking matrix for the differentiation of neuroblastoma (NB) cells (LAN-1). In practice, we combined the modulation of the mechanical properties of our PEM films with a commonly used pharmacological drug in neuroblastoma cancer treatment (all-trans retinoic acid, ATRA).

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

PEM films were built-up with 1 mg.mL⁻¹ CSA, PLL solutions, prepared in Tris/NaCl buffer. In some cases, films were crosslinked with GnP. Then, the films were characterized by AFM (topography and stiffness) and SEM. Cell morphology and neurites extensions were assessed by fluorescence microscopy (DAPI for nuclei, FITC-phalloidin for actin cytoskeleton (MC3T3-E1) or rhodamin-phalloidin (LAN-1), and I-Ab anti-β3-tubulin with FITC-labelled II-Ab (LAN-1). Raman microspectroscopy was used to inspect the formation of mineralized nodules (MC3T3-E1). Data were treated by Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon test (p<0.05 considered as significant).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We observed a favourable synergy of topo-mimetic surfaces and our PEM films since pre-osteoblasts cells were able to mature and produced hydroxyapatite-containing nodules over time⁴ (A).

We found that by combining appropriate PEM films stiffness to ATRA treatments, NB cells were able to differentiate and produced neurite extensions as revealed by the presence of β3-tubulin (B).

CONCLUSION

CSA-based PEM films are promising versatile matrices for (i) osteogenic surface functionalization and (ii) modelling healthy or pathological tissues in fields of neurobiology/neuroscience.

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Synthesis of dPG-based Nanogels as Polyvalent Carriers for T Cell Staining

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INTRODUCTION

The recognition of peptide-major histocompatibility complex (pMHC) class I and II molecules by the T cell receptor (TcR) is essential for the control of intracellular pathogens and cancer. This event is defined by the specific interaction of a TcR and a specific pMHCII and represents the first step towards the initiation of efficient T-cell mediated responses to pathogenic threats. In this context, the identification of antigen-specific reactive T cells to be used in cancer immunotherapies has urged researchers to develop improved methods for the isolation and stimulation of antigen-specific T cells.

To date, direct antigen-reactive T cell identification relies on the use pMHC multimeric reagents, which include up to 10 monomeric pMHC units in a single molecule and fluorochromes¹. Higher orders of multimerization, however, should improve the detection of low abundant or low affinity TcR. We seek to design a new platform based on biocompatible materials. Nanogels (NGs) are promising scaffolds for immunotherapeutics that can be tuned in size and shape and have a large surface area allowing further modifications². Furthermore, nanoprecipitation can be performed under mild conditions, making them good carriers for sensitive biomolecules³. We developed a NG scaffold - based on dendritic Polyglycerol (dPG) as carrier units - including cyanine (cy5) dye and Streptavidin (SA). Biot-pMHC are conjugated to the corresponding scaffolds and are used to stain and isolate antigen-specific T cells.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

To allow for strain promoted azide alkyne cycloaddition, polymers were functionalized with azide groups and cyclooctynes, respectively. Furthermore, a carboxylic acid linker was synthesized which can be conjugated to the dPG-azide *via* copper(I)-catalyzed azide alkyne cycloaddition. NGs were synthesized under mild conditions *via* inverse nanoprecipitation and coupled to dye and protein by *in situ* NHS ester formation. Different ratios and concentrations of the macromonomers were screened for inverse nanoprecipitation and show NG formation in the desired size range of 100-250 nm. NGs were analyzed by means of cryo-TEM, NMR, NTA and DLS. Test reactions were performed with Fluorescein-labeled Bovine Serum Albumin (FITC-BSA) was used as a model protein. Streptavidin coupling was quantified by BCA Protein Assay. Binding of the respective scaffolds was checked by Flow Cytometry with antigen-specific and unspcific T cells.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Different ratios and concentrations of the macromonomers were screened for inverse nanoprecipitation and show NG formation in the desired size range of 100-250 nm. For comparison, a high molecular weight polyglycerol (1.4 MDa) was functionalized with carboxylic acids and coupled to Streptavidin accordingly. In order to test the binding of proteins and the efficiency, FITC-BSA was used. As protein coupling could be verified, Streptavidin and cy5-amine were conjugated to the corresponding dPG/NG scaffolds. Furthermore, dPG was modified accordingly as a control. SA conjugates were subsequently incubated with Biot-pMHC, specific and unspcific to the targeted T cells and compared to tetrameric pMHC reagents. Flow Cytometry measurements indicate successful staining of the antigen-specific T cells as well as increase in staining efficiency with increasing valency.

CONCLUSION

Here, we present a novel platform based on high molecular weight dPG or NGs which can be used for staining and isolating antigen-specific T cells. Flow Cytometry measurements with these scaffolds coupled to different biotinylated pMHCs indicate successful staining of antigen-specific T cells. The increase in staining efficiency with larger scaffolds and thus higher valency makes this a useful tool especially with regards to low abundant or low affinity TcR. Activation of the T cells remains to be proven and is currently under investigation.

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Controlled released of risperidone from β -chitosan hydrogels

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INTRODUCTION

Schizophrenia is a common chronic brain disorder¹. Risperidone is used for the treatment of schizophrenia and the most appropriate therapeutic treatment is the controlled release administration covering long therapeutic periods². Chitosan - β -glycerolphosphate (β GP) hydrogels, xerogels injectable formulations have been widely used in the controlled release of different drugs^{3,4,5}. We hypothesized that Chitosan - β -glycerolphosphate formulations may be an appropriate system for the controlled release of risperidone.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

β -chitosans were isolated from squid pens (CHT-S) and cuttlefish bone (CHT-C). Chitosans were characterized in terms of their physicochemical characteristics. Chitosan- β GP formulations were produced by mixing a polymer solution with β GP and risperidone at 4°C and heating the mixture at 37°C during 5h in a Eppendorf tube (pre-formed hydrogels) or in a dialysis membrane in PBS (in-situ hydrogels). Pre-formed hydrogels were lyophilised (xerogels). The release of risperidone from all formulations was studied in PBS at 37°C for 9 days. Risperidone was determined at 278 nm. Xerogels were characterized by SEM, XRD and FTIR-ATR.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chitosan samples showed a similar acetylation degree (around 0.08). CHT-S presented higher viscosity (1.2 vs 0.15 dL/g) and viscosity molecular weight (16 vs 2.76 kDa) than CHT-C sample. The release profiles from the different formulations (pre-formed, in situ and xerogels) in PBS at 37°C are shown in Fig 1. Best controlled release was observed with pre-formed and in situ hydrogels. At 9 days, around 80% of risperidone was released from CHT-C hydrogels while 60-70% was released from CHT-S hydrogels. The initial burst was lower in CHT-S hydrogels. Risperidone release from xerogels was fast with 100% of release at 48h.

Figure 1. Controlled release of risperidone from cuttlefish bone (A) and squid pen (B) chitosan formulations

CONCLUSION

Controlled release of risperidone was successfully achieved with pre-formed and in situ hydrogels. Chitosan Mv modulated the risperidone release.

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3D printing of a reactive hydrogel loaded with catechol containing nanoparticles

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INTRODUCTION

3D bioprinting is a powerful technology for tissue engineering applications, as it allows fabrication of 3D scaffolds with unprecedented flexibility and resolution¹. Hydrogels based on natural polymers are promising for the development of bioinks because of their biocompatibility and the possibility to tune their swelling and mechanical properties to match those of the natural cellular microenvironment². In order to be printed, the gelation kinetics of the hydrogel has to be adjusted to the time scale of the printing process while being compatible with the living cells. Covalent reactions such as Schiff's base formation can be used to crosslink hydrogels. Mussel-inspired catechol functionalities can be used for providing bioadhesion, antioxidant and antiinflammatory properties^{3,4}. In this project, reactive hydrogels based on covalent crosslinking of two natural polysaccharides have been formulated for 3D printing. Additionally, catechol containing nanoparticles are trapped in the hydrogel network and enhance the bioactivity of the material.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

To obtain the hydrogel ink carboxymethyl-chitosan (CMCh) and oxidized hyaluronic acid (HAox) were combined. Homogeneous nanoparticles (NP) (70-100 nm) of two terpolymers with catechol compositions of 2 and 29 molar % obtained by nanoprecipitation were embedded in the hydrogel. The rheological properties of the developed inks, with and without particles, were characterized. To obtain 3D scaffolds, CMCh with NP and HAox, were formulated as two-component system, loaded in two separate syringes and printed using a custom-made static mixing tool. The printed 3D scaffolds were analysed in terms of stability, shape fidelity, mechanical stability. Viability and proliferation of cells seeded on the scaffolds was tested with fibroblasts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fast covalent Schiff's base reaction of the aldehyde groups of HAox and the amine groups of CMCh allowed obtaining a stable hydrogel network. Catechol containing NPs were uniformly distributed in the network and provided mechanical stability to the network. The rheological characterization of the polymer mixtures allowed optimization of the CMCh/HAox ratio and the total solid concentration to obtain printable bioinks. Matching the crosslinking kinetics of the hydrogel precursors (Fig. 1) with printing speed allowed obtaining well-defined strands. Finally, 3D scaffolds with homogenous morphology, shape fidelity and high stability were obtained with good cell viability and proliferation. In the future, NP release kinetics and bioactive properties such as anti-inflammatory and antioxidant will be analysed.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the hydrogel printing process using the static mixing tool.

CONCLUSION

Stable hydrogel bioinks based on natural polysaccharides enriched with synthesized bioactive catechol containing NP, were successfully developed. 3D scaffolds with good mechanical properties that supported fibroblast viability and proliferation were obtained. Static mixing of hydrogel precursors lead to fast yet controlled gelation and allowed reactive printing. We envision that this system can be developed into drug release platforms with bioactive properties.

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Geometric Separation of Detection Levels by a Bioorthogonal Porous Polymer – Introducing Functionality and Increasing Multiplexicity

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INTRODUCTION

In the fields of life science research, environmental analysis or medical diagnostics it is mandatory to screen and analyze a great number of biomolecules. With constantly finding new biomarkers for certain diseases or biomarkers that have an environmental impact there is a huge demand for a platform, that is easy to handle and enables the screening of a large number of parameters in only one run (multiplex assays). It should also provide a good sensitivity to allow for omission of sample enrichment procedures and be as universal as to facilitate an adaption to a variety of biomolecules. Therefore, we used fluorescence coded microbeads and separated them by a layer of a porous hydrogel.¹

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The hydrogel consists of two bioorthogonal components and can be designed to be size selective for different biomolecules, particles or cells. It creates a solution like environment which allows the target molecules to diffuse and interact freely with their specific probe molecule, but also separates the detection levels which enables a compound analysis in k elevations (CAKE). The introduction of this geometric separation adds a further parameter to the multiplex coding. During this novel detection method, the microbeads are not only discriminated by their fluorescence coding but also by their position in one of the k detection levels and can be assigned to a specific probe molecule (cf. Scheme 1 left). The used hydrogel is built up by combining a homobifunctional PEG spacer and a dendritic homomultifunctional crosslinker (cf. Scheme 1 right).^[2] They are crosslinked by utilizing the strain promoted azide-alkyne cycloaddition, which is a bioorthogonal Click reaction. By adjusting the PEG length, the mesh size of the hydrogel pores can be adapted for every layer.

Scheme 1 Exemplary setup with the geometric separation of 2 detection levels. In k_1 small oligonucleotides, in k_2 a medium sized Fab fragment are detected. Larger molecules like antibodies are excluded (left). SPAAC reaction for the built up of the hydrogel (right).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This enables the possibility to detect differently sized molecules which undergo the same affinity interaction in parallel, for example a Fab fragment next to an antibody in a single approach.

CONCLUSION

We combined an existing detection method based on fluorescence microbeads with the functionality of a porous hydrogel to enhance the multiplexicity and to control the diffusion path of the diffusing species.

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Encapsulation of hydrophobic agents into vitamin E-based polymeric nanoparticles

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INTRODUCTION

Polymeric nanoparticle (NP) carriers are a promising approach for drug controlled release since they are capable of reducing the doses and the systemic effects of the encapsulated drugs. One of the major problems of many therapeutic agents is their low bioavailability. Therefore, the encapsulation of these hydrophobic agents into NP could enhance their activity and reduce their toxicity. In this context, we present the development of terpolymer-based NP containing a vitamin E derivative for the encapsulation of hydrophobic drugs [1]. In this way, the nanoparticulate systems will have the antioxidant properties of the vitamin E derivative and the properties of the encapsulated drug.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Terpolymers were synthesized from hydrophilic monomers (vinylpyrrolidone, VP; vinylcaprolactam, VC) and an acrylic derivative of vitamin E (MVE) by free radical polymerization. Self-assembled NP were prepared by the nanoprecipitation method using dioxane and a saline aqueous phase. Drugs (e.g. curcumin, celecoxib, tenoxicam) were encapsulated into the NP in different concentrations (2-20%) and the encapsulation efficiencies were determined. The NP hydrodynamic properties (*i.e.* size polydispersity and surface charge) were studied by Dynamic Light Scattering and Laser Doppler Electrophoresis, respectively. Finally, *in vitro* studies of the NPs were carried out against a murine macrophage cell line.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Amphiphilic terpolymers were successfully synthesized and their chemical composition was confirmed by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance. The terpolymer amphiphilic nature allowed their self-assembly into NP having a hydrophobic core and a hydrophilic shell (Figure 1). Nude and drug-loaded NP were obtained with hydrodynamic diameters ranging from 120 to 170 nm and polydispersity indexes lower than 0.2. Zeta potential values were slightly negative and the encapsulation efficiencies over 30% in all cases. Additionally, *in vitro* cytotoxicity tests confirmed the non-cytotoxicity of the NP systems both, empty and drug-loaded.

Figure 1. Scheme of terpolymer and nanoparticle synthesis

CONCLUSION

The terpolymer-based amphiphilic NP were able to successfully encapsulate hydrophobic molecules with excellent hydrodynamic properties and cell viabilities. Therefore, these systems could be used as delivery vehicles reducing the toxicity of the encapsulated drugs and encouraging its use for drug release purposes.

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Bioactive Hydrogels for Bone Regeneration in Osteoporosis.

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INTRODUCTION

The repair of critical bone defects remains a major clinical orthopaedic challenge, especially in impaired situations like osteoporosis¹ that may require specific strategies. Scaffolds as osteoconductive support should meet certain criteria such as mechanical properties similar to those of the bone repair site, biocompatibility and biodegradability or osteointegration at a rate adequate for remodelling. Additionally, scaffolds can be used as delivery vehicles for active molecules involved in the regeneration process. For this purpose, hydrogels present some advantages² since they could be syringeable, adapt to the defect geometry and provide appropriate environment for cell growth and support. However, they also have important disadvantages², mainly poor mechanical properties and lack of control for the sustained drug delivery.

In the present study, different injectable scaffolds consisting of the combination of a hydrogel (HY) with PLA/PLGA microspheres containing β -estradiol (antiresorptive substance) and BMP-2 (osteogenic factor) were elaborated and tested for bone regeneration in an osteoporotic (OP) rat critical-size defect model.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Microspheres of PLA (Resomer[®] R203S) or PLGA (Resomer[®] RG504, RG755S, RG 858S) containing β -estradiol or BMP-2 were elaborated by simple or double emulsion evaporation technique respectively. The different HYs tested were a supramolecular thermogel composed of Pluronic F127:Tetronic 1307: α -Cyclodextrin (P-T- α CD), a mixture of the Tetronic with sodium alginate (Pronova[®] UP MVG) (T-A), and an alginate gel (A) crosslinked in two steps by ionic gelation. The ¹²⁵I-BMP-2 release profile was determined in vivo by periodically measuring the remaining radioactivity in the defect site with an external probe-type gamma counter. β -estradiol release profile in vitro (mixture of MeOH:water) was determined spectrophotometrically (280 nm). The systems consisting in 100 μ L of one of the above mentioned HYs with PLA/PLGA microspheres (15-18 mg) containing β -estradiol (200-300 μ g) and BMP-2 (4-6 μ g) were assayed in a critical-size bone defect (8 mm \varnothing) created in the calvaria of OP and non-OP female rats. Experimental osteoporosis was induced 4 months earlier by bilateral ovariectomy (OVA) followed by sc administration of dexamethasone-21-isonicotinate (0.3 mg/kg, depot) once every two weeks. Rats were sacrificed 3 months after bioactive HYs administration and bone samples were prepared for histological and histomorphometrical evaluation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Release profiles of the active substances (BMP-2 and β -estradiol) were governed by the microspheres and in general the HYs only produce a slight reduction in the initial release (first days). With P-T- α CD, 70% of BMP2 was released in the first day and 93% in 1 week, and the β -estradiol was released 8% on the 1st day, 50% in 1 week reaching only 60% in 6 weeks. The reparative effect with the BMP-2 was similar in non-OP and OP rats (55-61%). As expected, the combination with β -estradiol improve the bone regeneration only in OP rats. However, the ratio between mature bone and immature bone (MB/IB) was significantly higher in non-OP than OP rats, which indicate a lack of mineralization in the OP animals. With the T-A system, microspheres showing a release more sustained for BMP-2 (34% 1st day, 95% at 6w) and more complete for β -estradiol (18% at 1st day, 83% at 6w) were used, but the results for bone regeneration were not improved. In the crosslinked alginate gel, microspheres with a slower release rate of BMP-2 (14% 1st day and 45% at 6w) and faster for the β -estradiol (47% 1st day, 100% at 4w) were used. A larger residence time of this HY in the defect site was also expected. However, the bone regeneration was not increased.

CONCLUSION

Bone repair observed with the BMP-2 was similar in non-OP and OP rats but the degree of mineralization was lower in the OP ones. β -estradiol seems to improve the effect of BMP-2 in OP but not always significantly. Although different HYs and active substances release profiles were tested, similar bone regeneration was produced in all cases.

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Nanost ructure s Based on Stimuli-res ponsive Polymers: Pro mising Platfor ms for Co ntro lled Drug Delivery

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INTRODUCTIONs

Nanostructures based on thermo- and pH-responsive polymer represent promising smart drug delivery systems.¹ We have decorated surface of iron oxide nanocubes with thermo-responsive polymer (TR-cubes) using a facile and robust photo-polymerization.² By doing so we convert the magneto energy generated by the iron oxide nanocubes into heat that can activate the TR-polymer. The developed TR-cubes are capable of loading a chemotherapy, doxorubicin, and the release of cargo can be triggered using a magnetic hyperthermia (MH) treatment of clinical condition resulted in an excellent in vivo efficacy. In addition, we have also developed pH-responsive crosslinked polymersomes.³ This system features the capability to swell once being dispersed in acidic pH. The swelling can be controlled by adjusting the crosslink density. Acidic pH can trigger the release of loaded Rhodamine B from crosslinked polymersomes. These biomedical nanoplatfor ms hold promise for being used in smart DDS applications.

EXPER IMENTAL METHODS

Thermo-responsive poly(oligoethylene glycol methyl ether methacrylate) was grown from the surface of IONCs pre-functionalized with catechol-based pseudohalide using photo-ATRP to yield TR-cubes which was later investigated as a combinatorial nanosystem that enables the combination of magnetic hyperthermia and chemotherapy in vivo model. Meanwhile, clickable pH-responsive amphiphilic block copolymers were synthesized using the same polymerization technique. A novel pH-responsive crosslinked polymersomes was obtained using Diels-Alder Click Chemistry. The resulting materials were characterized by different means (i.e. light scattering, electron microscopy, etc.).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TR-cubes: a promising nanoplatfor m enables combination between MH and chemotherapy

Crosslinked pH-responsive polymersomes for drug delivery

Figure 1. TR-cubes remains the stability upon DOXO loading and exhibits a heat-triggered release feature which resulted in an excellent in vivo efficacy (Top panel). Cryogenic Transmittance Electron Microscopy of crosslinked polymersome and released of loaded Rhodamine B at different pH.

Thanks to a high stability and heat-triggered DOXO release feature, TR-cubes enable an efficient combination between MH and chemotherapy. In an efficacy study, TR-cubes-loaded with DOXO were eliminating the skin cancer tumor employing a MH conditions already applied in clinic. On the other hand, in a test tube study, the membrane of crosslinked pH responsive polymersomes gets porous once being exposed to an appropriated acidic pH, favouring the diffusion of loaded cargo from the lumen to the media.

CONCLUSION

Thermo-responsive polymeric iron oxides nanoparticles enable the combination of MH and chemotherapy under clinical condition, as here shown for the first time. In parallel, a very simple and straightforward procedure was set to prepare crosslinked pH-responsive polymersome which are able to load and release hydrophilic molecules in a controlled manner. These nanoplatfor ms are of interest for developing advanced drug delivery nanosystems.

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Process Optimization of Drug Loaded Silk Fibroin Nanoparticle Synthesis Using Ionic Liquids

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INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology has shown to bridge the barrier of biological and physical sciences by applying nanostructures and nanophases at various fields of science, particularly in nanomedicine and nano based drug delivery systems, where such particles are of major interest. The promising significance of nanoparticles in the biomedical fields and the need of materials with biocompatibility, biodegradability, and non-toxicity have propelled the efforts for developing and optimizing new materials¹. In this context, silk fibroin (SF) obtained from *Bombyx mori* cocoons has shown to be suitable for synthesis of nanoparticles showing a unique combination of mechanical and biological properties². The aim of this work is to optimize the synthesis of drug loaded-SF nanoparticles using ionic liquids.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The primary process which should be carried out is the sericin removal (degumming) from silk native to obtain silk fibroin, followed by the preparation of SF-ionic liquid (SIL) solution. After heating to 60 °C, the SIL solution is propelled using a peristaltic pump and then sprayed onto methanol by a thermostatically controlled 0.7 mm two-fluid nozzle which uses compressed N₂ to disperse the solution into fine droplets. Finally, the drug (i.e. curcumin, emodin, indomethacin) is loaded into the SF nanoparticles by different experimental procedures. Figure 1 summarizes the process of SF nanoparticles preparation from silk-ionic liquids solutions prior drug loading.

Figure 1. Scheme of SF nanoparticles preparation using ILs

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mean hydrodynamic diameter (Z-average), the PDI and the Zeta Potential of the nanoparticles were measured by DLS a Zetasizer Nano ZS instrument and the results before and after the drug loading are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Physical characterization of the SFNs before and after the drug loading.

	Z-average (nm)	PdI	Zeta Potential (mV)
SFNs (before loading)	157.9 ± 1.5	0.132 ± 0.011	-41.3 ± 0.6
Curcumin ²	166.0 ± 0.1	0.114 ± 0.003	-42.9 ± 2.8
Indomethacin	171.8 ± 1.1	0.140 ± 0.005	-30.4 ± 1.8
Emodin	184.0 ± 4.5	0.182 ± 0.008	-48.5 ± 1.8

Mean values ± SD (standard deviation)

CONCLUSION

Drug-loaded silk fibroin nanoparticles have been successfully synthesized and the process has been optimized using procedures more scalable than methods previously described, using ionic liquids. The results showed that nanoparticle formulations were 155 to 170 nm in diameter with a zeta potential of approximately -40 mV.

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Adipose derived stromal vascular fraction with Extracellular matrix scaffold synergetic effect on skin regeneration

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INTRODUCTION

Adipose tissue easily obtain by liposuction and by-product of cosmetic surgery and contains endothelial precursor cells, endothelial cells, macrophages, smooth muscle cells, lymphocytes, pericytes and pre-adipocytes among others, known as the stromal vascular fraction(SVF).

SVF compartment of mesenchymal tissues is thought to harbor stem cells that display extensive proliferative capacity and multilineage potential.

Extracellular matrix(ECM) provide structural and biochemical support of surrounding cells. Recent study shows SVF and ECM greatly improving wound healing.¹

We using discarded fat, isolated Adipose derived stromal vascular fraction and Extracellular Matrix. To make 3 dimensional structure, we use 3D printer mixed SVF and ECM.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Adipose tissue using 0.075% collagenase digested at 37°C at 220rpm for 30minutes After incubation, the sample centrifuged at 420rpm for 15minutes. The sample was filtered 100/ μ m mesh filter.

After filtering the sample centrifuged at 700G for 5minutes, then discard supernatant and add PBS centrifuged at 700G for 5 minutes again.

Adipose tissue obtained 20ml, washed with PBS to remove blood components. PBS added adipose tissue, homogenized at 12,000rpm for 5min. using homogenizer.

Tissue suspension was centrifuged at 3,000rpm for 5 min. and discarded upper oil layer. Leave the pellet, suspension moved new conical tube, centrifuged at 3,000rpm for 5 min. Discarded suspension, pellet collect new conical tube washed PBS, centrifuged 3,000rpm for 5min. The ECM pellet put in 10ml syringe, loaded 3D printer. We divided 6 groups.(Negative Control, AlloECM, SVF/Matriderm, SVF/Fibrin glue, SVF/Fibrin glue/ECM, Fibrin glue/ECM) Tested 4 times each model. Scar size was 2.5cm² x 2.5cm² injected 5x10⁵ cells/ml SVF.

Dressing was changed every 3 days using tegaderm. After 14 days we sacrificed and examed tissue regeneration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We examined wound healing was 15% faster than control and wound healing rates was increased 57% than control group. We also examined that compatibility and viability of adipose derived ECM contains high ECM. To assess collagen contents, we used masson's trichome staining. We confirmed that SVF/ECM sheet reduced keratin than control group. Next, we confirmed that epidermal thickness of SVF/ECM was 66% higher than control group. We also examined that no immune rejection.

CONCLUSION

We succeed allogenic transplant human SVF/ECM sheet to porcine.

We also found no immune rejection. We already finished animal experiment and approved IRB for application human clinical trials.

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Poster Presentations

Macroporous hydrogel scaffolds for stem cells cultivation: Comparison of microscopical methods SEM and LSCM

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INTRODUCTION

Macroporous synthetic hydrogels based on *N*-(2-hydroxypropyl) methacrylamide (HPMA) copolymers form 3D scaffolds applicable in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine, e.g. for the treatment of traumatic spinal cord injury¹. The morphology of porous hydrogels is usually determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), which provides visualization of porous structure in high resolution.² Nevertheless, the freeze-drying technique required for samples preparation before SEM can affect the hydrogel morphology and is not suitable for observation of growing cell on hydrogels *in vitro*. Thus, laser scanning confocal microscopy (LSCM) was used for morphology characterization of hydrogel together with visualization of scaffold seeded with rat mesenchymal stem cells (rMSC). Moreover, both microscopic methods were compared.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Three types of hydrogels with different porosity were prepared by salt templating of chemically cross-linked HPMA copolymers and labelled by fluorescein. For rMSC seeding the gels were coated by laminin. The viability of cells seeded on the scaffolds and cytotoxicity of these materials were determined by Alamar Blue cell viability kit. The cell growth on hydrogels were observed by LSCM. The gel morphology was evaluated by LSCM and SEM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Various hydrogels differing in the pores structure (0-30, 30-50, 50-90 μm) were prepared. The pore size had significant impact to the growth of rMSC on the scaffold. Figure 1 shows the cells growth determined by LSCM after 5 days of incubation (scaffold - green; cell nuclei - blue). The method of sample preparation, i.e. freezing conditions, for SEM analysis significantly change the morphology of gels.

Figure 1

CONCLUSION

Our data shows the LSCM is useful method to visualize the relevant spatial arrangement within the hydrogels in their native swollen state together with cell growth evaluation. SEM can lead to the failure of gel structure.

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Adipose derived stroma l vascular fraction with Extracellula r matrix scaffold synergetic effect on skin regeneration

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INTRODUCTION

Adipose tissue easily obtain by liposuction and by-product of cosmetic surgery and contains endothelial precursor cells, endothelial cells, macrophages, smooth muscle cells, lymphocytes, pericytes and pre-adipocytes among others, known as the stromal vascular fraction(SVF).

SVF compartment of mesenchymal tissues is thought to harbor stem cells that display extensive proliferative capacity and multilineage potential.

Extracellular matrix(ECM) provide structural and biochemical support of surrounding cells. Recent study shows SVF and ECM greatly improving wound healing.¹

We using discarded fat, isolated Adipose derived stromal vascular fraction and Extracellular Matrix. To make 3 dimensional structure, we use 3D printer mixed SVF and ECM.

EXPERIMENT AL METHODS

Adipose tissue using 0.075% collagenase digested at 37°C at 220rpm for 30minutes After incubation, the sample centrifuged at 420rpm for 15minutes. The sample was filtered 100µm mesh filter.

After filtering the sample centrifuged at 700G for 5minutes, then discard supernatant and add PBS centrifuged at 700G for 5 minutes again. Adipose tissue obtained 20ml, washed with PBS to remove blood components. PBS added adipose tissue, homogenized at 12,000rpm for 5min. using homogenizer. Tissue suspension was centrifuged at 3,000rpm for 5 min. and discarded upper oil layer. Leave the pellet, suspension moved new conical tube, centrifuged at 3,000rpm for 5 min. Discarded suspension, pellet collect new conical tube washed PBS, centrifuged 3,000rpm for 5min. The ECM pellet put in 10ml syringe, loaded 3D printer. We divided 6 groups.(Negative Control, AlloECM, SVF/Matriderm, SVF/Fibrin glue, SVF/Fibrin glue/ECM, Fibrin glue/ECM) Tested 4 times each model. Scar size was 2.5cm² x 2.5cm² injected 5x10⁵ cells/ml SVF.

Dressing was changed every 3 days using tegaderm. After 14 days we sacrificed and examed tissue regeneration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We examined wound healing was 15% faster than control and wound healing rates was increased 57% than control group. We also examined that compatibility and viability of adipose derived ECM contains high ECM. To assess collagen contents, we used masson's trichome staining. We confirmed that SVF/ECM sheet reduced keratin than control group. Next, we confirmed that epidermal thickness of SVF/ECM was 66% higher than control group. We also examined that no immune rejection.

CONCLUSION

We succeed allogenic transplant human SVF/ECM sheet to porcine.

We also found no immune rejection. We already finished animal experiment and approved IRB for application human clinical trials.

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Mechanical stimulation to promote direct reprogramming of glial cells into neurons

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INTRODUCTION

Direct cell reprogramming has gain momentum as a therapy for tissue regeneration. The main strategies to impose cell reprogramming are focused in generate changes at the level of gene expression. However, at the same time cells experience dramatic morphological changes that also have an impact at transcriptional levels. Yet, controlling the cellular morphology by using biomaterial platforms during direct glial reprogramming is unexplored ground.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

In our model, primary astrocytes undergo direct reprogramming to become induce neurons via overexpression of the transcription factor neurogenin-2¹ in which cells display a radical body reshape and a dramatic reduction of the nuclear volume (approx. 4 times). In order to understand the relevance of this changes during reprogramming we impose a particular cell body shape via cell adhesive patterning and hydrogels confinement and changing the nuclear volume by pharmacological stimuli.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Reprogramming efficiency change significantly on confined glial cells whenever nuclear shape is also modified. We demonstrated that nuclear contraction must escort the reprogramming process during at least 3 days for a successful event. However, an extended period of the nuclear compaction phase can put the cells at the brink of cell death. Surprisingly, impairing cell body shrinkage paused cell reprogramming but mRNA levels of downstream genes associated with reprogramming remained upregulated.

CONCLUSION

Our results, links the impact of cell morphological changes with the reprogramming efficiency and cell viability, determining the mechanical limits for a cell to be reprogrammed.

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Hyaluronic Acid-Based Hydrogel Membranes For Cartilage Regeneration

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INTRODUCTION

Autologous Matrix-Induced Chondrogenesis (AMIC) is a surgical technique applied to treat cartilage damage. This methodology combines the marrow-stimulating techniques, microfracture, and the implantation of a biodegradable polymeric matrix which allow cell differentiation and consequently the formation of hyaline cartilage. Examples of commercially available products based on natural polymers included Hyalograft and RST-CarGel®, among others.¹ These two systems are based on the glycosaminoglycan hyaluronic acid (HA) and the polysaccharide chitosan (Ch), respectively. In this study, hydrogel membranes mimicking the extracellular matrix by combining both, HA and Ch are obtained as an alternative to commercial products. HA is incorporated in the membrane by either, physical mixing or covalent crosslinking using metacrylated HA (HAMA). Additionally, amine groups of chitosan chains are ionically crosslinked with a phytic acid derivative, glycerylphytate (G₁Phy) which also can provide antioxidant and osteogenic properties to the hydrogel membranes.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Hydrogel membranes with different porosity were fabricated as follows: Ch membranes with (Ch_s) or without (Ch_{ws}) CaCl₂ salt were prepared by casting solution method and subsequently ionically crosslinked by their immersion into a G₁Phy aqueous solution. Membranes with CaCl₂ salt of Ch/HA_s or Ch/HAMA_s were prepared with a content of 75 % Ch and 25 % HA or HAMA, respectively, following the same protocol. In the case of Ch/HAMA_s membranes, the solution was supplemented with 5% PEGDMA crosslinker and 2% of the photoinitiator Irgacure 2959 respect to HAMA content in order to produce the covalent photo-crosslinking by UV-light. Additionally, a batch of membranes without CaCl₂ salt (Ch/HA_{ws}) and ionically crosslinked with G₁Phy were fabricated. Membrane composition, structural characterization and morphology were studied by EA, TGA, ATR-FTIR, SEM and EDX. Swelling and weight lost were evaluated in PBS buffer and 37°C. Release of G₁Phy in Tris buffer at 37°C was studied by ICP. Viability and proliferation of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) cultured on the membranes were measured by Alamar blue assay.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hydrogel membranes of Ch, Ch/HA and Ch/HAMA were stable under physiological conditions as it was observed after showing a low degradation degree (<14% after two months). Slightly differences in water absorption were appreciated for Ch and Ch/HA with and without salt (hydration degree lower than 100%). However, Ch/HAMA_s showed an increase in water absorption up to 140 % attributed to the formation of a dual crosslinked network and to a higher content of HA in them than in Ch/HA membranes. Thus, it could be suggested that the covalent crosslinked of HA avoids the leach out of HA from the membrane during the washing process. This was in agreement with the data obtained by TGA and EA. On the other hand, the presence of G₁Phy in the membranes was confirmed by ICP-OES, proving the crosslinking between the phosphate G₁Phy groups and Ch amines. Additionally, released profiles showed a sustained and controlled G₁Phy release from the membranes. Differences in surface morphology were observed by SEM which can influence the different cell adhesion behaviour of these membranes. Cell proliferation with MSC showed that all Ch/HA membranes allow cell attachment and support cell viability. Proliferation increased from day 1 to day 14, however, higher proliferation was detected at cells cultured at Ch/HA_{ws} and Ch/HA_s membranes indicating that the presence of HA plays a role.

CONCLUSION

Hydrogel membranes based on HA and Ch with different porosity show proper physicochemical characteristics to support adhesion of MSCs. Biological tests indicate that the HA-based hydrogels are a good alternative as biodegradable polymeric matrix for AMIC application.

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Application of Duck's Feet-derived Collagen and Gallus Gallus Var. Domesticus-derived Demineralized Bone Powder for Bone Tissue Engineering

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INTRODUCTION

Many attempts have been made and suggested to form new bone for skeletal fracture, replace and regenerate diseased, traumatic, or infected bone. Among them, a method of using scaffold in tissue engineering perspective has been widely applied. The basic concept to consider in designing a scaffold for tissue engineering (TE) is biocompatibility and biodegradability. The materials should not cause toxicity, chronic inflammation, and immunological reactions. The answer to this is in materials derived from nature. This is due to their similarity with the extracellular matrix (ECM) and biological macromolecules of a target tissue¹. Collagen is one of the most commonly used nature-derived material in bone tissue engineering and demineralized bone powder (DBP) is also a well-known biomaterial variously used in new bone formation². Herein, the effect of collagen derived from duck's feet and demineralized bone powder originated from Gallus gallus var. domesticus in bone and osteochondral tissue will be discussed. The properties of scaffolds were characterized in chemical and mechanical perspective. The *in vitro* and *in vivo* study was proceeded to confirm the effect of the scaffold in bioactivity, biocompatibility, and biodegradability. Lastly, the feasibility and therapeutic aspects of these materials will be proposed.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

DC and GD DBP were prepared according to our previously reported study³. The DC scaffolds were prepared by applying other biomaterials. GD DBP was incorporated into gellan gum (GG) scaffold to obtain the bone-like model. The properties such as morphology, chemical structure, and mechanical characters of the materials were tested by FTIR, SEM, XRD, TGA and compressive modulus study. In addition, GD DBP was characterized by histological study and bioactivity of GD DBP/GG scaffold was measured by incubating the scaffolds in a simulated body fluid (SBF) solution. In addition, *in vitro* study was analyzed by MTT, RT-PCR, live/dead staining, morphology study by SEM, and histological study by H&E, and Von kossa staining. *In vivo* study was proceeded by implanting scaffolds in a calvarial defect. The result of *in vivo* study was measured by micro-CT and histological staining.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The specific amount of biomaterials (5 μ M EGCG/DC/HAp sponges, 100 μ M Smn/DC/HAp, and 25 μ M Qtn/DC/HAp) incorporated in DC scaffold displayed higher cell proliferation, growth, and differentiation *in vitro*. This represents that the application of other biomaterials can enhance the property of DC by providing enhanced biological environment and attachment sites. Furthermore, *in vivo* shows higher regenerated sites compared to pristine DC. These results suggest that composite of DC and beneficial components can lead to the ideal scaffold for bone tissue engineering.

GD DBP showed rich collagen type-1 and large amount of melanin. Composite of GD DBP and GG showed enhanced mechanical properties. Bioactivity of GD DBP/GG scaffolds displayed a high amount of crystal shape apatite formation on the surface of the scaffolds. The cell viability and mRNA expression was highest in 1% GD DBP/2% GG. The cell attachment was enhanced as GD DBP was incorporated. *In vivo* study displayed larger regenerated site when the defect tissue was implanted with GD DBP/GG scaffold. These results are due to the advantageous effect of rich melanin and collagen in GD DBP.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, DC scaffold and GD DBP which are originated from nature are studied to be beneficial in bone tissue engineering. DC and GD DBP are not only biocompatible and biodegradable but also are sufficient in sources and economical. Therefore, DC and GD DBP are regarded as a prospective candidate to apply in bone tissue engineering.

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Free-standing films created by dip coating using Genipin crosslinking for wound dressing applications

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INTRODUCTION

Free-standing multi-layered films have been investigated as promising candidates in biomedical engineering and wound healing applications.¹ Layer-by-layer (LbL) technique has emerged as a versatile method, based on alternating deposition of biogenic polyelectrolytes for the formation of multilayer coatings.² Our goal was to fabricate thick detachable membranes from alternating layers of chitosan (CHI) and alginate (ALG) using Genipin as a crosslinker to enhance the membranes' properties in order to be used as wound dressings.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The combination of LbL and an automated dip coating device was used to create 100-bilyered films of alternative coatings of CHI and ALG. Films were detached from their substrates and were used either untreated, or underwent additional crosslinking with Genipin. Layer growth and deposition were studied via QCM. Structural and morphological properties were investigated with SEM and AFM while physical properties were studied via swelling experiments and contact angle measurements. In order to address the biocompatibility of the films, the metabolic activity and number of viable cells were studied using NHDF cells in contact with the films. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA (with post hoc Tuckey) and p values of 0.05 or below were considered as significantly different.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Genipin crosslinking, led to relatively smooth, more hydrophobic, thinner films that uptake less water and swell less, having no significant effect on cells compared to non-crosslinked samples. Layer deposition is accelerated through time while both polyelectrolytes seem to equally contribute to the growth. Observed results revealed a more intermingling nature of the two components with no strictly separated layers. Further, cell experiments highlighted the fact that CHI-ALG films did not favour NHDF cell growth and proliferation on top, while no cytotoxic effects were observed.

CONCLUSION

Based on our results, these crosslinked films appear to be appropriate candidates for wound dressings that could additionally facilitate local and controlled release of growth factors and pharmaceuticals for wound healing.

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Fast-forming hybrid sericin hydrogel with tissue-inspired multifunctionality

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INTRODUCTION

In situ-forming hydrogels are versatile and provide a convenient platform for the effective delivery of cells and drugs towards accelerated healing and tissue regeneration (1). Horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-catalysed crosslinking is a promising strategy to fabricate fast forming and biocompatible hydrogels due to its highly tuneable properties by coupling phenol derivatives via decomposition of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) (2). We have previously reported the development of HRP-crosslinked sericin hydrogels presenting important biological activity such as: biocompatibility, biodegradability, antioxidant behaviour, among others (3). In this study, enzyme-triggered crosslinked hydrogels, composed of silk sericin (SS) and marine origin hydroxyapatite (HAp) treated with calcium chloride (CaCl₂) or with iron chloride (FeCl₂) were developed for the first time, to produce multifunctional hydrogels with tissue healing and regeneration capacity.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Silk sericin was extracted from *Bombyx mori* cocoons and HAp was used from cod fish bones. To convert the raw bones into HAp, a calcination process was employed, followed by a treatment with CaCl₂ and FeCl₂ solutions. In the first case the objective is to increase the amount of calcium similar to biological apatites in order to mimic the composition of the human bones. The presence of Fe-doped HAp has previously been demonstrated to improve UV absorption rates, which is relevant when addressing skin related applications. Enzymatic crosslinking sericin-based hydrogel was optimized to a final concentration of SS 14% (w/v), HRP 0.010% (w/v) and H₂O₂ 0.015% (v/v), with CaCl₂ and FeCl₂, both at 1 and 5% (w/v). The developed hydrogels were characterized regarding: the degradation profile (1 and 5% (m/m) during 24h at 37°) under physiological conditions (i.e. phosphate buffer with Protease XIV *Streptomyces griseus*); UV absorption rate was tested between 260-500 nm, to compare the absorbed or transmitted radiation of the solutions which constitute the hydrogel; solutions and hydrogels structures were analysed through Fourier transform infrared absorption (FTIR); and the morphology and distribution of the doped HAp particles were analysed by Scanner Electron Microscopy (SEM) to samples that were previously freeze dried.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fabricated SS hydrogels presented fast-gelation (~3 min.), which was not compromised with the addition of the doped HAp. As expected, the hydrogels presented a higher degradation rate under enzymatic condition (up to 70% after 24h). SEM together with EDS analysis allowed to confirm an homogeneous distribution of the HAp in the SS hydrogel matrix at a percentage of 1%, while a particle deposition was observed when increasing the percentage to 5%. For the SS/Fe-HAp hydrogels UV absorbance analysis allowed to demonstrate additional UV blockage properties which can have potential in skin related applications.

CONCLUSION

Up to the level of our knowledge, this research reports the first steps upon *in situ* sericin-based hydrogels by HRP-catalysed crosslinking, incorporating Ca- and Fe- doped HAp. In this preliminary study the two developed hydrogel platforms showed excellent gelling capacity and adequate degradation profile to be considered for tissue regeneration, in particular in bone and skin contexts. Current *in vitro* cell studies are ongoing to explore and validate this hypothesis, primary cells will be used (i.e. Human Calvaria Osteoblasts and Human Neonatal Dermal Fibroblasts).

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***In vivo* assessment of an antibacterial carboxymethylcellulose gel loaded with chlorhexidine for the prophylactic coating of hernia repair mesh materials**

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INTRODUCTION

Prosthetic mesh infection constitutes one of the major complications following hernia repair surgery¹. As a prophylactic strategy to reduce the risk of developing postoperative infections, an option is to coat the prosthetic mesh with antibacterial compounds before its implant². This study assessed the performance of a carboxymethylcellulose gel (CMC) provided with chlorhexidine (CHX) as a prophylactic coating for polypropylene meshes (PP), using an animal model of *Staphylococcus aureus* mesh infection.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Partial abdominal wall defects (5 x 2 cm) were created in New Zealand White rabbits (n=15) and inoculated with 0.25 mL of *S. aureus* ATCC25923 (10⁶ CFU/mL). Defects were repaired with a lightweight PP mesh (Optilene Mesh Elastic) without coating (n=3), coated with CMC (n=6), or with CHX-CMC (n=6). Fourteen days after surgery, bacterial adhesion to the implant (sonication, immunohistochemistry), host tissue incorporation (light microscopy) and macrophage reaction (immunohistochemistry) were examined. Data collected were compared among the different study groups (Mann-Whitney U test).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

By day 14, observations from the uncoated and CMC-coated implants showed evident signs of infection, displaying parietal bulges, abscesses with purulent material and high bacterial adherence to the implant surface. By contrast, CHX-CMC implants exhibited a strong reduction of these parameters, showing a mesh surface free of bacteria in 5 of the 6 implants (bacterial clearance: 83.3%). In that infected specimen, bacteria were found along the suture line. This interface between mesh and host tissue provides a good niche for bacteria³, promoting infection persistence. This is a risk factor since, in those surgeries involving biomaterials, even few persistent microorganisms are enough to trigger a prosthetic infection⁴. So that, the implant margins represent a vulnerable area and therefore must be carefully protected during the coating process. Histologic evaluation revealed no impairment of the mesh integration into the host tissue caused by the antibacterial gel coating. The macrophage reaction in this experimental group was reduced compared to the other groups, reaching statistical significance when compared to the uncoated materials (p<0.05). The well-known biocompatibility and stability as drug carrier of CMC⁵ aligns with our observations, making this compound suitable for developing antibacterial coatings for medical devices. Together, these findings suggest that the preoperative application of a CHX-CMC coating may be used to reduce the risk of mesh-related infections following hernia repair.

CONCLUSION

The prophylactic coating of hernia repair PP meshes with an antibacterial CMC gel containing CHX provides a local and adequate bactericidal action in the surgical field, causing no detrimental effects on wound repair processes.

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Functional Graphene Nanomaterial-Coated Implants to Enhance Osseointegration

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INTRODUCTION

Dental implants have been clinically used to restore lost teeth. Currently available materials for dental implants include titanium (Ti) and its alloys because of their good biocompatibility, suitable mechanical properties, corrosion resistance, and chemical stability. However, their bio-inertness often leads to poor osseointegration at bone and implant interface, and is often quoted as a disadvantage. In order to improve bioactivities of dental implants, recent some studies have suggested bioactive molecule-loaded implants. On the other hand, the potential of graphene and its derivatives has attracted significant attention as planar culture platforms or porous scaffolds for the differentiation of stem cells towards osteogenic lineages¹⁻³. In the present study, commercially available dental implants coated with reduced graphene oxide (rGO) were prepared, and their potential to enhance osteodifferentiation and osseointegration was investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The physicochemical properties of rGO-coated Ti were characterized by atomic force microscopy (AFM), Raman spectroscopy, and contact angle. The cellular behaviors of human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSCs) on rGO-coated Ti, including proliferation, alkaline phosphatase activity and extracellular calcium deposition, were examined. Moreover, *in vivo* study was conducted to examine the effects of rGO-coated implants on the osseointegration in a beagle dog model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our results showed that rGO-coated Ti can significantly enhance cellular behaviors, including proliferation and osteogenic differentiation, which were confirmed by cell counting kit-8 assay, alkaline phosphatase activity assay and alizarin red staining. Furthermore, it was revealed that rGO-coated implants can significantly increase bone-to-implant contact and intra-thread bone density values.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is suggested that graphene-coated implants are highly effective for osteogenic differentiation and osseointegration, and can be a promising candidate for clinical dental applications.

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Bioengineering microenvironments to study vascularization in bone regeneration

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INTRODUCTION

Bone is a high vascularized tissue so engineering successful novel bone biomaterials must involve not only the formation of new bone tissue but also promote the creation of a microvascular environment resembling the uninjured tissue. In the present work, VEGF is presented tethered to poly-ethyl acrylate (PEA) to induce vascularization. This polymer has been shown to allow solid-phase presentation of GFs through material surface-binding mimicking the stem cell microenvironment and allowing low and controlled dose administration of signals ¹. In addition, the current work is focused in the application of nanovibrational stimulation or ‘nanokicking’ in order to study stretch-activated ion channels, gated specifically by mechanical force in mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs). This mechanical stimulation have shown a strong osteogenic response in two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) conditions ^{2,3}.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Fibrin gel in vitro angiogenesis assay kit was used to evaluate tube formation of HUVECs in 24-well plates. Briefly, after FN (20 µg/ml) and VEGF (25 ng/ml) coatings, cells were seeded at a density of 10,000 cells/cm² complete endothelial cell medium and left at 37 °C overnight. Then, fibrinogen and thrombin were added to the plates which were placed in CO₂ incubator at 37 °C for 1 hour to polymerize. After clotting, fibrin matrix was covered with endothelial complete growth medium that was changed every 48 hours. Plates were nanostimulated during this period by a bioreactor at 1000 Hz and 30nm. After this, immunostaining was carried out for CD31 and phalloidin to evaluate protein expression and tubular formation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Immunofluorescence staining of CD31 expression in HUVEC. Images were captured in a fluorescence microscope. Experiments were carried out in two independent repeats. cVEGF = surface VEGF-coated (25 ng/mL); sVEGF = soluble VEGF (1 ng/mL); + control = ECs media + phorbol myristate acetate (PMA) + angiogenic supplement. Scale bar: 100 µm.

The adhesion molecule CD31, that is expressed in intracellular EC junctions, was analysed (quantification is not shown). Apart from FN surfaces, the rest seem to form vessel-like structures both when treated with nanokick (NK) and when they are not. However, CD31 expression differs depending on the condition. When VEGF is presented bound to FN (cVEGF), CD31 expression is similar to soluble VEGF form (sVEGF) and controls, with no statistical differences between them. In the presence of fibrin gels, sVEGF samples showed a higher CD31 expression although again no statistical difference was noticed regarding cVEGF condition. In all the cases, 2D and in the presence of fibrin gels, NK condition showed an increased CD31 expression compared to non-NK samples.

CONCLUSION

Based on CD31 expression during in vitro angiogenesis assay, it is possible to suggest that NK itself does not seem to induce tubule formation but does appear to increase CD31 expression. We could propose that this will make the cells more receptive to MSCs, but is not affecting vasculature formation per se.

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Biomimetic SrFO/ZnFO-loaded biohybrid scaffolds for osteochondral tissue regeneration

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INTRODUCTION

New cartilage regenerative therapies that combine the use of biomimetic scaffolds and the deliver of accessible and affordable morphogens that drive the regeneration of missing tissues, are urgently demanded in order to treat the degenerative musculoskeletal disorders of articular cartilage¹. In this work we present the development and evaluation as tissue replacements of hierarchical microstructured 3D scaffolds made of PEGDMA/PLGA/TCP covered with a hydrogel of methacrylated hyaluronic acid (MAHA). Bioactive folic acid derivatives (ZnFO, SrFO) were also included in the formulation and their potential to promote the differentiation of human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSC) and proliferation of osteoblasts (hOB) and chondrocytes (hCs) were tested.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

ZnFO and SrFO were synthesized as reported elsewhere². The hierarchical porous scaffolds containing the folate derivatives were fabricated by cryo-polymerization of PEGDMA in the presence of PLGA and TCP. MAHA was deposited and photopolymerized leading to a bilayer scaffold. Microstructure and *in vitro* behaviour of scaffolds were determined by ESEM-EDS and ICP/UV-VIS analysis. Biological action of SrFO/ZnFO in hMSC and their ability to induce cell differentiation were evaluated by determination of ALP activity and specific staining for Ca and GACs deposition. hCs and hOB cells were micro-seeded within the scaffolds. DAPI staining and confocal microscopy observations were used to confirm cell colonization capacity and AlamarBlue assay was used to assess the biocompatibility of the scaffolds. Scaffolds were fixed with formaldehyde, embedded in paraffin and subsequently sliced with a microtome sectioning equipment. The sliced samples were stained with H&E and by using anti-CD44 and D2-40 primary antibodies, for podoplanin and CD44 protein immunohistochemical detection. These proteins are characteristic of the osteoblasts and chondrocytes membranes respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chondrogenic and osteogenic properties of ZnFO and SrFO were confirmed due to their potential to induce hMSCs differentiation as showed by overexpression of ALP kinase, and increased GACs and calcium deposition. Biomimetic scaffolds exhibited hierarchical microstructure and interconnected pores. The materials permitted a high capacity of water retention allowing a sustained release of ZnFO and SrFO for three weeks. ESEM microanalysis revealed that the 3D support swells in hydrated conditions but kept the open porous microstructure favouring hOB colonization in the calcified zones while maintaining a closer and more compact environment in the hydrogel zone facilitating hCs colonization. These results were confirmed by histochemical staining wherein scaffolds slides showed selective cell colonization through the porous structure.

Figure 1. (A) Macroscopic observation of bilayered scaffolds and (B) Haematoxylin and eosin staining slides scaffolds showing osteoblast and chondrocyte cells

CONCLUSION

Hierarchical scaffolds containing bioactive Zn/Sr folates were fabricated by a two step manufacturing process and showed spatially-varying properties with the ability to direct the colonization of different cell populations towards the different parts of the scaffold. In addition, the SrFO and ZnFO derivatives induced the formation of calcified deposits and deposition of cartilage like GAGs by hMSC.

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In Situ Alginate/Hyaluronic Acid Hydrogel with Ultrasound Stimulation for Effective Bone Regeneration

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INTRODUCTION

Ultrasound is described as an acoustic pressure wave which can transfer mechanical energy into tissues and cause beneficial biochemical events at the cellular level. It has been proven systemically by huge efforts using a variety of animal models over several decades. Researchers have believed that the stimulatory effect of ultrasound on bone healing is caused by the promotion of osteogenesis and mineral deposition, etc. at the site receiving stimulation. In our previous study, injectable alginate (ALG)/hyaluronic acid (HA) mixture hydrogels with time-dependent sol-gel transition showed the positive bone regeneration behavior.¹ In this study, we investigated the bone regeneration potential of the ALG/HA hydrogels combined with ultrasound stimulation.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

ALG and HA at different ratios [ALG/HA (w/w): 10/0, 9/1, 8/2, 7/3, and 6/4] were dissolved in PBS. After CaSO₄ powder was evenly dispersed in PBS, each ALG/HA mixture solution was mixed immediately with the same volume of the CaSO₄ suspension. To examine the residence stability of ALG/HA hydrogels, each hydrogel was incubated in PBS and fresh PBS was replaced daily. Mechanical strengths of the ALG/HA hydrogels were measured to obtain the compressive stress and modulus. The extent of bone regeneration by the ALG/HA hydrogels with pulsed ultrasound stimulation was evaluated using a skull defect model of SD rats. The animals were divided into two groups: ultrasound stimulation and non-stimulation groups. Each group was divided into 4 groups according to the ALG/HA ratios [ALG/HA (w/w): 10/0, 9/1, 8/2, 7/3] hydrogels. Bone regeneration behavior was analyzed by micro-CT and Masson's trichrome staining at 4 and 8 weeks after surgery.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Residence stability of the ALG/HA hydrogels slightly reduced with increasing HA ratio in the hydrogel. Compressive modulus of the hydrogels also gradually decreased with increasing HA ratio, but the difference was not significant, except ALG/HA (6/4). The compressive modulus of the ALG/HA (6/4) was low and could not use as a bone regeneration sample. The in vivo animal study result showed that the ultrasound stimulation groups regenerated more effectively bone regeneration than the groups without ultrasound stimulation. Particularly, ALG/HA (7/3) hydrogel group with ultrasound stimulation was found to be very effective in bone regeneration.

CONCLUSION

From the results, we could suggest that the ALG/HA hydrogel with ultrasound stimulation seems to be a promising strategy for the enhanced bone regeneration.

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Bone Regeneration by Plasmid DNA-Loaded Polycaprolactone/Hyaluronic Acid Hybrid Microspheres

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INTRODUCTION

Although bone is a tissue with superior regenerative capacity, massive bone defects created by trauma, tumor resection, or infection are a significant challenge in reconstructive surgery. The needs for microspheres made of synthetic biodegradable polymers have gradually increased with the developments of bioactive delivery systems, tissue engineering, and regenerative medicine. Hyaluronic acid (HA) has attracted interest as a biomaterial for bone regeneration. It plays important roles in biological processes and exhibits osteoinductive/proangiogenic properties as well as leading to cell mineralization. Growth factors releasing from the gene-transfected cells are allowed many advantages including the minimal denaturation during storage or device formulation processes, low cost compared to growth factor itself, and the localized release of growth factors for maximal effectiveness. However, the long-term production of the growth factor from the gene-transfected cells can be prohibited in the body, because of the cell migration and apoptosis. In this study, plasmid pDNA (pDNA; BMP-2 encoding) complex-loaded polycaprolactone (PCL)/HA hybrid microspheres were fabricated as a bone filler material for effective bone regeneration.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

pDNA-loaded PCL/HA microspheres were prepared by a spray/precipitation method using a double nozzle spray. PCL and HA were dissolved in DMSO at 90 °C (10 wt%) and the pDNA (with BMP-2 encoding) complex of N/P ratio 16 was homogeneously suspended in DMSO at a concentration of 2,000 µg/mL. pDNA/PCL/HA mixture solution was immediately transferred in a 10 mL syringe. The solution was sprayed through a double nozzle spray with N₂ purging of 2.5 L/min (outer nozzle) into 70% ethanol solution (coagulation solution) to induce the solidification (precipitation) of pDNA/PCL/HA solution. The precipitated pDNA/PCL/HA microspheres were maintained at coagulation solution for 2 hrs, and then the microspheres were washed in excess water for 24 hrs to remove residual DMSO and ethanol. The pDNA/PCL/HA microspheres were obtained by centrifugation and drying in a vacuum oven overnight. The microspheres were separated in different size ranges (53 ~ 100, 100 ~ 200, 200 ~ 300, 300 ~ 425, 425 ~ 500, 500 ~ 600 µm) using standard testing sieves. The pDNA/PCL/HA microspheres with different sizes were investigated for their potential of the enhanced osteogenic differentiation (in vitro) and bone regeneration (in vivo).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The prepared pDNA/PCL/HA microspheres were seeded with human bone marrow stem cells (BMSCs) as a model cell to demonstrate the feasibility of utilizing these microspheres for bone regeneration. For effective transfection of pDNA into stem cells, the pDNA was condensed by polyethyleneimine-polyethylene glycol copolymer (PEI-PEG) as a non-viral vector. The pDNA complex was effectively loaded into the PCL/HA microspheres and was continuously released from the microspheres for 6 months. From the in vitro cell culture using BMSCs, the pDNA-loaded PCL/HA microspheres showed the effective osteogenesis of BMSCs. From the in vivo animal study using a skull defect model of SD rats, the pDNA-loaded microspheres showed faster bone regeneration behavior than those without pDNA groups.

CONCLUSION

From the results, we recognized that pDNA-loaded PCL/HA microspheres can be applicable for bone tissue engineering applications.

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Influence of different cocoon stifling methods on the properties of silk fibroin biomaterials

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INTRODUCTION

Silk fibroin (SF) is a protein-based material, biocompatible, with excellent mechanical properties, biodegradable and it can be processed in different configurations (dissolutions, hydrogels, films, sponges, particles and nanofibers)¹. There are thousands of research articles that have explored the biomedical applications of SF².

Stifling treatments are applied to silk cocoons in order to kill the pupae, preventing the emergence of moths and allowing to preserve the silk. All of them involve aggressive steps such as exposure to the sun, hot steam from boiling water or dry heat. As none of the scientific articles related to SF biomaterials has previously taken into account this fact, this work explores its consequences, using fibroin films as biomaterial model.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Cocoons of *Bombyx mori* were stifled in different ways: *sun exposure* (5 d), *water vapour exposure* (3h) or *dry heat* (7h at 55°C, 70°C or 85°C). Non-stifled fresh cocoons were considered the negative control. After degumming the silk, SF was dissolved in LiBr 9.3M and dialysed against distilled water. The SF dissolution was used to analyse the protein degradation (SDS-PAGE). SF films (25 µm thick) were produced and, after a water annealing step, ATR-FTIR analysis was carried out (Fourier self-deconvolution of the Amide I peak). Evaluation of the mechanical properties was performed by means of tensile tests. Cell proliferation of human fibroblasts was evaluated using PrestoBlue kit (Invitrogen). Cells were visualised using Molecular Probes® Neurite Outgrowth Staining Kit. SPSS software was used for statistical analyses (ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's test).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The protein degradation increased in all the dissolutions produced from stifled cocoons; SF heavy chains were specially degraded, as well as light chains, although to a lesser extent (fig.1A). This fact generates a series of consequences not only in the secondary structures of fibroin, but also in the mechanical properties and ultimately in the biocompatibility of the materials produced. The β -sheet content was significantly higher when stifling was performed by means of dry heat at higher temperatures (70°C and 85°C), with a reduction in the content of random coil and side chains. Tensile strength and strain at break were detected as significantly lower when this procedure was carried out by means of dry heat (85 °C) and sun exposure. The cell proliferation on the materials was improved by all the different stifling methods, compared to non-stifled cocoons (fig.1B). This improvement was especially accentuated on the films produced from cocoons treated with dry heat.

Figure 1. SDS-PAGE (1A) and proliferation results evaluated at different experimental times (B).

CONCLUSION

The methodology of cocoon stifling should be taken into account in tissue engineering research using fibroin, since this step has been proven to be crucial, affecting the protein degradation, the secondary structures content, the mechanical properties and the biocompatibility of the materials.

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Preclinical model for bone infected: the use of polylactic-co-glycolic acid microspheres added to fixative cements and its role on bone.

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INTRODUCTION

The frequency of primary or revision hip and knee arthroplasty has exponentially increased in recent years. The prevalence rates of hip arthroplasty and knee arthroplasty were 0.83% and 1.52%, respectively, in the United States in 2010.¹ The estimated incidence in 2020 will be 75% in hip and 110% in knee arthroplasty.² Infection and aseptic loosening, hip instability, and periprosthetic fracture are the most important causes of failure. The prevalence of infection in 2003 was ~1.3% in primary arthroplasty and between 2% and 20% in revision surgery. Joint prostheses are an essential element to improve quality of life. However, prostheses may fail due to several factors, including the most frequent cause, *S. aureus* infection. The identification of new fixing bone cements with less reactivity on bone tissue and an adequate response to infection remains a primary challenge. The aim of this study is to evaluate the response of bone tissue in rabbits after introduction of a hydroxyapatite-coated titanium rod with a commercial fixative cement (Palacos®) compared to a modified experimental cement (EC) containing polylactic-co-glycolic acid (PLGA) microspheres in the presence or absence of contaminating germs treated or not with antibiotics.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

This study used 20 New Zealand rabbits (2.5–3 kg) divided into 4 groups, depending on the cement (commercial or experimental) and the antibiotic (vancomycin, daptomycin or linezolid) used to control a bone infection caused by *S.aureus*. The commercial cement is Palacos® R and the experimental cement has been achieved by adding PLGA microspheres to the solid phase of Palacos® R cement. A novel histological staging method based on bone histoarchitecture has been used. Animals were managed in accordance with the current International Regulations on Experimental Animals (609/86/EEC and ETS 123) at the Animal Research Center of the University of Alcalá.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A histological method, based on bone architecture damage, was proposed to evaluate from 1 to 9 the histological results and the response of the infected tissue. If we compare the control groups, that is, the rod groups without contaminating with contaminated rods, we observed that in the groups of cement without PLGA, the presence of bacteria contributes to a structural loss of the bone. However, in the groups in which cement has been used supplemented with PLGA, it seems that PLGA protects the bone from infection thus maintaining the structure of the bone itself, even in the presence of bacteria (P<.01). In groups of contaminated rods, when we doped PALACOS cement with antibiotics, the used antibiotics, protected the bone from the action of them, maintaining better bone structure, especially when Vancomycin or Daptomycin were present. (P=.04). The treatment with Linezolid seems to be clearly less effective against this type of bacteria and fails to protect the structure of the bone reaching values as high as the rod with contaminated control PACACOS. When the rod is cemented with PALACOS / PLGA, it seems that the PLGA is sufficient to maintain bone structure regardless of the efficacy of the different antibiotics against the type of bacteria used for the infection.

The macrophage increased with the use of EC with PLGA microspheres against the Palacos® commercial cement, including the non-contaminated and contaminated groups. The percentage of macrophages varied exclusively depending on the antibiotic used, and was higher in the vancomycin groups (P=.04).

CONCLUSION

The new formulation of PALACOS cement with the introduction of microspheres of PLGA, induces a clear and significant preservation of the bone structure before infection and opens a pathway for the maintenance and prolonged release of local antibiotic.

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Paclitaxel-loaded polylactide/polyethylene glycol fibers with long-term antitumor activity as a potential drug carrier for local chemotherapy

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INTRODUCTION

Local recurrence of solid tumors following surgical resection remains a big challenge in oncology. Anticancer drugs like paclitaxel¹ were previously loaded to nanofibrous carriers composed of biocompatible materials, e.g. polylactide (PLA)² or polyethylen glycol(PEG)³. Paclitaxel (PTX) is an antitumor agent with poor solubility in water and is effective in treatment of ovarian and breast cancer⁴. In this work, we report the preparation of PTX-loaded PLA and PLA-PEG fibrous nanomaterial for local drug delivery.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The degradation of PLA materials, PTX release kinetics and stability were determined *in vitro* and analysed by HPLC/UV method, and Alamar Blue Assay. Cytotoxicity of released PTX was tested on four human cell lines: neuroblastoma (SH-SY5Y, UKF-NB-3), breast adenocarcinoma (MCF-7), and prostate carcinoma (LNCaP). *In vivo* experiments were performed on adult male nude mice with subcutaneous HT1080 fibrosarcoma. All results were analysed by ANOVA and $P < 0.05$ was considered significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sensitivity of cell lines for released PTX (1 and 10%) was different and increased from MCF-7, LNCaP, SH-SY5Y to UKF-NB-3 cells. PTX release in cell culture was enhanced by PEG which lead to higher toxicity of the nanomaterial, 35kDa PEG being the most effective. In *in vivo* tests, the recurrence of fibrosarcoma in mice was significantly lower in group treated with PLA-PTX fibres.

CONCLUSION

PLA fibrous material can serve as a depot for PTX. PTX enhanced by PEG diffuses for several days and keeps its toxicity both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. PLA-PTX fibres show a potential for localized chemotherapy.

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HPMA copolymer-bound ritonavir as nanotherapeutics with suitable properties for advance anticancer therapy

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INTRODUCTION

Ritonavir (RIT) is widely used antiviral drug that acts as HIV protease inhibitor with emerging potential in anticancer therapy.¹ RIT also causes mitochondrial dysfunction leading to decrease ATP production and reduction of caveoline I expression, which can affect cell migration and tumour development. *N*-(2-hydroxypropyl)methacrylamide copolymer carrier (pHPMA) bound RIT (pRIT) was synthesized to increase the drug solubility, prolong drug circulation in the blood and enable enhanced accumulation and controlled RIT activation in solid tumours². Here, we report the synthesis of pRIT differing in the drug content and study of pRIT internalization and impact to mitochondrial dysfunction and caveoline I expression³.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

In vitro pRIT internalization, endocytic pathways and colocalization with organelles were evaluated using laser scanning confocal microscopy and flow cytometry. Expression of caveoline I was detected by western blot and ATP was measured by luminescence based assay.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We demonstrated that polymer-bound RIT enhanced the cell internalization of pRIT conjugates, differing in RIT content from 4 to 15 wt%. pRIT with 11 wt% showed the most effective penetration properties. pRIT is internalized to the cell using caveoline and clathrin dependent endocytic pathways in contrast with pHPMA, which preferentially uses only clathrin mediated endocytosis. Moreover, we showed colocalization of pRIT with mitochondria and decreased ATP production.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated polymer RIT conjugates as a promising advanced polymer carriers suitable for antitumour therapy and potential mitochondrial drug delivery system.

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Designing reverse thermo-responsive polymeric nano-shells

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INTRODUCTION

The approach typically pursued in the past to render nano-particles with the ability to respond to small environmental differentials, did so by grafting reverse thermo-responsive (RTR) chains onto the surface of various nano-particles or by blending them with a non-responsive matrix. Expectedly, these nano-sized materials exhibited a very limited ability to respond to temperature changes since a non-responsive component was part of the system^{1,2}.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

This work presents reverse thermo-responsive poly(ethylene oxide)-poly(propylene oxide)-poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO-PPO-PEO) triblock based hollow nano-structures. These supramolecular architectures are formed via intra-micellar cross-linking, while these constructs were analysed with DLS and electron microscopy methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hydrodynamic diameter versus temperature plots for FDMA and PF2DMA (two coupled F127 triblocks) nano-shells

Hydrodynamic diameter of temperature and pH responsive nano-shells

The uniqueness of these novel nano-sized constructs stems from their ability to display a remarkable and reversible change in size (hundreds of times by volume - up to 900 times), within a narrow temperature interval. Due to their RTR nature, these nano-shells displayed a remarkable and reversible change in size, ranging from nano-sized to micrometric structures. Since the shape and size of the micelles depend on the temperature, nano-shells having various geometries, e.g. spherical or rod-like, were "sculptured" by performing the cross-linking reaction at different temperatures. Also, these nano-shells were rendered with additional features, such as biodegradability and pH-responsiveness.

CONCLUSION

Hollow nano-structures of F127 end-capped with different functional groups exhibited interesting properties, which have potential to be utilized in the biomedical field, for example as "smart" vehicles for drug and gene delivery.

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NEW UCST-TYPE THERMORESPONSIVE HYDROGELS AS ARTIFICIAL GELATIN

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INTRODUCTION

The free radical polymerization of (N-acryloyl glycinamide) (NAGA), a water-soluble monomer, yields polymers (PNAGA)s that exhibit reversible gel \leftrightarrow sol transition of the Upper Critical Solution Temperature (UCST) in aqueous media without volume and shape modifications. The transition temperature depends on macromolecule molar mass and concentration [1]. We previously took advantage of these factors to adjust the transition temperature slightly above body temperature in order to allow parenteral injection of a warm drug-PNAGA sol that gelled very rapidly *in situ* at body temperature. It was shown that some PNAGA gels fulfilled many of the other characteristics required to administrate and progressively deliver neutral or ionic and hydrophilic or hydrophobic drugs [2-4]. In attempts to introduce hydrophobicity in NAGA-based polymers, we took advantage of copolymerization to extend the family of thermoresponsive PNAGAs. New copolymers were synthesized by free radical polymerization of mixtures of N-acryloyl glycinamide and of its N-acryloyl L-alaninamide (NALALA) analog in various proportions. The present work explores the structures and several properties of these new polymers and considers the possibility of using such copolymers as injectable hydrogels exploitable as sources of smart therapeutic devices.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

NALALA was synthesized using the method applied to NAGA [2]. Homo and copolymers were synthesized by free radical polymerization in water as friendly solvent. Molecular masses were controlled using isopropanol as the transfer agent as reported in [1]. Optically active copolymers with 10, 25, 50, and 75 % NALALA-based units were obtained. They were characterized by ¹H and ¹³C-NMR, FTIR, Dynamic viscosity, Circular Dichroism (CD) and gel \rightarrow sol transition temperature by the reverse tube method. Hydrophilic Methylene Blue dye and hydrophobic Risperidone were used as model compounds to evaluate the potential for application in sustained drug delivery.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

NMR and CD data showed that structures corresponded to copolymerization of monomers with similar reactivity that yielded random copolymers. At 5% w/v copolymer concentration, and slightly above, all the investigated copolymers exhibited UCST-type gelation with molecular weight and concentration-dependences of the gel \leftrightarrow sol transition. The gels were more or less cohesive and consistent depending on the copolymer composition and concentration. Some of the copolymers exhibited a sol \rightarrow gel transition below 50°C that may allow injection under warm sol form as in the case of PNAGAs. The release of the Methylene Blue hydrophilic model was diffusion-controlled whereas that of Risperidone was linear and thus solubility-controlled.

CONCLUSION

Some of the investigated PNAGA-*co*-NALALA copolymers led to gelling and sol \rightarrow gel transition exploitable in the field of biomaterial applications but only after *in vivo* investigations.

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Semisolid formulation with microparticulated functional ingredients

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INTRODUCTION

Chitosan is a natural polymer with functional characteristics such as biodegradability, biocompatibility, mucoadhesion or antioxidant properties¹. Chia is an herbaceous plant that belongs to the *Lamiaceae* family. Chia seed oil has interest due to the rich pool of natural antioxidants that contains². The aim of this study is to obtain particulate systems with functional ingredients and cosmeceutical interest based on chitosan, which are highly demanded in cosmeceutical market.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Chitosan was first purified and characterised in terms of its physicochemical properties (ash content, humidity degree, deacetylation degree, viscosimetry, molecular exclusion chromatography) and functional properties (antioxidant activity). Once the chitosan was characterized, chia oil was encapsulated using chitosan and other biopolymers to form a coacervation complex and techniques such as spray-drying or lyophilisation were used to dry-off the sample. The encapsulated were characterized by optical microscopy, SEM, encapsulation efficiency and *in vitro* release studies. Different semisolid formulations were prepared with the chia oil encapsulated and using natural ingredients. The characterization of the semisolid formulations was dispersion studies, pH, viscosity and stability of the emulsion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results showed a chitosan with the characteristics needed to be used as a polymeric matrix. Chitosan-loaded particles, that improve the stability and prevent the oxidation of chia oil, allowed a controlled release of the active principle (Figure 1). A stable semisolid formulation with the microparticles and natural ingredients has been obtained with a pH between 5 and 5,5 (skin pH) and the emulsions were stable at least for one year.

Figure 1. In vitro release profile of microencapsulated chia oil in chitosan at 37°C in PBS pH 7.2 and 100 rpm (N=3± SD).

Table 1. pH and rotational viscosity values of the different semisolid formulations.

	Initial pH	Final pH	Viscosity (cP)
LC1	2,2	5,34	2739,38
LC2	2,30	9,80	1812,90
LC3	2,00	7,20	2514,00
LC4	1,54	5,33	2739,38
LC5	1,54	5,25	2253,86
LC6	2,17	5,06	3215,38
LC7	2,48	5,24	2944,06
CH1	4,70	5,87	4019,90
CH2	4,30	5,93	4180,20

CONCLUSION

A stable dermocosmetic semisolid formulation has been obtained with the physicochemical characteristics suitable for its possible use in the prevention of pressure ulcers. The incorporation of microparticulate systems that provide beneficial properties for skin health has been necessary.

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Novel multifunctional nanoparticles for drug delivery and nanocrystallization

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INTRODUCTION

The applications of lipid cubic phases (LCP) have experienced explosive development during the recent years. Important LCP application was originally suggested by Prof. Kare Larsson¹, who proposed to make drug delivery nanoparticles by fragmentation of the bulk LCP. Biocompatible LCP based multiphase nanoparticles (cubosomes and hexosome derivatives) permit enhanced drug loading for the purpose of uptake of therapeutic biomolecules such as peptides, proteins and plasmid DNA. Investigated nanoparticles for delivery of peptides, proteins and plasmid DNA is designed in the context of neuroregenerative therapy. Nonlamellar lipid mixtures are used for nanoparticle formation via self-assembly.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The structure of the fluorinated polyoxazoline-based nanoparticles, revealed by structural investigations based scattering methods (SAXS/WAXS and SANS). Micro structure and dynamic of the nanoparticles segments are analysed by different high resolution NMR spectroscopy methods (such as ¹H, ¹³C, ¹⁹F Diffusion and Relaxation Experiments).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main method of sample preparation is self-assembly, including continuous or stopflow rapid mixing. Combination of NMR and SANS method allow to characterize the sizes of core and of whole particles, aggregation number, volumes of the core and shell, solvent amount in the core.² The structural change for the core of the nanoparticles with increasing solvent content is more evident from the corresponding pair-distance distribution function (PDDF) curves. The PDDF patterns from solutions with 20 to 50 vol % of solvent exhibit a skewed bellshape, a typical feature of ellipsoidal particles. From the concentration dependence we can conclude that increasing the solvent content decreases the length of the core of ellipsoidal nanoparticles whereas asymmetry of the whole core increases. The presence of a larger amount of solvent results in swelling and distortion of the interior of the nanoparticle.

CONCLUSION

Investigation of the internal structure of the nanoparticles is especially useful for investigation of the loading of proteins in LCP since the key parameters of the protein in water and in lipid membrane can differ significantly. Once a membrane protein enters in the lipid membrane, its probability for crystallization increases substantially.

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Thermoresponsive polymeric systems studied by NMR Spectroscopy

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INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, design and development of stimuli-responsive polymers is an issue of the great importance due to the wide range of potential applications in control drug and gene delivery systems, bioseparation, tissue engineering. Stimuli-responsive polymers or so called smart polymers are materials which can change significantly their physical or chemical properties according to the influence of external stimuli¹. The most frequently used stimuli are change of temperature, pH, light irradiation, ionic strength or addition of chemical agents. When the stimulus is applied a smart polymer undergoes strong conformational changes and transit from coil to globule like state.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Recently, copolymers based on poly(2-alkyl-2-oxazoline)s were highly acknowledged due to their versatile properties in drug, protein, radionuclide or gene delivery². Therefore, thermoresponsive amphiphilic poly-oxazolines copolymers were newly synthesised and studied by high resolution Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) Spectroscopy. It is well known that ¹H NMR spectra in combination with spin-spin relaxation times T₂, ¹H-¹H NOESY spectra and PFG NMR self-diffusion measurements provide valuable information about structure of the polymer in solution as well as conformational changes of polymer chains. Furthermore, with help of NMR spectroscopy is possible to investigate the interactions between polymer and solvent, dynamics of polymer segments and solvent molecules in solution during the phase transition.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Triblock copolymers based on a statistical thermoresponsive poly(2-isopropyl-2-oxazoline) (iPrOx), hydrophobic poly(2-butyl-2-oxazoline) (BuOx) central block with terminal hydrophilic blocks poly(2-methyl-2-oxazoline) (MeOx) with different block ratios were studied with the temperature increase. The separation fraction was used for characterization mobility of different polymer groups while the temperature ascended. The separation fraction obtained from the NMR data allowed us to identify mobility of each polymer block separately and thus, provided us with the idea of the whole nanoparticle formation process. Generally, during temperature increases, polymer nanoparticles form in a process starting with single molecules that become loose aggregates and ends with the formation of core-shell like compact structures. Understanding of nanoparticle formation process as well as drug-loading process is extremely important for drug delivery systems.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, there were determined the effects of each block on nanoparticle formation. It has been shown that the different BuOx-iPrOx blocks determine the character of the nanoparticle formation process, whilst iPrOx/MeOx ratio determines the value of the phase separation temperature.

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Synthesis of Sugar and pH -Responsive Triblock Terpolymers Based on Polyesters and Phenylboronic Acid via ROP and Click Chemistry and Controlling their Aqueous Self-Assembly into Multicompartment Micelles

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INTRODUCTION

Self-assembling amphiphilic block copolymers are effective vehicles for toxic and hydrophobic drugs delivery. Recently much affords have been made to design biocompatible and biodegradable amphiphilic block copolymers as a smart vehicles to solubilize, retain and release the drug in response to many stimuli's for example light, enzymes, sugars, acidic cytosolic or endosomal conditions in tumour cells. Depending on the relative block length of linear amphiphilic AB diblock copolymer four most typical nanostructures can be formed in selective solvent, star-like micelles, crew-cut micelles, cylindrical micelles or the vesicles (polymersoms). With growing complexity of the polymer architecture (additional third noncompatible block C incorporated into AB diblock copolymer in fashion as a linear ABC triblock terpolymer or as a miktoarm star ABC triblock terpolymer), increases tremendously the complexity and the structural variability of the self-assembled nanostructures¹. Block copolymers containing phenylboronic acids (PBA) reversibly binding biologically relevant molecules such as polyols including, saccharides, catechols and other cis-diols has recently became the subject of great interest. Such dynamic covalent ester bonds open up wide range of promising applications in sensing of glucose and local pH, controlled release of insulin and other therapeutics².

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

NMR spectra were recorded on Varian SYSTEM 300 spectrometer at 25°C in CDCl₃. SEC analyses were performed on an Agilent Technologies 1100 Series apparatus fitted with a UV/vis Diode Array Detector (DAD) and a Differential Refractometer. A series of three PL-gel (polystyrene-divinylbenzene) columns (Polymer Laboratories, UK) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) (flow rate 0.7 mL/min) were used. Light scattering measurements were performed on ALV setup (Langen, Germany) equipped with a 22 mW He-Ne laser operating at the wavelength $\lambda = 632.8$ nm, an ALV CGS/8F goniometer, an ALV High QE APD detector, and an ALV 5000/EPP multibit, multitaup autocorrelator. Cryo-TEM was performed using field emission cryo-EM (JEOL JEM-3200FSC), which was operating at 300 kV voltage. Images were acquired in bright field mode and using zero loss energy filtering (omega type) with a slit width of 20 eV.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We developed a micellar platform composed of terpolymers for the encapsulation of diol containing drugs, we used Alizarin red S (ARS) as a model fluorescent drug. For this purpose, a series of terpolymers composed of poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO, block A), poly(α -propargyl- ϵ -caprolactone) (PPCL, block B), and poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL, block C) with a blocked, i.e., BC or CB, block copolymer sequence in the polyester segment was synthesized. The propargyl groups on block B were further modified with 2-azidomethyl(phenylboronic) acid pinacolate (PBA) by standard CuAAC procedure for ARS encapsulation. We then investigated how sequence of terpolymers can affect the self-assembly process and stability of micelles as well as the drug delivery, i.e., ARS, by different stimuli, pH or sugar concentration. Light scattering and cryo-TEM were used to study the structure of different terpolymer micelles. Our results showed micelles with ABC sequence to have better stability over those of ACB as reflected by a deprotection or oxidative deboronation of PBA. The zero order controlled and sustained release profiles for ARS-loaded ACB and ABC micelles have been found respectively. The drug-release rates from micelles strongly depend on solution pH and sugar concentration. Stability and micelles structure are key parameters that can influence the performance of polymeric micelles as nanodrug carriers. Based on these results, we suggest ABC micelles to have improved characteristics for ARS delivery compared to ACB micelles.

CONCLUSION

Sugar- and pH-responsive micelles of ABC and ACB triblock terpolymers with phenylboronic ester as the sensitive linkage with drugs were successfully prepared and characterised in detail using scattering techniques (SLS and DLS), microscopy (cryo-TEM), and fluorescence spectroscopy. Our results show the block sequence to have great influence on the drug release profile.

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Simultaneous dual release of hydrophobic drugs from PHBV microparticles/ κ -carrageenan composite hydrogel

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INTRODUCTION

Currently the development of new drug delivery systems has been intensified. Among many types of polymeric systems that are used as drug carriers, hydrogels have attracted considerable interest¹. Despite the favourable characteristics of hydrogels, there are still certain limitations for medical applications. For example, for the hydrogel-based drug delivery system, the homogeneity and quantity of drug loading into hydrogels is often very difficult, particularly in the case of hydrophobic drugs². In order to exploit the advantages of hydrogels for drug delivery and address their limitations in delivering incompatible hydrophobic drugs, different strategies have been adopted to modify the hydrogels, as the incorporation of micro or nanoparticles^{3,4}. Under this context, the aim of this work was to develop a novel composite hydrogel for simultaneous hydrophobic drugs delivery. Dual drug encapsulation of the anti-inflammatory ketoprofen (KTP) and of the antibiotic mupirocin (MU), was obtained in poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) microparticles (PHBV MPs) and then incorporated into κ -carrageenan/locust bean gum hydrogel and its potential use as a drug delivery system was determined.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

κ -carrageenan (κ C) and locust bean gum (LBG) were used for the preparation of hydrogel, KCl was used to promote the gelation of κ C. PHBV MPs were prepared using emulsification/solvent evaporation method. The surface morphologies, particle size, zeta potential and porosity, swelling assays in PBS at 25°C and 37°C, in vitro release studies of PHBV MPs and PHBV MPs loaded hydrogels and biocompatibility assays with fibroblast cell line (NIH 3T3) were realized to determine their potential as drug delivery system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PHBV MPs had a size of $1.0 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}$ and a zeta potential of -14.1 mV , the negative surface charge is attributed to the presence of free carboxylic acid groups at the chain ends of the PHBV polymer exposed in the particle surface. Porosity analysis indicated that the PHBV MPs exhibited a surface area of $3.36 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$, pore volume of $0.0046 \text{ cm}^3\text{g}^{-1}$ and pore size of 5.54 nm indicating a mesoporous material. The morphology of the composite hydrogels shows that the PHBV MPs were completely embedded within the matrix. The swelling ratio (SR) of the hydrogels with and without PHBV MPs increased with increase of the temperature from 25 °C to 37 °C showing a swelling behaviour sensitive to temperature. For κ -carrageenan hydrogel of SR increased from 0.18% to 223.5% and for PHBV MPs loaded hydrogel increased from 0.5% to 183.6%. Also, the incorporation of PHBV MPs into hydrogels produced a decrease of SR, this is attributed to the hydrophobic nature of PHBV. This may be due to the fact that the increase in temperature increases the mobility of the chains and more water molecules can penetrate the network, resulting in a higher swelling capacity. In vitro release of KTP and MU was evaluated for PHBV MPs and PHBV MPs loaded hydrogel at 37 °C. In 4 h, 100% of KTP and MU were release from PHBV MPs. On the other hand, 100% of KTP and MU were release in approximately 72 h. Therefore; the presence of the hydrogel matrix surrounding the MPs allows a longer elimination of drugs. To evaluate the potential application as drug delivery system, the viability of the fibroblast 3T3 on the hydrogels was assessed with the MTT assay. The results indicate that the composite hydrogel is biocompatible.

CONCLUSION

A composite hydrogel formed by PHBV microparticles loaded in κ -carrageenan/locust bean gum hydrogels for dual delivery of KTP and MU was developed. The temperature-sensitive composite hydrogel showed a release of both drugs over 120 h. Thus, the combination of a polysaccharide-based hydrogel and PHBV MPs represents a potential controlled drug delivery system.

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Characterization and antioxidant activity of catechol-chitosan/ β -Lactoglobulin nanoparticles

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INTRODUCTION

The development of bio-adhesive materials is an emerging topic because of their potential application as wound healing patches and tissue engineering. A classic example of bio-adhesive molecules is represented by the set of proteins produced by marine mussels to anchor foreign surfaces in seawater, in which the main component is the catecholic amino acid.¹ Different bio-adhesives catechol derivatives have been developed over the last decade.² In addition, catechol groups have the capacity to inhibit oxidative damage by scavenging free radicals and chelating active transition metals.³ Examples of polymeric-protein mussel mimics include the catechol derived chitosan.⁴ In this research, chitosan-catechol nanoparticles incorporating β -Lactoglobulin have been obtained and characterized. The β -Lactoglobulin is a major whey protein of milk of different mammalian species, which is utilized as a functional additive in food applications due to its excellent organoleptic and functional properties, such as antioxidant activity.⁵

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Chitosan-catechol (Cs-Ca) conjugates were synthesized using standard N-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-N'-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) chemistry. Catechol content of the conjugates was calculated by ¹H NMR and UV-Vis measurements. To produce the nanoparticles, certain volumes of sodium tripolyphosphate (TPP) solution were gradually added to Cs-Ca solution under magnetic stirring. The hydrodynamic diameter and zeta potential (ζ) of the nanoparticles were determined by dynamic light scattering and the morphology was studied by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM). Milk protein β -Lactoglobulin (β -Lg) was incorporated to the nanoparticles suspension during the synthesis and the association efficiency (AE) was calculated based on the absorbance of the supernatant at 280 nm. The ATR-FTIR spectra were collected to describe the interaction between the polysaccharide and the protein. The radical scavenging activity (RSA) of the nanoparticles was evaluated by DPPH• experiments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cs-Ca conjugates were synthesized by the creation of amide bonds between a carboxylic acid groups in hydrocaffeic acid (HCA) and a primary amine groups in Cs. Successful Cs-Ca conjugation was characterized in the ¹H NMR spectra, showing the aromatic ring protons of the catechol from 6.61 to 6.76 ppm. UV-Vis spectroscopy was also used to determine the degrees of catechol substitution, which correspond to 4.8 and 10.6%, depending of the experimental conditions. It was possible to produce Cs-Ca nanoparticles including β -Lg with quasi-spherical shape. According to the DLS measurements, the average hydrodynamic diameter of the particles was 190 nm (PDI = 0.36) with ζ potential of +40 \pm 3 mV. The ATR spectrum displays features of both Cs and β -Lg, which confirmed the presence of the protein in the material. Catechol groups have an important role in the antioxidant properties of the materials due to its radical scavenging capacity. However, the total RSA is attributed to the synergic effect of the antioxidant capacities of the polymer and the β -Lg. After 240 minutes of analysis, the RSA of the Cs-Ca/ β -Lg nanoparticles reached 80%.

CONCLUSION

Polymeric nanoparticles based on chitosan-catechol incorporating β -Lg were produced using TPP as crosslinking agent. The materials have quasi-spherical morphology in aqueous suspension with hydrodynamic diameter of about 190 nm and positive surface charge. The nanoparticles showed high RSA attributed to the synergistic antioxidant effect of the compounds. The results demonstrated that the catechol groups were efficiently attached to the polymeric materials, which would provide interesting bio-adhesive properties that will be characterized in future experiments.

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Bilayer coating of vascular stent with electrospun bioactive nanofibers for the prevention of restenosis and thrombosis

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INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular diseases are the first cause of death in developed countries. These diseases are mainly due to atherosclerosis, a systemic arterial pathology responsible for stenosis and thrombosis¹. The angioplasty stenting is often applied to treat this pathology; however, restenosis occurs in 30% of cases. The objective of this work is to coat stents by electrospinning technique with two layers of nanofibers based on biopolymers (Figure 1a): a first layer with antithrombotic properties to prevent blood coagulation *intra lumen* and a second drug loaded layer to deliver simvastatin (SV) to the vessel wall, for preventing restenosis.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Electrospinning was used to coat NiTiNOL stents with nanofibers (NFs) (Figure 1b and c). The first NFs intraluminal layer is based on an anticoagulant sulfonated chitosan (CHTs)² and the second one is based on chitosan (CHT) and anionic cyclodextrin polymer (PCD)³ forming a polyelectrolyte complex CHT/PCD loaded with SV (CHT/PCD-SV NFs). The electrospinning of both types of NFs was optimized in terms of precursor polymers solutions and process parameters through physico-chemical characterization (SEM, TGA ...). Crosslinking of CHTs NFs using genipin (gnp) was performed and their stability in aqueous media was studied. Different thicknesses of the outer layer were obtained by varying the electrospinning time. The hemocompatibility and antithrombotic CHTs properties of the intraluminal layer were studied by hemolysis and adequate coagulation tests respectively. The *in vitro* SV release study in PBS (Phosphate Buffered Saline, pH 7.4) from the CHT/PCD-SV NFs was followed in dynamic conditions (35 mL/min).

Figure 1: Bilayer structure of the coating (a), picture of the coated stent (b) and SEM observation (magn. x30) (c)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The two bioactive nanofibrous layers were first characterized separately. Crosslinking of CHTs nanofibers using genipin led to a structural stability of NFs in aqueous media. Genipin crosslinked NFs showed no cytotoxicity and good hemocompatibility. The anticoagulant effect of CHTs layer was also demonstrated. The *in vitro* release profile of SV from the CHT/PCD/SV NFs layer was found dependant on the NFs thickness. Prolonged release of SV up to 6h in PBS was obtained thanks to PCD in the NFs matrix. Adherence and mechanical resistance of NFs sheath on stents during manufacturing (squeezing in the crimping step) and angioplasty (expansion) were considered.

CONCLUSION

After the promising preliminary tests described here, the *in vitro* cytocompatibility and bioactivity of the final bilayer coated stents has to be confirmed. Finally, *in vivo* experiments will be carried out using a rabbit model to investigate the efficiency of this bilayer coated vascular stent towards antirestenosis and antithrombosis activity.

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Polymeric nanoparticulated systems for transdermal drug delivery of hydrophobic drugs

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INTRODUCTION

Percutaneous drug delivery is often used as a route of administration for low-molecular-weight drugs since it avoids hepatic first-pass and increases patients' compliance to the therapeutic treatment. However, these advantages are shortened by the skin protective barriers, in particular those exerted by the outermost layer, the stratum corneum (SC). Nowadays, nanometric drug delivery systems have reported elevate drug penetration across the skin barrier, as the intercellular spaces in SC are considered to have dimensions in the 50-100 nm range [1]. In this context, we have synthesized polymeric nanoparticulated systems based on vitamin E which may serve as a hydrophobic drug reservoir, and we have optimized the preparation conditions to obtain the appropriate nanoparticle (NP) size profile for ease percutaneous drug delivery.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

A methacrylic derivative of vitamin E (MVE) was synthesized with methacryloyl chloride in the presence of triethylamine as catalyst and copolymerized by free radical polymerization with two hydrophilic monomers (*N*-vinylpyrrolidone, VP, and vinylcaprolactam, VC) [2]. The hydrophobic/hydrophilic balance of the resultant amphiphilic terpolymer was determined by Magnetic Resonance (¹H-NMR). Self-assembled NP were prepared by nanoprecipitation method. Coumarin-6 (C6) was encapsulated as a model hydrophobic molecule at 1 % (w/w) with respect to the terpolymer and the encapsulation efficacy (%EE) was determined by UV absorbance ($\lambda = 465$ nm). C6-loaded NPs hydrodynamic properties (diameter, PDI, and Z-potential) were determined by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) and Laser Doppler Electrophoresis (LDE), respectively. NP were prepared in 0.9% NaCl or Milli-Q water to determine the influence of the ionic strength of the aqueous phase and, keeping constant the ratio between the terpolymer concentration in the organic phase and NP concentration in the aqueous phase ($[NP]_{AP}$). Different $[NP]_{AP}$ ranging from 2 to 0.5 mg/ml was also tested. C6-loaded NPs stability at 4 °C was assessed up to one month.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MVE was successfully synthesized and copolymerized with VC and VP as demonstrated by ¹H-NMR analysis. C6 was physically entrapped with a %EE above 60 % demonstrating the load-bearing capacity of the nanoparticulated system. No impact of aqueous phase ionic strength was observed in diameter, PDI or Z-potential as there are no charges exposed on the NP surface. However, it was seen a direct relationship between $[NP]_{AP}$ and size (**fig. 1**). A homogenous size distribution with PDI below 0.15 for all $[NP]_{AP}$ was obtained. Sizes below 100 nm were achieved at $[NP]_{AP}$ equal or lower than 0.5 mg/mL which might facilitate percutaneous drug delivery. NP stability was demonstrated as no changes were registered in hydrodynamic properties for one month.

Fig. 1. NPs size distribution in 0.9% NaCl at different $[NP]_{AP}$.

NP stability was demonstrated as no changes were registered in hydrodynamic properties for one month.

CONCLUSIONS

The nanoparticulated system has demonstrated high efficacy to encapsulated hydrophobic compounds and, at concentrations below 0.5 mg/mL, hydrodynamic diameters are within the ranges that may enhance drug delivery of hydrophobic active compounds through the skin.

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Designing New Hybrid CO Releasing Materials based on Silk Fibroin Nanoparticles

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INTRODUCTION

Silk Fibroin Nanoparticles (SFNs) have been showed as promising carriers for different drugs due to their unique features in terms of particle size, amphiphilic surface and biodegradability¹. On the other hand, carbon monoxide (CO) has recently emerged as an important biosignaling molecule, which exhibits a wide range of beneficial physiological effects (anti-inflammatory, antiproliferative, anti-apoptotic and antithrombotic) at specific concentrations². Several CO-releasing materials (CORMAs), such as photoactive metal carbonyl complexes, known as photoCORMs, have been described³ but great efforts are still needed in order to achieve the actual administration of exogenous CO for therapeutic purposes. We propose the SFNs, as active vehicles of photoCORMs, leading to the new hybrid material an enhanced CO-delivery features.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

In this work we present the synthesis and characterization, including X-ray single crystal structural studies, of novel metallic carbonyl complexes and the preparation and characterization of new photoCORMAs based on the combination of SFNs⁴ and the light-responsive CO-prodrugs (Scheme 1). The new hybrid nanomaterials (photoCORM@SFNs) were fully characterized by using SEM, DLS, ICP-MS, EDX-TEM, ATR-FTIR, Solid State Fluorescence Spectroscopy and Myoglobin Assay for spectroscopic CO releasing kinetic determination.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Once both CO-prodrug and SFNs were fully characterized, the absorption conditions were also optimized in terms of efficiency. The new hybrid photoCORM@SFNs not only retains the interesting size and morphology of “naked” SFNs, but also the photoactivable properties of free CORMs, showing a similar CO kinetic profile, but higher amount of delivered CO was observed upon irradiation (Figure 1). This result might be indicative of a charge transfer process from SFNs to the attached metal complex, and consequently related to the more efficient labilization of the corresponding CO ligands.

Scheme 1.

Figure 1.

CONCLUSION

In this work, we have prepared and characterized new photoCORMs, and their loading onto the SFNs has been successfully achieved by simple adsorption, leading to the first example of a light responsive CO-prodrug system based on biocompatible nanocarriers (photoCORM@SFNs). Noteworthy, this hybrid material releases approximately 34 % more of CO compared to free CORM, which is related to a more efficient CO ligand sensitization of the metal complex loaded onto the SFNs.

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Supramolecular structure of antimicrobial polycations with amphiphilic anions

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INTRODUCTION

Due to increase of antibiotic resistance alternative antimicrobial agents are on high demand¹. Amphiphilic, cationic polymers are the class of promising materials presenting antibacterial properties with the mechanism of action similar to naturally occurring antimicrobial peptides based on disturbing integrity of cell membrane². In order to optimize the desired properties of these polymers we work on modification of their structures such as increasing hydrophobicity of the polymer chain which is one of the parameters responsible for their activity². In this poster we will present the research on supramolecular systems of linear polyethyleneimine (L-PEI) with organic anions containing long alkyl chains. Such non-covalent modification would enable simple and potentially reversible functionalization of cationic polymers. Herein we present studies on the stability in aqueous solution with and without NaCl for L-PEI with different counter-anions to simulate physiological solution as the stability in such conditions is one of the key issues.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Solutions of polyethyleneimine hydrochloride and sodium salts of studied anions in deionized water with or without NaCl addition were dialyzed using dialysis membrane with MWCO 500 Da. Water was removed via lyophilization and the degree of anion substitution was determined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. Steady-state fluorescence of pyrene in aqueous solutions were measured to analyze the influence of L-PEI on aggregates formation in solution of studied amphiphilic anions in pure water as well as in NaCl solutions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CMC for studied surfactants and CAC for systems of surfactants with L-PEI were determined via measurements of steady-state fluorescence showing that value of CAC is significantly lower for solutions with L-PEI (Figure 1). Addition of L-PEI to the surfactant solution increases the stability of formed aggregates. We will present the stoichiometry of obtained complexes in water and in aqueous solutions of NaCl. Presence of studied organic counter-ions in dialyzed structures (confirmed by ¹H NMR spectra), despite dissolution and possibility of being washed by pure water in excess, confirmed the stability of the structures.

Figure 1. I_1/I_3 in function of concentration of sodium decylmalonate in aqueous solutions.

CONCLUSION

Presented results allow to draw conclusions about relatively high stability of studied systems based on non-covalent interactions which enable to consider them as appropriate for use in physiological conditions, however further studies are necessary.

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A *Caenorhabditis elegans* model for testing toxicity of zinc and doxycycline loaded polymeric nanoparticles.

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INTRODUCTION

Polymeric nanocarriers were synthesized and loaded with zinc and doxycycline. Zinc and doxycycline were found to be potent antimicrobials and facilitated hard tissue remineralization^{1,2}. NPs are employed to reduce elemental toxicity. *C. elegans* have the capability of providing the real-time toxicity information of nanomaterials at molecular level, subcellular level and whole organism level simultaneously and then, helping to draw more relevant conclusions for the biosafety of nanomaterials³. The objective was to ascertain the effect of tested NPs on lethality, metabolism, growth, reproduction and fertility endpoints using *C. elegans* as a model organism.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Polymeric nanoparticles have been synthesized and loaded with zinc and doxycycline. The exact amounts of zinc and doxycycline loaded onto NPs were calculated. Worm's death rate in a concentration-response curve basis was calculated for lethality. Metabolism was assessed through pharyngeal pumping assay. Body length measurements, brood size and eggs laying were used to assess growth, reproduction and fertility respectively. One-way ANOVA and Bonferroni were used for comparisons ($p < 0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tested NPs at the highest dosage (10 mg/mL) did not affect lethality or worm metabolism, expressed in terms of death rate and pharyngeal pumping per minute. Un-doped NPs reduced fertility and reproduction. However, Zn-NPs lightly increases worm growth and fertility, but did not affect worm's reproduction. Dox-NPs retard fertility and reproduction during the first 72 h, probably due to a cross-effect, as doxycycline may impair *E. coli* concentration, which is the main food source for worms.

CONCLUSION

Our study indicates the possibility of evading the toxicity of zinc and doxycycline by incorporating these compounds in polymeric nanoparticles.

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Conductive polyaniline/PVA scaffolds: biocompatibility study

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INTRODUCTION

Bioelectricity plays a crucial role in a variety of cellular processes, such as cell division, cell signalling and differentiation, as well as on the tissue level, e.g., in wound healing or angiogenesis^{1,2}. Emerging knowledge about role of bioelectricity in the physiology has led to the application of conducting materials in regenerative medicine, the tissue engineering of electrically excitable tissues and in the field of biosensing. Conventional materials however demonstrate number of disadvantages, for example different elasticity.^{3,4}. Polyaniline cryogel is a new unique macroporous form of polyaniline combining its intrinsic electrical conductivity with the suitable material properties of hydrogels.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The surface energy, pore-size distribution and elasticity expressed by Young moduli were determined. Moreover, impurities leaching from the cryogel were characterized by chromatography. To determine biocompatibility, cytotoxicity, embryotoxicity, cell adhesion and growth of embryonic stem cells, embryoid bodies, cardiomyocytes and neural progenitors were employed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PANI cryogels supported by PVA are soft conducting materials. They do not have only good mechanical integrity represented by Young modulus of 9.7 ± 0.5 kPa but they are also macroporous and highly hydrophilic. These properties, together with cytotoxicity and embryotoxicity of PANI cryogels, are prerequisites for number of its applications in tissue engineering or biosensing. Results show that PANI cryogel has the potential to be used as a carrier for cells in these applications. Regarding the results of the porosity and elasticity, the cryogel mimicks the properties of native tissue.

CONCLUSION

Polyaniline cryogels supported by poly(vinyl alcohol) are novel macroporous soft conducting materials with good mechanical properties, appropriate biological properties and high hydrophilicity, which are essential prerequisites for any application in tissue engineering or biosensing. Polyaniline cryogels are therefore suitable for application in tissue engineering and biomedicine in general, where the electrical monitoring or stimulation of tissue is required.

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Biological properties of linear polyethyleneimine and its hydrophobic modification

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INTRODUCTION

Typically bacterial infections are treated with antibiotics, although increase of antibiotic resistance makes this therapy ineffective. Many research groups try to overcome this problem by development of polymers that mimic action of antibacterial peptides. Structural parameters like amphiphilic balance were pointed to be important. Appropriate contribution of hydrophobic and hydrophilic groups in polymer structure could influence both antibacterial activity and polymer toxicity to human cells.^{1,2} Those two biological properties can be compared by selectivity index. Polymers that apart from selectivity between bacteria and human cells show also selectivity between Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria described as double selective could also be interesting.³

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

In this research biological properties of linear polyethyleneimine and its hydrophobic derivative (hL-PEI) were investigated. Firstly minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was measured toward *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Next polymers toxicity toward spontaneously immortalized human keratinocyte cell line (HaCaT) was tested with MTT assay. Finally haemolytic activity was determined with human erythrocytes. Based on obtained results parameters like 50% inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀), concentration causing 50% haemoglobin release (HC₅₀) and selectivity index were determined.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Comparison between results obtained for L-PEI and hL-PEI showed that modified polymer exhibit enhanced toxicity to erythrocytes, HaCaT cells and both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Both polymers show small double selectivity. Chosen results are presented in table 1.

Table 1 Biological properties of L-PEI and hL-PEI

	MIC <i>E. coli</i> [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$]	MIC <i>S. aureus</i> [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$]	HC ₅₀ [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$]	HC ₅₀ /MIC _{<i>E. coli</i>}	HC ₅₀ /MIC _{<i>S. aureus</i>}
L-PEI	128	64	>1536	>12	>24
hL-PEI	32	16	364	11.38	22.75

CONCLUSION

Hydrophobic modification of L-PEI increases its biological activity.

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The stability study on antimicrobial polycations containing novel degradable linker.

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INTRODUCTION

During our previous research we found that short oligomers of methylated linear polyethyleneimine (Me₂-L-PEI) increase their reactivity toward hydroxide with the added number of repeating units¹. The stiffening of the four-mer Me₂-L-PEI oligomer by DABCO subunit incorporation (Figure 1) makes this molecule much more reactive. The study on stability in physiological conditions (PBS 7.4, 37°C) of **1** revealed slow degradation of this molecule¹ and leads to hypothesis that **1** could be used as a degradable linker in antimicrobial polymers construction. Cationic polymers are broadly tested as antimicrobial agents being an alternative for classic antibiotics, however most of tested polycations are non-degradable what could limit their application². Herein, we report stability studies of polymers containing **1** in different pH conditions characteristic for healthy and infected tissues.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Studied polycations containing analogue of **1** were prepared by Menshutkin reaction. Stability studies were performed in deuterated saline phosphate buffer in deuterioxide in NMR tubes incubated at 37°C without light access. Degree of degradation was determined based on ¹H NMR spectra.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of stability study of **1** in pH value and temperature related to physiological environment are presented on Figure 1¹. After 3 weeks degree of degradation reached *ca.* 10%.

Figure 1. Degradation rate of **1** in PBS 7.4 at 37°C¹.

The degradation undergoes *via* Hofmann elimination reaction without any side products and it is enzyme independent. A rate of the degradation is dependent only on hydroxide concentration what makes it pH dependent. The results strongly suggest possibility of application of **1** as a structural component making antimicrobial polycations biodegradable.

We will present results of the degradation study of our rigid antimicrobial polycations with high positive charge density in different pH conditions characteristic for healthy and infected tissues.

CONCLUSION

We have found out that DABCO derivative **1** undergoes slow degradation under physiological pH and temperature conditions. Further stability studies on antimicrobial polymers containing linker **1** will be presented on our poster.

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Synthesis and Biomedical Applications of Poly-amido-saccharides

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The chemical synthesis of high molecular weight polysaccharides is challenging for chemists and new, robust approaches are needed. Introducing an amide linkage between monosaccharide repeat units instead of an ether linkage is a strategy that enables molecular-level control during synthesis while preserving some of the unique properties of natural polysaccharides. The synthesis and characterization of chiral, controlled molecular weight poly-amido-saccharides via the anionic ring opening polymerization of a beta-lactam sugar monomer will be presented. Finally, the biological activities and biomedical applications of these unique polymers will be described.

Recent Publications: *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, **2012**, 134, 16255-16264; *ACS Macro Letters*, **2013**, 2, 887-890; *Chemical Science*, **2014**, 5, 551-557; *ACS Macro Letters*, **2014**, 3, 359-363; *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, **2014**, 136, 9544-9547; *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, **2016**, 138, 6532-6540; *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, **2017**, 39, 14217-14223; *ACS Macro Letters*, **2018**, 7, 772-777.

Synthesis and characterization of well-defined polyrotaxanes for the design of stretchable gels

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INTRODUCTION

Several strategies have been used over the last thirty years to improve mechanical properties of polymer gels.^{1,2} Most of the stretchable polymer gels present well-structured architecture, such as double polymer networks which consist in a specific combination of two networks with contrasting structures.^{1,2,3} On the other hand, most of cross-linked polysaccharides gels do not exhibit enough stretchability to be ideally used in biomedical applications such as topical patches.

In 2001, Okumura and al. were the first to report slide-ring gels,⁴ based on cross-linked polyrotaxanes (two or more cyclic molecules threaded on a linear polymer end-capped by bulky moieties).⁵ This first slide-ring gel inspired us to develop polyrotaxane-based cross-linkers for the design of mechanically improved polysaccharide hydrogels.

One of the key factors of the stretchability of slide-ring gels is the ability of cyclodextrins to freely slide along the linear chain when a mechanical stress is applied. In this regard, the ability to control the number of threaded cyclodextrins is a crucial challenge in the synthesis of polyrotaxanes, which has been little studied to date. By wisely choosing the linear polymers and the nature of cyclodextrins, we were here able to synthesize polyrotaxanes with a controlled number of sliding cyclodextrins along poloxamer chains in a one-pot reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Reactive poloxamers were stirred together with natural and modified cyclodextrins in an appropriate aqueous buffer for 12 hours. Bulky, end-capping moieties were then added to the pseudo-polyrotaxane by photo-activated thiol-ene reaction. Finally, purification steps comprised dialysis for 24 hours and freeze-drying. Structural studies consisted in mono- and bidimensional ¹H and ¹³C NMR experiments and electrospray ionization mass spectrometry. Polyrotaxanes samples were then associated with a reactive polysaccharide by a photo-activated cross-linking reaction and further tested with dynamic rheological measurements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

By changing the nature of cyclodextrins and linear poloxamers, we synthesized polyrotaxanes with 2, 4 and 8 cyclodextrins threaded onto the linear chain, end-capped by functionalized cyclodextrins. ¹H and ¹³C, mono- and bi-dimensional NMR experiments confirmed the chemical structures. These polyrotaxane-based cross-linkers were used for the formation of polysaccharide-based stretchable gels, which were characterized by dynamic rheological measurements.

CONCLUSION

Well-controlled and well-defined polyrotaxanes with few threaded cyclodextrins were successfully synthesised and further associated with a polysaccharide to form a slide-ring gel.

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Mucin-inspired broad range virus binding inhibitor based on multivalent high molecular weight hyperbranched polyglycerol

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INTRODUCTION

Multivalent binding inhibitors are a promising class of novel antivirals for various viruses, as binding of viruses to cells, which is the inevitable first step of the infection process, can be effectively blocked by formation of multiple interactions between virus and inhibitor. Herein, high molecular weight multivalent binding inhibitors based on hyperbranched polyglycerols are presented that have been functionalized as inspired by mucins with sialic acids and sulfate groups. Inhibitor sizes up to 6 MDa have been achieved, thereby approaching the size of small mucins¹ and hitting the theoretically expected optimal size for inhibiting binding of 100 nm viruses² (such as influenza A virus) by formation of multivalent virus-inhibitor interactions. As these inhibitors have been inspired physically and chemically by mucins, they are promising candidates of broad-band antivirals.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

High molecular weight hyperbranched polyglycerol (hPG) is synthesized in two steps via anionic ring-opening polymerization of glycidol. To introduce a similar functional surface compared to mucins the hPG is functionalized with sialic acids and sulfate groups.

The quantification of the inhibition efficiency for the synthesized binding inhibitors against various virus species (such as influenza, herpes simplex, and vesicular stomatitis virus) is based on a novel inhibitor assay involving total internal reflection fluorescence (TIRF) microscopy. Hereby, a supported lipid bilayer with incorporated receptors acts as artificial plasma membrane, where the binding of fluorescently labelled viruses can be visualized with TIRF microscopy³.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results show that multivalent binding inhibitors are highly potent to prevent the first step of viral infection: binding to the cell surface.

Binding kinetics such as on- and off-rates of single viruses to incorporated receptors in a supported lipid bilayer are analysed using TIRF microscopy. A competitive approach of viruses binding to receptors in the SLB or binding to inhibitors shows the inhibition efficiency of the mucin inspired polymer.

CONCLUSION

Functionalized high molecular weight hyperbranched polyglycerols are able to prevent virus binding to receptors on a supported lipid bilayer. TIRF microscopy is a powerful characterization tool to determine binding kinetics such on- and off-rates.

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Enhanced biocompatibility and reduced capsule formation of silicone surfaces via tantalum ion implantation

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INTRODUCTION

Although silicone rubber-based implants have been utilized as a prosthesis material in a plastic surgery for the past decades, the long-term failures induced by capsular formation and contracture surrounding the silicone implants have not been resolved yet^{1,2}. In this study, we developed a new surface modification, denoted as sputtering-based plasma immersion ion implantation, to enhance the biocompatibility of biomedical silicone rubber surfaces³.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Tantalum ion implanted silicone rubbers were prepared through a sputtering-based plasma immersion ion implantation technique and evaluated the surface characterization, mechanical property, water contact angle, *in vitro* cellular response. *In vivo* model of capsular formation with insertion of silicone implant into dorsal side of rats was established. After 8 weeks, capsules around silicone implant were harvested and histologic analysis and Western blots were done. A *p* value below 0.05 for the statistical analysis was considered significant in all cases.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on relatively hydrophilic surfaces and stable Ta functionalization of Ta-implanted silicones, the *in-vitro* biocompatibility of human dermal fibroblast was significantly enhanced. In a rat *in vivo* model, factors related to fibrous capsule formation including the capsular thickness, number of inflammatory cell, myofibroblast differentiation, collagen density and related biologic markers (α SMA, CTGF, Col I, TGF- β , VEGF, and MPO) were significantly reduced around the Nano/Ta silicone implant compared to around the bare implant. These results suggest that Ta ion implantation made the medical silicone rubber surfaces more biocompatible, followed by reduced fibrous capsular formation.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we confirmed that the fibrous capsule formation around silicone implants can be substantially suppressed by the introduction of a nano-textured surface topography and Ta-implanted surface chemistry.

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Preparation of Graphene Oxide / Polyethyleneimine Composite Aerogels

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INTRODUCTION

Polyethyleneimine (PEI) is an interesting biocompatible polymer that has been previously used as a coating material for drug delivery systems.¹ Additionally, carbon based materials, such as carbon nanotubes, graphene and graphene oxide (GO) offer a good structural support with high surface area. Specifically, GO combines the textural advantages of graphene with convenient hydrophilicity and fascinating surface chemistry,² allowing the formation of free-standing aerogels. However, these aerogels are thoroughly unstable in the presence of polar solvents, such as water, limiting the possible applications in the biomaterials field. In this work, a method previously described by our group using aziridine and supercritical CO₂ is implemented to obtain composite aerogels of graphene oxide and polyethyleneimine.³

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The PEI in situ polymerization under high pressure of CO₂ was performed using aziridine (Metadona S.A). The GO aerogels that were used in the experiments were previously synthesized using supercritical CO₂ in a one-step procedure at 200 bar and 60 °C starting from a graphene oxide dispersion (Graphenea Inc.).⁴

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After performing a typical foaming experiment,⁵ a GO aerogel is obtained (Fig 1.). On a second step, the addition of aziridine under high pressure of CO₂ induce the presence of amine groups inside the aerogel. This process is carried out in supercritical conditions, as the pore structure of the aerogel needs to be maintained. Having into account the exothermic reaction that happens when the aziridine polymerizes, which could alter the structure and composition of the material, the samples were studied before and after the reaction by solid state characterization techniques (N₂ adsorption, TGA, XPS, IR...). One of the most exciting characteristics was the structural stability in water attained by the addition of branched ethyleneimine chains that served as unions between the GO flakes. After the aziridine polymerization, the aerogel became able to be submerged in water without collapsing, enhancing its possibilities as a composite biomaterial, making it a viable study object for drug delivery systems.

Figure 1. GO aerogel.

CONCLUSION

The methods used in this work, including the in situ polymerization of aziridine implies a new way to obtain composites of polyethyleneimine and graphene oxide with mixed and very interesting properties, viable for a drug delivery system.

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Surface functionalization of polyurethane foams: silver-based antimicrobial treatments on air filtration units for prevention of respiratory diseases

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INTRODUCTION

Indoor bioaerosols containing fungi, bacteria, allergens and also non-biological particles such as dust and tobacco smoke can originate from outdoor air or internal sources [1] and can be associated with a wide range of adverse health effects and respiratory diseases [2]. Heating, ventilating and air-conditioning (HVAC) systems are designed to create a comfortable climate of indoor air and to avoid a high number of microorganisms being circulated. However, the air filtration pads represent one of the most susceptible parts of the unit to microbial colonization, due primarily to the moisture and the presence of nutrients favourable to the bacterial proliferation resulting from organic deposition [3]. The maintenance of the clean state of HVAC is often insufficient to reduce microbial colonization of air filters. Prevention strategies developed for protection from aerosolized agents require efficient air filtration and air sterilization system. The use of silver as antimicrobial agent has long been recognized and many products based on the presence of silver compounds and silver nanoparticles have recently been developed for a range of biomedical applications [4].

This study aims at evaluating the potential of silver coatings deposited on polyurethane pads in reducing the level of biocontamination and cross transmission associated to contaminated air filtration units.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Polyurethane foams were treated with silver by using a deposition technology based on an *in situ* photo-assisted chemical reaction. The process consists in impregnating the substrate with a silver based solution and in exposing the surface of the material to an ultraviolet source in order to promote the conversion from silver precursor to metal silver clusters [5]. Scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy were performed to verify the successful deposition of the silver coating. Then, the materials were tested through microbiological procedures to verify the efficacy of the silver-coated filters on the viability and growth of selected micro-organisms and, in particular, on microbial human pathogens associated with air filtration units and respiratory disease, namely *Legionella pneumophila*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Procedures used in industry such as direct inoculation test, filtration experiment and shaking test were adopted as testing methodologies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presence of silver on the substrate surface and the efficacy of the technology in providing a homogeneous distribution of the silver cluster were demonstrated. Microbiological analyses revealed that the silver coating was capable of reducing the number of viable recoverable cells for five of six test species at a statistically significant level (*Ps. aeruginosa*, *E. coli*, *Staph. aureus*, *A. flavus*, *A. niger*), with the sixth (*Leg. pneumophila*) still indicating a decrease in number. These organisms are all associated with human disease and might indicate that the inclusion of silver particles on filtration devices could lead to a significant reduction in the bioaerosolization of viable human pathogens into environments using recirculated air. Further, the organisms tested are all noted to be significant sources of human morbidity and mortality. Thus, the results indicated a broad spectrum activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative cells, and against filamentous fungi.

CONCLUSION

The results provided evidence of the effectiveness of the silver coating in reducing the bioaerosolization of viable human pathogens into environments through recirculated air. Microorganisms can affect the air quality in indoor environments and can be responsible for infectious, allergic or toxic disturbances on human airways. The development of an adequate bioaerosol control might ameliorate a positive health effect in humans.

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Silver treated antibacterial compounds for the development of bioactive devices for prevention of respiratory diseases

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INTRODUCTION

The huge concerns associated to the antibiotic resistance demonstrated by many microorganisms and the potential pathogens contaminations in public places have encouraged the definition of novel prevention strategies to reduce the risk of cross transmission. In hospital environment, schools and waiting rooms, for example, the contact with contaminated surfaces and devices can promote bacteria spread among people, medical staff and patients. The use of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) represents an effective protection for health and, in particular, nasal filters can prevent inhalation of microorganisms and related respiratory diseases [1]. However, in terms of humidity and temperature, the nasal cavities represent an ideal environment for bacterial growth and proliferation and *Staphylococcus aureus* has been recognized as one of the most common microorganisms responsible for nasal colonization [2]. This work aims at developing an antibacterial bioactive polymer for incorporation in nasal filters, in order to obtain devices with improved capability in reducing the risk associated to potentially inhaled bacteria in hospitals. Silver has been selected as antibacterial agent due to its well-known broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity [3]; the bioactive compound was obtained by adding silver-treated hydroxyapatite in a biogel and by properly defining the related parameters in terms of antibacterial properties.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Hydroxyapatite (HA) powder with average size of 10 μm was treated with silver by using an *in-situ* photo-deposition technology [4]. The process consists in the preparation of a silver solution containing silver precursor and photo-reducing agent (*i*), the deposition of the silver solution on the surface of the material through spray coating or dip coating (*ii*), the exposure of the substrate to a ultraviolet source which promotes the photo-reduction reaction and the following conversion from silver precursor to metal silver (*iii*). Different process parameters have been tested, including different percentages of silver precursor (0.5 wt/v%, 1 wt/v% and 2 wt/v%) and different UV exposure times (10 and 20 minutes). Then, the treated HA powders were incorporated into the biogel in different percentages and the bioactivity of the compounds was tested through agar diffusion tests on *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The antibacterial tests performed on silver treated HA demonstrated the successfully deposition of the silver coatings on hydroxyapatite. Indeed, even the lowest percentage of silver precursor (0.5 wt/v%) resulted in the presence of an inhibition area to bacterial growth around the sample. Even when mixed into the biogel, the efficacy of the silver coating was confirmed against both *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, thus also indicating a good distribution of the silver particles in the samples. Dependence from the process parameters was observed and analysed to define the best technological choice in terms of costs and effectiveness for potential scale up. At this purpose, the lowest silver percentage and the shortest UV irradiation were selected.

CONCLUSION

The results obtained in this work confirmed the effectiveness of the silver deposition technology in providing an antibacterial coating on the specific HA substrate, even by using very low amounts of silver precursor. Hydroxyapatite demonstrated a good potential as additive material for the development of a bioactive compound and the antibacterial capability was demonstrated on both Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria. Further studies will be addressed to the development of the prototype of the bioactive nasal device based on the silver-modified biogel.

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Bacterial Response on Thin PLA/Mg Composite Film

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INTRODUCTION

When a new protocol is established to manufacture a polymer, it is necessary to carry out new tests in order to evaluate its response to different biological processes that may occur after inserting this material into the human body, and which are related to the biomaterial surface properties. This is the case, for example, of *in vitro* tests of cell or bacterial adhesion to evaluate the biocompatibility of new biomaterials. In this work, we present bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation assays on PLA and PLA10Mg films prepared by solvent-cast method.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Staphylococcus epidermidis ATCC 35983 was used for bacterial adhesion. Adhesion experiments were carried for 60, 150 and 240 min. Adhered bacteria were quantified by using a kit Live/Dead BacLight L-7012; this kit also gave the bacterial viability. Early and mature biofilm formation on the polymer film surfaces were performed for 8 and 24h at 37 °C. The viable bacteria included in biofilm were quantified using the BacTiter-Glo™ Microbial Cell Viability Assay. The light emission was measured in a Fluorescence Microplate Reader.

The experiments were carried out in duplicate and repeated at least three times with independent cultures in order to confirm reproducibility.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PLA10Mg films have bactericidal effect on *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 35983. Presence of Mg in PLA causes impairment on bacteria. Adhered microorganisms are progressively damaged with time. Bacterial viability in early biofilms on PLA10Mg samples decreases significantly in relation to PLA control. Nevertheless, this behaviour is not maintained at longer biofilm time: in mature biofilms (24 h) bacteria behave similarly in PLA and in PLA10Mg films.

CONCLUSION

The initial bacterial viability and early biofilm formation on PLA films are impaired when Mg is present in the polymeric matrix. As time goes by, mature biofilms are similar in the films without and with magnesium, which indicates that bacterial effect could be shielded by damaged bacteria.

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Magnesium powder filled PLA for filament based 3D Printing for medical applications

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INTRODUCTION

Additive Manufacturing technology exist on the market since 1988, which is known as the year of launching of the first machine (SLA 1) based on stereolithography (SL) process. Since than a large number of applications, especially in the medical field, were developed using this technology: personalized surgical guides, tissue-engineering scaffolds, drug dosing, and customized implants^{1,2}. Some of these applications are based on Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) process, which usually uses thermoplastic polymers. Literature shows several studies on developing new composites for FDM process, like producing feedstock filament by mixing matrix and reinforcements³ or inserting continuous fibers into the polymer matrix⁴. The purpose of this study was to prove the viability of obtaining polylactic acid based composites reinforced with magnesium powder as filament feedstock for Additive Manufacturing (AM) based on fused deposition modeling (FDM) process.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Two compositions of PLA-Mg particles were prepared: (1) 150 g of PLA pellets were mixt with 6 g of Mg particles, 100 µm particles; (2) 150 g of PLA pellets were mixt with 4 g of Mg particles, 125 µm particles. Using the two compositions and vitamin E as precursor, we obtain, by extrusion, filaments for 3D printing process. In order to analyze both PLA filament and the two new PLA-Mg filaments we used a scanning electron microscope type Philips ESM XL40SEM. In order to analyze the integration of the Mg particle in PLA matrix, a SEM analysis was performed on the filaments after their fracture. To prove that the produced filaments are suitable for building fine geometrical features, two 3D-printed screws (ACL-Anterior Cruciate Ligament) were manufactured.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The diameter of the filament containing Mg was less constant; it varied between 1.11 mm and 1.17 mm. According the SEM analysis in the fracture area it can be observed a good integration of Mg particles due to the use of vitamin E as precursor. The implants screws were manufactured at a extrusion temperature of 200°C and 50°C bed temperature, these values being chosen after analyzing the samples obtained by varying process parameters.

CONCLUSION

The results of this research proved that Mg reinforced PLA filaments can be produced and used in 3D printing process based on filament extrusion. One important aspect revealed is related to the use of vitamin E for assure Mg particles adherence to the PLA pellets during raw materials preparation phase. Regarding the filament production stage, the experiments performed showed the need of optimizing the process for ensuring a constant diameter and for avoiding the formation of air bubbles that negatively affect the characteristics of filaments and 3D-printed samples and implants. Further research will be focused on filament composition optimization in accordance to the results of mechanical tests and biodegradation studies.

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Effects of Silk Degumming in Fibroin Nanoparticle Synthesis

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INTRODUCTION

Silk fibroin nanoparticles (SFNP) show excellent properties for its use as nano drug delivery systems (NDDS)¹. The sericin removal (degumming) from silk native is the primary process which should be carried out at sufficient level and homogeneity to get silk fibroin fibres to be treated in further processes². In this work, we study the influence of four degumming treatments for silk from silkworms *Bombyx mori* and how the treatment correlates with the size distribution.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Four degumming methods were chosen among the most representative of the commonly used in literature and where named as: M1) Degumming by autoclave; M2) Degumming by short alkaline boiling; M3) Degumming by long alkaline boiling; M4) Ultrasonication probe in water. The resultant silk fibroin was dissolved in ionic liquid (1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium Acetate) and used for nanoparticle synthesis by rapid desolvation in polar organic solvents². The integrity of the SF fibres after the degumming process was analysed by SDS-PAGE. Particle size and morphology was analysed by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) and Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The distribution of molecular weight (Mw) of the SF samples analysed by gel electrophoresis reflects the integrity of the protein after the degumming process. It can be seen from Figure 1a that the different process produced vastly different Mw distribution. The degradation of SF follows the order: M1 < M4 < M2 < M3, starting from the least degraded to the most. Size distribution and mean hydrodynamic diameter (Z-Average) (Figure 1b) can be correlated with the integrity/degradation of the SF. The higher the degradation the smallest mean diameter and narrower distribution were obtained.

Figure 1. a) SDS-PAGE results for SF degummed with methods M1 to M4, b) Size distribution by intensity of SFNP after degumming process of Autoclave, Na₂CO₃ 30', Na₂CO₃ 120' and Ultrasound.

CONCLUSION

By DLS measurement of the SFNP synthesized it was possible to confirm a correlation between the degradation of the proteins and the reduction of mean size and size distribution. As final remarks, the degumming method implemented for the SF purification must be taken into account for the SFNP synthesis, as the integrity of the protein greatly affects the SFNP mean size and size distribution.

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Evaluation of the osteoinductive potential of HDPSCs on membranes of PCL/f-MWCNTs decorated with β -glycerol phosphate for bone regeneration.

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INTRODUCTION. Several investigations have been carried out to find the ideal construct that is osteoconductive, osteoinductive and osteogenic for bone defects (Khan et al., 2012). Due to this need, current approaches are focused in the development of new biomaterials with the capacity to induce bone formation in the implantation of heterotopic sites (Barradas et al., 2011). Nowadays, research continues on the development of this type of biomaterials using nanoparticles with properties that consider the biological environment and improve the tissues regeneration (Newman, 2016). This work report, the potential of β -glycerol phosphate loaded poly (ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) membranes reinforced with functionalized multiwall carbon nanotubes (f-MWCNTs) to induce the differentiation of Human Dental Pulp Stem Cells (HDPSCs) into bone-like.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS. Two types of membranes were made: PCL / f-MWCNTs-A and PCL / f-MWCNTs-BGP-B (decorated with a BGP molecule) following a similar procedure. Mechanical stress was observed. HDPSCs were seeded, biocompatibility and proliferation were carried out through Live and Dead and MTT assays, osteodifferentiation of HDPSCs was checked through the Alizarin red test. Finally, an implant of the constructs was made in biomodels that was analyzed histologically at certain times (4 and 12 weeks).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Mechanical stress test showed an increase in the average elastic modulus of the PCL up to 608 ± 4.3 MPa in both groups when introducing the f-MWCNTs. The biological techniques showed a higher number and percentage of living cells with an enhanced formation of calcium deposits in the PCL/f-MWCNTs-B membranes. In vivo histologies studies demonstrated a new bone formation around the critical size membranes defects.

CONCLUSION. These PCL/MWCNT matrices showed good biocompatibility and favored cell proliferation in vitro, as well as histological findings demonstrated the formation of mature connective tissue, characterized by the presence of collagen fibers mature, some fibrocytes and newly formed cells in addition to blood vessels in vivo.

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Degradation of Carboxymethylcellulose by Radiation for Sterilization

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INTRODUCTION

Carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) is a cellulose derivative with carboxymethyl groups bound to some of the hydroxyl groups of the glucopyranose monomers that make up the cellulose backbone. CMC is used for a variety of applications in a number of industries, including the food, personal care, pharmaceutical, oilfield and paper industries, due to its superior properties as a binding, thickening, and stabilizing agent in these end uses. The most important character that makes CMC useful in these applications is its high viscosity in a low concentration. It has been found that CMC could be chemically modified by a radiation.¹ In this study, there was studied the effect of an electron beam irradiation at a sterilizing dose on the viscosity of CMC.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Carboxymethylcellulose sodium salt (CMC) was purchased from SEAN Co. Ltd. (Chungnam, South Korea). A dose of 30 kGy absorbed by an electron beam irradiation was used in this study. UELV-10-10S accelerator (NII EFA, Moscow, Russia) (Energy 10 MeV, current 1 mA, output 570 kW) and ELV-8 electron accelerator (EB Tech, Daejeon, South Korea) (Energy 2.5 MeV, current 18 mA; Energy 1 MeV, current 11.4 mA, output 100 kW) were used for the electron beam irradiation of the CMC solution. The viscosity of the CMC solution was measured by the Brookfield viscometer (DV-II+ pro, Brookfield Engineering Laboratories, MA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It was observed that the relative viscosity decreased as the irradiation dose increased. When the irradiation dose was 5 kGy, the relative viscosity of the 3% CMC solution decreased to 76.35% of the non-irradiated control. The relative viscosities of the CMC solution irradiated at 10, 20, and 30 kGy were 62.9%, 43.1%, and 29.2% of the control, respectively.

When the absorbed dose in the CMC with a 10 MeV energy was 30 kGy, the relative viscosities of the irradiated 3%, 4%, and 5% CMC solutions were 29.2%, 45.1%, and 49.5%, respectively.

When vitamin C was added at final concentrations of 0.1%, 0.5% and 1%, the relative viscosities at 30 kGy with a 10 MeV energy were increased from 29.2% to 36.3%, 42.4% and 47.1%, respectively.

CONCLUSION

During the irradiation with the electron beam, the CMC in the solution was degraded, but less severely than with the gamma irradiation. The irradiation with a low energy led to a lesser degradation of the CMC due to its low penetration. Also, the addition of vitamin C and a frozen irradiation were shown to be effective against this degradation, but the extent of the protection was less when compared with the case of the gamma ray irradiation.

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Nose-to-Brain Controlled Drug Delivery from Microparticles Embedded in a Hydrogel Patch

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INTRODUCTION

Central nervous system (CNS) disorders (e.g., multiple sclerosis, Alzheimer's, Parkinson's or Huntington's disease, etc.) represent a growing public health issue, primarily due to the increased life expectancy and the aging population. The treatment of such disorders is particularly elaborated and requires the delivery of therapeutic compounds to the brain in sufficient amounts to elicit a pharmacological response. The role of the nose as an entry point for the brain-targeted delivery of various medications has long been identified, revealing an unprecedented opportunity to deliver drugs to the brain, thus posing a potentially promising alternative to intravenous delivery modes. Although highly advantageous due to its non-invasive nature, rapid onset of action and highly localized delivery resulting in low systemic exposure, the delivery of medications to the brain via the nasal cavity exhibits particular challenges, associated with poor permeability across biological barriers (e.g., nasal and olfactory mucosae) and poor stability attributed to enzymatic activity observed in the nasal cavity.

The development of an innovative nanotechnology-based formulation is described that can be applied to the nasal olfactory region for the chronic treatment of CNS disorders. The novel formulation consists of biodegradable polymer nanoparticles (NPs) loaded with cognition enhancing drugs (e.g., long-acting insulin analogues). The drug loaded particles are embedded into a biodegradable hydrogel that is deposited, via a nasal endoscopic applicator as a thin liquid-gelling film, onto the olfactory region. By controlling the molecular and morphological properties of the biodegradable hydrogel and the embedded polymeric nanocarriers, a controlled and sustained release of the therapeutics at the desired site can be achieved thus resulting in improved drug bioavailability.

EXPERIMENTAL AND COMPUTATIONAL METHODS

In this work, a process systems computational approach, comprising models at different time and length scales, is applied to elucidate the fundamental physical, transport and biological processes related with nose-to-brain delivery of biopharmaceutics. In particular, it includes a CFD-based computational model to describe the flow of a reactive polymer solution through the endoscopic applicator in terms of polymer solution flow rate and tube characteristics (e.g., tip geometry, diameter). The extrusion of the reactive polymer solution and its conversion to a solid hydrogel film deposited on the olfactory region of the nasal cavity is examined for different tip placements, tip shapes, and total extruded matrix volume. The muco-adhesive forces, which control the hydrogel film spreading, are considered via the development of a hydrogel/mucus model. The long-term stability of the deposited hydrogel matrix is examined in terms of the hydrogel swelling and degradation kinetics. A dynamic drug release model has been developed to describe the drug release rate from the drug-loaded microcarriers embedded in the hydrogel matrix in terms of molecular and morphological properties of polymeric carriers-hydrogel system. The dynamic model includes particle and hydrogel degradation kinetics, drug diffusion from the carriers via the hydrogel matrix to the olfactory epithelium, etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the numerical solution of the above computational models, the dynamic drug mass transfer rate from the hydrogel matrix to the mucosa interface was calculated. Finally, the drug flux from the hydrogel-mucosa interface to the olfactory bulb (i.e., drug transfer through the mucus layer in series with the epithelium (i.e., effected by two transfer pathways, namely, transcellular and paracellular) was calculated. The simulation results were compared with experimental measurements.

CONCLUSION

The various mathematical models will be integrated following a PSE approach to obtain a general computational framework that will identify the key characteristic system's design parameters that will optimize the complex formulation-deposition process to achieve a desired therapeutic effect.

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Oligopeptide-Polymer Conjugates for Image-Guided Surgery Targeted against $\alpha_v\beta_3$ Integrin

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INTRODUCTION

Image-guided surgery offers possibility of surgical excision of solid tumors with minimizing of unwanted residues. This requires development of efficient contrast agents to improve the visualization of tumor margins as well as identification of target moiety on tumour cells. $\alpha_v\beta_3$ integrin belongs to one of the promising targets that is highly expressed in some tumors and their vasculature^{1,2} and can serve as promising target. RGD-based peptides containing arginine-glycine-aspartic acid tripeptide motif bind selectively to the $\alpha_v\beta_3$ integrin³. Here we investigate the influence of the length of the spacer between a polymer carrier and RGD, peptide structure and substitution of one amino acid in cyclic RGD motif on binding efficiency to the $\alpha_v\beta_3$ integrin.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Oligopeptides were prepared by conventional SPPS on TentaGel Rink amide resin or Wang resin using Fmoc-strategy. Oligopeptides were attached to the poly(*N*-(2-hydroxypropyl)methacrylamide) based (pHPMA) reactive polymer precursor labeled with fluorescent dye Cyanine 5.5 by copper-free click chemistry. Cell binding of the polymer-peptide conjugates was evaluated by flow cytometry using $\alpha_v\beta_3$ integrin receptor positive human glioblastoma cell line (U87-MG) and primary human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs). A statistical analysis was performed by one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnet's post-test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We have successfully prepared fluorescently labeled RGD-based oligopeptide conjugates including linear RGD with PEG4 or PEG12 spacer, branched RGD with PEG12, cyclic RGD and cyclic RGN with PEG4 or PEG12 spacer. Results from flow cytometry analysis showed that the length of the spacer significantly influenced binding affinity of oligopeptide conjugates to $\alpha_v\beta_3$ integrin. Surprisingly, substitution of aspartic acid with asparagine caused significant change in binding efficiency of cyclic RGD oligopeptides.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our results indicate that the length of the spacer and substitution of the one amino acid in cyclic RGD oligopeptide conjugates have strong influence on binding affinity to $\alpha_v\beta_3$ integrin receptor.

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Personalized nanomedicin for Non-Hodgkin lymphoma treatment

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INTRODUCTION

Therapeutic potential of nanomedicines such as drug delivery systems (DDS) could be supported by their active targeting.[1] Previously published targeted systems consisted of anti-CD20 monoclonal antibody (mAb) decorated with biocompatible polymer based on *N*-(2-hydroxypropyl)methacrylamide (HPMA) loaded with doxorubicin (Dox). The mAb anti-CD20 targeted polymer system showed somehow enhanced therapeutic potential for Non-Hodgkine lymphoma (NHL) therapy.[2] Because CD20 B-cell surface molecule is affected by first line drug therapy (including mAb anti-CD20 and Dox), thus anti-CD20 actively targeted DDS may lose its great therapeutic potential and alternative targeting should be established.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The aim of this study is synthesis of mAb actively-targeted high molecular weight “star-shape” nanomedicines and evaluation of their anti-lymphoma potential. Generally, the systems consist of monoclonal antibody (anti-CD19, anti-CD20, anti-CD38 and polyclonal IgG as a control) and semitelechelic linear *N*-(2-hydroxypropyl)methacrylamide based copolymers with Dox attached via a pH-labile hydrazone linkage. For *in vivo* activity evaluation, two Non-Hodgkin lymphoma PDX models were established from patient i) before and ii) after first line chemotherapy including the anti-CD20 antibody therapy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our DDS based on anti-CD38 monoclonal antibody showed superior anti-cancer therapy potential for tumour after the relapse with high potential as a second line therapeutic. We suggest personalized therapy based on tumour cell surface screening and using block building DDS system which can be easily synthesised based on individual tumour cell CD molecules profile.

CONCLUSION

mAb-targeted nanomedicines could be very efficient tool in the second line therapy of NHL after the relapse of the disease which become non-sensitive to the first line therapy drugs.

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Synthesis and characterization of new methotrexate derivatives containing divalent cations and their evaluation as bioactive compounds for musculoskeletal regeneration

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INTRODUCTION

Methotrexate (MTX) is considered as the first line treatment for rheumatoid arthritis (RA) due to its effectiveness, tolerability and reduced price¹. However, the complete regeneration of the damaged joints after the treatment is yet to be achieved². In this regard, divalent cations such as strontium, zinc and magnesium have been shown to promote musculoskeletal regeneration processes and can be easily coordinated with MTX providing synergic therapeutic activities³. For these reasons, the main objectives of the present work were synthesizing and characterizing by different physicochemical techniques novel methotrexate derivatives containing these divalent cations (M-MTX). In addition, some of these compounds were tested *in vitro* to analyse their potential use as musculoskeletal regenerative drugs. Finally, polymeric encapsulation and vehiculization of these drugs was performed.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Three different methotrexate derivatives were synthesized following a previously described analogous methodology for folate derivatives: strontium-, zinc- and magnesium-methotrexate derivatives⁴ (Fig. 1). The compounds were physicochemically characterized by ATR-FTIR, DSC, TGA, EDS and XRD. In addition, cytotoxicity of the different drugs was analysed in Raw264.7 cells and primary human chondrocytes-articular cultures by the alamar blue assay. Glycosaminoglycans deposition by M-MTX-treated chondrocytes was measured by the dimethylmethylene blue method. Anti-inflammatory properties of the synthesized compounds were studied by the Griess assay measuring NO release by LPS-activated macrophages. Furthermore, polymeric microparticles were synthesized by double emulsion followed by spray drying and their morphology, size dispersion and encapsulation efficacies were determined by SEM, Coulter and spectrophotometrically methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All the compounds were successfully synthesized in high yields (>95%) with no other co-precipitates. The obtained characterization results demonstrated a higher thermal stability of the complexes when compared with non-coordinated methotrexate due to the monodentate bond coordination between the methotrexate moiety and the cations.

Secondly, *in vitro* cell studies performed with methotrexate derivatives showed that zinc could prevent the methotrexate-related cytotoxic effects at determined doses in chondrocytes as well as it could decrease nitric oxide production by pro-inflammatory stimulated macrophages. On the other hand, strontium slightly increased the glycosaminoglycans deposition in the matrix while its cytotoxicity did not significantly vary when compared with non-complexed methotrexate. Finally, spray-dried microparticles containing methotrexate derivatives were synthesized (Fig. 2) achieving encapsulation efficacies above 70%. MTX derivatives were released within three days through a mechanism based on opened particles.

Fig 1. Scheme of the reaction conditions for methotrexate-derivatives syntheses.

Fig 2. SrMTX-loaded spray-dried microparticles.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this work serves as a proof-of-concept for future studies focused on musculoskeletal regeneration due to use of methotrexate bearing bioactive divalent cations and their interesting biological properties and their possibility to be encapsulated in microparticles.

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Approach to Sterilization of Implantable Device for Therapeutic Delivery

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INTRODUCTION

Implants intended for therapeutics deliver should fulfil essential requirements, such as mechanical and chemical stability in physiological environment during treatment of a disease or during their lifespan, and then be explanted or gradually degraded. In order to guarantee proper operation of such systems, especially in the case of their complex configuration or multifunctional tasks of the implant (e.g. active medical devices), besides selection of biomaterials and involved manufacturing processes, the designer should also consider potential sterilization method. Academia scientist involved in early stage development of systems delivering therapeutics often overlook potentially detrimental effect of sterilization on material properties or sophisticated components of the device, e.g. embedded electronics. Though, the sterilization by a validated method is indispensable when it comes to commercialization of the new device.

Validation of selected sterilization technique in terms of its effectiveness, reliability and reproducibility is the prerequisite the manufacturer demonstrates to the notifying authorities in order to prove microbiological safety of the device.¹ Reduction of the bioburden on and in the device to Sterility Assurance Level (SAL) 10^{-6} is required.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The theoretical approach to selection of potentially applicable sterilization methods is based on the knowledge of properties of the polymeric materials comprising the device of bio-electronic implant intended for therapeutics delivery from genetically engineered cells stimulated by light, the complexity of its design and presence of sensitive components or subsystems (Fig. 1²). The device should be provided sterile for cells loading, therefore terminal sterilization of manufactured implant or aseptic processing of pre-sterilized components may be applied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Approach to selection of a sterilization technique should begin on screening materials, components and systems included comprising the device. If all of those can withstand high temperature, a dry hot air (160-200°C) or moisturised air (steam, 121°C) methods may be the first choice. The complex shapes and inner elements are also heated, thus the device is entirely sterilized. The method is in principle restricted for thermoplastics, and unsuitable for biodegradable polymers. Encompassed electronics as well as the presence of optically functional polymers – opacity may occur, eliminate thermal methods of sterilization. As only low-temperature methods are acceptable, radiation may be considered. Either electron beam or gamma rays are highly penetrable and provide sterility of the entire implant, not only its surface, which is especially appropriate for complicated shapes or highly porous materials. Nevertheless, the energy may cause polymer degradation, which reduces applicability of this method. Besides, radiation induces severe deterioration of embedded electronics (thermal annealing may restore operation). Plasma-hydrogen peroxide may be considered, and applied as effective surface sterilization method. One should take under consideration rise of the temperature (40-60°C) and pressure changes during the process. Surfaces not resistant to highly oxidative environment may be altered. In general, it can be applied to electronic systems. Yet, ISO standards have not been developed for plasma method. The other option is the ethylene oxide (EO) sterilization, utilized for polymers and combined materials. Since the method can be applied for optics and electronics it was selected for current optogenetic implant. Beside minor temperature rise (35-65°C) and rapid pressure changes, a dissolution of the gas (highly toxic) in the polymeric biomaterial and possible chemical reactions with the polymer should be examined in details.

Fig 1. Concept of wireless-powered cell-based implant for therapeutic delivery.²

CONCLUSION

The course of selection of potentially applicable sterilization methods for bio-electronic implantable device for therapeutics delivery was presented. Validation of those methods, particularly EO, is done experimentally through evaluating possible alternation of physical and chemical properties of the implant, and biocompatibility assessment.

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Study of biological fluids adsorption by surgical fibers

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INTRODUCTION

An important part in a surgical procedure is choosing the adequate fiber based on the balance between the physico-chemical properties of fibers and the characteristics of involved tissue. The physician selects the type of fiber that is the most suitable for the surgical procedure, regarding the kind of surrounding tissue. A poor choice of suture fibers that ignores the biological interactions between the material's surface and the biological environment can determine various postoperative complications such as infection, wound disruption and formation of chronic sinus tracts¹. Usually, polymeric sutures made of polyamide and polypropylene are used for general soft tissue closure². The purpose of this study is to make a comparison of different fibers adsorption at the interface with fluids presented near the wound closure. Work of adhesion evaluation is presented as a measure of adhesion properties.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Adhesion properties of a certain biological fluids onto cylindrical surface are evaluated by sessile drop method based on Contact Angle Measurement (CAM). Adequate homemade experimental arrangements have been used for measuring *in vitro* contact angle between different liquids and polymeric fibers. In this paper, non-absorbable (polyamide and polypropylene) commercial suture fibers (from Demophorius Healthcare Ltd.) with a diameter of 5 UPS size (0.14 mm) have been selected for their different chemistries. The testing liquids are distilled water, Ringer's solution and glycerol, based on their similarities to the fluids found in the human body. The volume of drops used in determining the contact angle was 1 μ l, at this value gravity being neglected. The contact angle was obtained as an average of tens of measurements performed at room conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The interface between fibers and adjacent tissues is very complex due to the double sense of exchange of ions, enzymes, proteins or even bacteria. Classical CAM method applied to fibers is accompanied by errors due to the different geometry of a drop placed on cylindrical surfaces and it requires a rigorous mathematical approach starting from the Young-Laplace equation³. We used a practical method to evaluate the contact angle and the work of adhesion of polymeric fibers. Also, supplementary experiments are performed regarding the influence of temperature of body fluids and the variation of pH correlated with the diverse locations of wounds.

CONCLUSION

Comparative studies of fibers-fluids interface demand many experimental measurements correlated with rigorous calculations based on Young-Laplace equation.

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The influence of volume fraction on the microstructure and physical properties of zirconia produced with polymer suspensions by the additive manufacturing

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INTRODUCTION

Zirconia can be manufactured by the mixture of ceramic powder, dispersants and some other additive agents for the suspensions. In recent years, newly polymer composite materials and engineered with CAD/CAM technique have been widely applied in the dentistry. Due to the agglomeration occurring among the ceramic powder with their large specific surface leading to flaws in productions easily, adding polymer is one of the effective methods to decrease the surface energy and agglomeration ratio. Polymer can also enhance ceramic particle uniform dispersion in the organic solvent to obtain the higher mechanical character. To create new ceramic, some advanced techniques have been introduced for ceramic powder by plasma polymerization. But it is still lack of the information on the additive polymer in zirconia fabricated by the additive manufacturing method. This study was to analyze the influence of volume fraction on the microstructure and physical properties of zirconia produced with polymer suspensions by the additive manufacturing.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Zirconia specimens fabricated by additive manufacturing technique using a DLP (digital light processing) system. The zirconia suspensions were divided into six groups in the range of 48–58 vol% zirconia volume fraction. The printed specimens were measured in terms of viscosity, 3-point bending strength and microstructural analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A highest viscosity was measured at the highest volume fraction of 58 vol%. It is very important to increase the dispersibility of suspension using optimized materials. The highest mechanical property was measured in the group of volume fraction of 58 vol%. Cracks increased in number as zirconia volume fraction decreased. The relative density increased as the volume fraction increased. Photo polymers and dispersants within the solid product acted as impurities and might have formed porous structures during the debinding and sintering processes, thus affecting the bending strength.

CONCLUSION

58 vol% was the maximum volume fraction possible for additive manufacturing. After polymerization, all specimens showed some distortion by geometrical overgrowth. The maximum strength of sintered zirconia by additive manufacturing had inferior physical properties than that of sintered zirconia by milling.

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Edge sharpness of geometric microcavity enhances contractility and osteogenesis of mesenchymal stem cells via ROCK signaling

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INTRODUCTION

Mesenchymal stem cell (MSC) is a promising cell source for tissue regeneration not only attributed to its differentiation but also its migration capacity, which relies on the cytoskeleton remodeling and contractile force generation^{1,2}. MSCs are highly sensitive to structural cues from their local environment such as surface topography³. Traditional applied "adhesive island" system for topographical studies could regulate cellular behavior by various geometric factors including the size, aspect ratio, edge sharpness and local curvature^{4,6}. However, such 2D patterns forced cells to form flattened morphology, isolated cells and restricted cell migration. The 2.5D microcavity system has been widely used to generate cells and colonies with defined sizes and spatial shapes⁷. To date, there is still limited understanding of the geometric shape and local edge sharpness change of microcavities on altering MSC functions and fate.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Polystyrene-based inserts with microstructured bottom surfaces for 24-well cell culture plate were created via injection molding. The cell migration, morphology, contractility, osteogenesis and the underlying intracellular signaling were investigated via applying immunostaining, chemical dye, collagen gel and pharmaceutical inhibitors. Data were presented as mean ± standard deviation and analyzed by two-tailed independent t-test. $p < 0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initially after seeding, MSCs were preferentially rolled into the cavities on microstructured substrates, and cells migrated along the microcavities without physical constrains post spreading (Fig. A). Extended actin stress fibers were observed at the corners during cell migration into the cubic cavity (B). The cell morphologies were three-dimensionally modulated by the local curvature change of cell membrane in response to the geometric shape of microcavity. The focal adhesions were concentrated at the corner area of cubic microcavity, while the cylinder group showed a random focal adhesion distribution along the circumference (C). The substrate with cubic microcavities enhanced cell contractility (squeezed cell-laden collagen gel) and calcium deposition (ARS dye) during osteogenesis (D, E). In consistency with the findings from the previous study that cells generated high contractile force and differentiate into osteoblasts on 2D star patterns containing sharp corners⁵. Such microcavity shape-dependent modulatory effect was mediated by ROCK kinase (D-F), which involved in controlling of cytoskeleton assembly and cell contractility⁸. Following ROCK inhibition, the different contractility and osteogenesis between cells on microstructured substrates comprising cubic and cylinder cavities were diminished (D, E). These results highlight the possibility to control the cellular function of stem cells through adjusting edge sharpness and local curvature of culture vessels.

CONCLUSION

Without forcing cell to form flattened morphology and restricting cell migration, the 2.5D geometry regulated spatial distribution of focal adhesion, actin cytoskeleton remodeling, contractility and osteogenesis of MSCs. These findings

indicate that the distinct edge sharpness and local curvature of cubic and cylinder microcavities can be a potential trigger involved in modulating stem cell cellular response. Our system bridges the gap between 2D cell cultures and 3D micro-engineered matrices and provides the basis for surface design of various cell-laden and cell-free implants.

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Luminiscent chitosan-based silver nanoclusters with photothermal activity

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have attained great scientific interest due to technological potential offered by their electronic, mechanical, magnetic, optical, chemical and antimicrobial properties.¹ But also, as the dimensions of these AgNPs are further reduced to sub-nanometer scale ($\leq 1-2$ nm), new molecular properties appear as photophysical properties.² These named silver nanoclusters (AgNCs) exhibit important advantages compared to other luminescent NPs, such as their availability, low cost, high biocompatibility which makes them useful as new therapeutic and diagnostic systems.³

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Hybrid Ch@AgNCs were obtained by *in situ* photochemically reduction and simultaneously functionalized with chitosan (multi-amino natural polysaccharide) as unique ligand stabilizer using UV irradiation in the presence of a photoinitiator, in presence and absence of oxygen. The reactions were monitored by both UV/Vis and Fluorescence spectroscopy by recording the increase of the Ag surface plasmon absorption band (410–430 nm) and emission one (620 nm).

To study the photothermal efficiency of synthesized Ch@AgNCs, hybrid NPs dispersed in water were exposed to the light of 808 nm laser emitting at 44 mW/mm² and temperature changes were monitored by infrared thermography. The particle size distribution was studied by dynamic light scattering (DLS). Morphology of hybrid AgNPs was analyzed by Scanning- (sTEM) and cryo-Transmission Electron Microscopy (cryoTEM). Finally, the evaluation of the cytotoxicity of nanoparticles samples was determined human dermal fibroblasts using the *Alamar Blue* (AB) assay.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The procedure involves the photochemical activation of the photoinitiator with UVA light (365 nm) to yield free ketyl radicals, which act as reducing agent toward the silver ions precursor (AgNO₃) in the presence of the amino groups of the chitosan. Then, AgNCs can be photogenerated, stabilized and coated by the biopolymer in one-step. The characteristic absorption and emission spectra obtained with UV-irradiation time indicate the generation of AgNCs in our systems (Figure 1). Synthesis of hybrid AgNCs was possible in the presence or absence of oxygen in the aqueous medium that indicated the versatility of the methodology followed.

Figure 1. UV/Vis spectra of the hybrid Ch@AgNPs diluted solutions and its evolution with respect to UV-irradiation.

Figure 2. Cryo-TEM images of Ch@AgNCs.

In general, the fluorescence emission and the absorbance provides the same behavior, an emission intensity increases with the irradiation time. This behavior is more marked and faster in the hybrids obtained in medium depleted of oxygen, while the reactions performed in the presence of this element showed less fluorescence emission regardless of the application time of UV light.

The size distribution of the obtained nanohybrids showed a monomodal distribution with a diameter in DLS around 50 nm, in agreement with the images obtained by sTEM and cryo-TEM (Figure 2), showing independent NPs of spherical morphology without the formation of large aggregates.

Moreover, all samples of AgNPs obtained were cytocompatible when they were administered to human dermal fibroblasts in a concentration below 100 µg/mL

CONCLUSION

The luminescent nanohybrids using chitosan as template for the photogeneration of AgNCs will be have multifunctional behavior (fluorescence and antibacterial and antifungal properties) and their incorporation in this type of biocompatible supports could be applied in regenerative medicine as dressing for the treatment of compromised cutaneous wounds (ulcers, burns, etc.).

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